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Consumer preferences for disease-resistant wine: Implications from thematic and latent Dirichlet allocation analyses

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Abstract

This study explores consumer perceptions and attitudes toward disease-resistant wine varieties (DRGVs) in terms of packaging, labeling, and communication strategies. As the wine industry emphasizes more on sustainability, disease-resistant grape varieties emerge as a compelling solution to reduce fungicide use, production costs, and environmental impact. However, consumer acceptance of these innovative wines remains unknown, which makes an in-depth understanding of consumer behavior necessary. Employing qualitative data from 500 participants, the research utilized latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) for topic modeling and thematic analysis to investigate the underlying factors driving wine purchases and perceptions of DRGVs.

Key results and insights

Consumer motivations for wine purchases

Consumers often base purchasing decisions on the wine's ability to enhance experiences, health perceptions, and meal pairings. Additionally, gifting, relaxation, and special occasions were significant motivators. Labels that highlight these motivations, such as meal pairing suggestions or health benefits (where permissible), may effectively capture consumer interest.

Visual appeal and packaging design

Labels act as the primary interface between the product and the consumer. Preferences for visually attractive, clean, and modern designs emerged as a consistent trend. However, design preferences varied, with some favoring traditional and refined aesthetics and others preferring bold and colorful labels. Consumers also valued imagery reflecting the wine's origin, such as vineyards or regional landscapes, and practical packaging features like screw caps or unique bottle designs.

Sustainability as a selling point

While sustainability was a favorable attribute, consumers were particularly drawn to pesticide reduction and the perceived health benefits of disease-resistant wines. However, the term "disease-resistant" elicited mixed reactions, with some finding it off-putting. Alternative terminologies emphasizing strength, sustainability, or eco-friendliness could better align with consumer expectations.

Barriers to adoption

Challenges such as unfamiliarity, choice overload, and concerns about taste and quality deter consumers from trying new wine varieties. Strategies like smaller sample sizes, taste guarantees, and transparent communication on labels can mitigate these barriers.

Effective labeling strategies

Participants emphasized the importance of clear and informative labeling, particularly for new wine varieties. Key elements included flavor descriptions, health-related information, and environmental benefits. Awards and accolades on labels also significantly influenced purchasing decisions, increasing confidence in product quality.

Methodology and analysis

The study leveraged open-ended surveys distributed to a representative sample of U.S. wine consumers via Qualtrics. Thematic analysis and LDA modeling were used to explore patterns in the

qualitative data. This dual approach ensured a robust understanding of consumer attitudes and allowed for the identification of actionable insights.

Implications for the wine industry

The study offers actionable insights for winemakers and marketers on how to introduce sustainable wine varieties. By emphasizing positive attributes, employing consumer-friendly terminology, and addressing barriers to adoption, producers can foster greater consumer acceptance of DRGVs. Additionally, appealing to consumers' desire for transparency, health-consciousness, and visual aesthetics can further align marketing strategies with evolving preferences.

Tailoring the content strategies of food advertisements to healthy food: An empirical exploration

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Abstract

This study examines the real-world application and impact of advertising content strategies in TV food advertisements, focusing on their differential effects on healthy and unhealthy food products. Specifically, we explore how food healthiness influences the use of advertising attributes, values, and appeals, as well as the interaction between advertising content strategies and consumer price and promotion sensitivity. Our findings contribute to the literature on food advertising and offer practical implications for improving consumer response to healthy food advertisements.

Our research makes three key contributions. First, we expand the food advertising literature by empirically analyzing how advertising content strategies vary across food categories and their impact on market response. Prior studies have acknowledged the differing effects of advertising on healthy versus unhealthy foods, but a comprehensive understanding of advertising content strategies and their effectiveness using real sales data was lacking. We address this gap by examining sixteen advertising content strategies, categorized into three broad groups, and their respective influences on consumer behavior. Second, in contrast to prior research that largely relies on experimental methods, we leverage actual sales data to provide a more robust and generalizable analysis. Third, our study is the first to explore how different advertising content strategies interact with other marketing elements, such as price and in-store promotions, shedding light on the indirect impacts of advertising on food sales.

Our findings reveal that advertising content strategies have mixed effects on sales for both healthy and unhealthy food products. While some content strategies directly enhance sales, others may indirectly reduce sales by influencing price and promotion sensitivities. Notably, certain advertising strategies consistently produce either positive or negative effects. For example, for healthy food products, emphasizing mouthfeel attributes and the value of social affiliation lowers price sensitivity, leading to better sales performance. Highlighting convenience in healthy food ads reduces price sensitivity but increases promotion sensitivity compared to unhealthy food ads. In contrast, for unhealthy food products, emphasizing convenience tends to boost sales while reducing price sensitivity. Advertising the ingredients and innovativeness of unhealthy foods, however, increases price sensitivity while decreasing sensitivity to promotions.

A key insight from our analysis is that emphasizing health- and fitness-related characteristics, such as naturalness and freshness, may harm the sales of healthy food products. One possible explanation is that consumers perceive health-related claims for healthy foods as redundant, thereby reducing the effectiveness of such advertising. This finding suggests that health-benefit messaging may inadvertently lower consumer demand by increasing price sensitivity and diminishing promotional effectiveness. Our analysis also highlights that these ineffective strategies are frequently used in advertising for healthy food products, underscoring the need for marketers to reassess their approach.

This study provides a framework for content analysis of food advertisements, demonstrating that the effects of advertising content differ between healthy and unhealthy foods. Future research should explore other media formats beyond TV commercials and help establish a more comprehensive understanding of how advertising content influences food sales across different platforms.

Building trust: Consumer awareness, acceptance and attitudes related to European aquaculture and the potential effects of greenwashing

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Abstract

Greenwashing is a major challenge for the promotion of sustainable markets. This study examines consumer segmentation and preferences about farmed fish, with a focus on understanding consumer behaviour regarding greenwashing and its impact on perceptions.

The study utilized a cross-sectional online survey conducted in 2019, gathering responses from 2500 participants across the UK, France, Spain, Germany, and Italy. Its focus was to investigate European consumers' awareness, attitudes, and acceptance regarding aquaculture production methods. The results of cluster analysis identify three different consumer profiles that offer valuable insights for experts and policy makers. Moreover, findings show that consumers are concerned about the prevalence of greenwashing in sustainability communication in European aquaculture production. Despite a generally positive attitude and acceptance, the respondents' overall awareness of the various production systems is low.

As far as we know, this is the first study to analyse consumer behaviour towards aquaculture taking into consideration the potential effects of greenwashing, helping to enrich the economic literature.

Veganism and gen z in the midwest U.S.: Consumer perceptions, barriers, and market opportunities

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Abstract

As plant-based diets gain global traction, understanding the perceptions and behaviors of young consumers is essential for businesses and policymakers. This study explores the motivations and barriers influencing vegan adoption among Generation Z (Gen Z) college students in the Midwestern United States. Using preliminary survey data from 149 students at a Midwestern public university, we examine the key factors shaping attitudes toward veganism. The findings reveal a mix of ethical, environmental, and cultural drivers behind interest in plant-based diets, as well as significant barriers related to taste, social acceptance, and accessibility. Expanding on previous research, this study incorporates both qualitative and quantitative analyses to provide a deeper understanding of how cultural background and regional food traditions shape dietary choices. The role of taste preferences, affordability concerns, and accessibility of plant-based options are explored in greater detail, drawing insights from behavioral psychology and food marketing literature. This research aims to inform food industry strategies, policy recommendations, and marketing campaigns targeted at increasing plant-based product adoption in traditionally meat-centric regions.

Introduction

The food industry is rapidly evolving, driven by growing concerns over climate change, health, and animal welfare (Beck et al. 2021, Khan et al. 2023, Poore & Nemecek, 2018). Veganism and plant-based diets have seen increased acceptance in urban centers, yet adoption remains limited in the Midwestern United States, where agricultural traditions deeply influence food culture. Meat and dairy products are central to regional diets, and the economic significance of animal agriculture further reinforces consumption patterns. According to Gheihman (2021), veganism has transitioned from a niche social movement to a mainstream lifestyle movement, reshaping consumer habits in various regions.

Generation Z has emerged as a key demographic shaping food trends, with increased awareness of sustainability and ethical food production (Forbes, 2023). Despite this, many young consumers in the Midwest face barriers that prevent them from fully embracing plant-based diets. Research indicates that 13% of Gen Z identify as flexitarian, reducing meat consumption but not eliminating it entirely (Gheihman, 2021). This study investigates the primary motivations for and obstacles to vegan adoption among Gen Z college students.

Research Methodology

This study utilized a mixed-methods research approach, combining quantitative survey data and qualitative insights from Generation Z (Gen Z) college students in the Midwestern United States. A structured survey was distributed to 149 undergraduate students at a Midwestern public university, allowing for an in-depth examination of their perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors related to veganism. This methodology was designed to explore both broad statistical trends and individual perspectives, providing a holistic understanding of the factors influencing plant-based dietary choices.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following research questions:

What are the primary motivations influencing Generation Z college students in the Midwestern United States to consider a vegan lifestyle?

What are the key barriers preventing Gen Z college students from fully adopting a vegan diet?

How do cultural and social influences shape Gen Z's perception of plant-based eating in the Midwestern United States?

How does accessibility and affordability impact the willingness of Gen Z students to incorporate more plant-based foods into their diets?

Data Collection

This study was conducted following approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to ensure ethical standards were met. Data was collected using Qualtrics, a widely used online survey platform, which facilitated the integration of both quantitative and qualitative responses. Participants were recruited through multiple channels to ensure a diverse sample. The survey was distributed through the university's Learning Management System (LMS), allowing direct access to students enrolled in various courses. Additionally, the snowball sampling method was employed, where initial participants were encouraged to share the survey with their peers, expanding the reach to a broader student population. This approach helped in gathering a more representative dataset of Generation Z students from different academic disciplines and backgrounds. The survey was structured to capture a wide range of factors influencing dietary choices, including: The survey was designed to capture a wide range of factors influencing dietary choices.

Data Analysis

A combination of descriptive statistical analysis and thematic coding of qualitative responses was used to assess consumer attitudes. Mean comparisons were conducted to identify the most influential motivations and barriers to vegan adoption. Correlation assessments were performed to determine whether specific factors, such as growing up in rural areas versus urban areas, had a significant impact on perceptions of plant-based eating. Qualitative responses were analyzed using an inductive thematic approach to highlight recurring themes related to cultural identity, food traditions, and social acceptance.

Results

Motivations for considering veganism

The results indicate that ethical and environmental concerns were the strongest motivators for Gen Z students considering a plant-based diet. The highest-rated motivation was animal rights (M=4.17), with students expressing concern over factory farming practices and animal welfare. Many respondents mentioned exposure to documentaries and social media campaigns that highlighted the mistreatment of animals in industrial farming, reinforcing their inclination toward plant-based eating.

Cultural influences (M=4.02) also played a significant role, with some students citing exposure to plant-based diets through family traditions, religious beliefs, or social movements as factors influencing their openness to veganism. For instance, some participants with backgrounds in Jainism, Hinduism, or Seventh-day Adventism reported an existing familiarity with vegetarianism or plant-based eating, making the transition to veganism seem more feasible. Social movements promoting sustainable and ethical consumption, such as the rise of "Meatless Monday" initiatives and online activism, also contributed to shaping students' perceptions.

Environmental concerns (M=3.92) were another key driver, with students recognizing the impact of industrial animal farming on climate change, greenhouse gas emissions, and resource depletion. Many respondents acknowledged the role of factory farming in deforestation, excessive water consumption, and pollution, aligning with previous research that identifies climate concerns as a motivating factor for younger consumers considering plant-based diets (Poore & Nemecek, 2018). However, qualitative responses revealed some skepticism about whether individual dietary choices could significantly impact environmental issues, highlighting the need for stronger public education on the subject.

Health and nutrition (M=3.64) were rated slightly lower, suggesting that while students acknowledge the potential health benefits of plant-based eating, ethical and cultural considerations were more compelling. Students who cited health as a reason for considering veganism often referenced

perceived benefits such as improved digestion, reduced risk of chronic diseases, and weight management. However, others expressed concern about misinformation surrounding vegan diets and whether they could provide adequate nutrients such as protein, iron, and vitamin B12. The results indicate that ethical and environmental concerns were the strongest motivators for Gen Z students considering a plant-based diet. The highest-rated motivation was animal rights (M=4.17), with students expressing concern over factory farming practices and animal welfare. Cultural influences (M=4.02) also played a significant role, with some students citing exposure to plant-based diets through family traditions, religious beliefs, or social movements as factors influencing their openness to veganism. Environmental concerns (M=3.92) were another key driver, with students recognizing the impact of industrial animal farming on climate change and resource depletion. Health and nutrition (M=3.64) were rated slightly lower, suggesting that while students acknowledge the potential health benefits of plant-based eating, ethical and cultural considerations were more compelling.

Barriers to vegan adoption

Despite growing awareness and interest, several barriers prevented students from fully adopting a vegan diet. The most significant challenge reported was taste preferences (M=3.98), with many respondents indicating that they found plant-based alternatives less satisfying or unfamiliar. Several students noted that traditional Midwestern diets emphasize rich, savory flavors found in meats and dairy products, making plant-based substitutes seem less appealing in comparison. Some respondents expressed a preference for familiar textures and flavors, stating that current plant-based meat and dairy alternatives do not yet fully replicate the taste of animal products. Concerns over protein and nutrition (M=3.93) were also prominent, highlighting the persistent perception that vegan diets may lack essential nutrients. While some respondents acknowledged the availability of plant-based protein sources such as tofu, legumes, and quinoa, others remained skeptical about whether these foods could adequately replace meat in terms of protein content and overall satiety. A lack of knowledge about vegan nutrition and dietary planning contributed to hesitation among some participants, emphasizing the need for targeted educational initiatives. High price/cost (M=3.73) was frequently cited, particularly among students with limited financial resources who viewed plant-based products as more expensive than traditional meat and dairy options. Many respondents noted that plant-based alternatives were often priced higher at grocery stores and on-campus dining facilities, making them less accessible to students on tight budgets. This aligns with previous research indicating that perceived affordability remains a significant barrier to plant-based diet adoption (Makowska et al., 2024). Limited accessibility (M=3.62) was another notable barrier, as many respondents mentioned difficulty finding plant-based meals at campus dining facilities or local grocery stores. Several students reported that their university's meal plan offered limited vegan options, making it difficult to maintain a plant-based diet consistently. In rural areas, access to diverse plant-based ingredients was seen as even more challenging, with some students stating that grocery stores in their hometowns had few or no vegan alternatives available. Finally, social judgment (M=3.14) emerged as a factor, with some students reluctant to adopt a vegan diet due to peer pressure or fear of being perceived as "preachy" or different. Many respondents mentioned that social gatherings, particularly in Midwestern communities where meat-centric meals are a staple, made it difficult to maintain a vegan diet without drawing unwanted attention or having to justify their choices to others. Additionally, concerns about being labeled as "extreme" or "difficult" in social situations discouraged some participants from fully transitioning to plant-based eating. These findings highlight the multifaceted nature of vegan adoption barriers, underscoring the importance of addressing taste, affordability, accessibility, and social acceptance in efforts to promote plant-based diets among Gen Z students in the Midwestern United States.

Discussion

Findings suggest that while Gen Z students in the Midwest recognize the benefits of plant-based diets, adoption remains low due to concerns over taste, cost, and availability. Many respondents reported growing up in households where meat was a staple, reinforcing cultural norms around animal-based diets. Taste preferences (M=3.98) were a primary deterrent, with students expressing skepticism toward plant-based alternatives. Concerns over protein intake (M=3.93) and the perceived high cost of vegan products (M=3.73) also influenced resistance to dietary change. Additionally, geographic

factors played a role. Students in urban areas with access to plant-based grocery stores and restaurants were more likely to consider veganism compared to those in rural communities with fewer options. Campus dining services also influenced decisions, as students noted limited availability of well-balanced plant-based meals at their university. Economic constraints further shaped dietary habits, with students identifying plant-based products as expensive compared to traditional meat options. Despite these barriers, ethical and environmental concerns emerged as key motivators. Animal rights (M=4.17) and environmental sustainability (M=3.92) were highly rated motivations, aligning with previous studies emphasizing Gen Z's commitment to social responsibility. However, many students lacked clear information on nutritional adequacy, leading to misconceptions about plant-based diets. To increase adoption, food marketers should focus on improving the taste and affordability of plant-based products, ensuring accessibility in Midwest markets. Campaigns emphasizing culturally familiar, budget-friendly plant-based meals may help bridge resistance. Additionally, universities could implement educational initiatives to address misconceptions about plant-based nutrition and offer greater plant-based dining options.

Conclusion, limitations, and future research

This study provides preliminary insights into the factors influencing vegan adoption among Gen Z college students in the Midwestern United States. Ethical and environmental concerns are strong motivators, yet practical challenges such as taste, price, and accessibility continue to deter many potential adopters. The findings suggest that cultural norms and regional food traditions significantly impact dietary choices, making it essential for food marketers, policymakers, and educators to develop strategies that align plant-based eating with existing social and economic realities.

Limitations of the research

While this study offers valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the sample size of 149 students, though informative, is relatively small and limited to one Midwestern public university, which may not fully represent the broader Gen Z population in the region. Future studies should include a more diverse and larger sample size across multiple institutions to increase generalizability. Second, the study relied on self-reported survey data, which is inherently subject to response bias. Third, while the study examined quantitative and qualitative responses, deeper insights could be gained through in-depth interviews or focus groups to further explore students' perceptions of plant-based diets. A qualitative approach could reveal more nuanced cultural and psychological barriers to vegan adoption that may not be fully captured through survey methods alone. Lastly, geographic limitations must be considered. While the study focuses on the Midwestern United States, plant-based diet adoption varies across different regions due to economic, cultural, and social factors. Comparative studies between the Midwest and other regions (e.g., the West Coast or Northeast, where plant-based diets are more widely accepted) would provide a richer understanding of the regional variations in consumer behavior.

Future research directions

Future research should explore how different marketing strategies influence Gen Z consumers' perceptions of plant-based diets, particularly in regions where meat consumption is deeply ingrained. Additionally, examining the role of food technology, such as lab-grown meat and plant-based alternatives, could provide insights into consumer acceptance and market potential. Policy interventions, including plant-based food subsidies and university dining hall initiatives, should be studied to assess their effectiveness in increasing plant-based food adoption. Investigating the impact of peer influence, social media trends, and community engagement may also help identify strategies for making vegan diets more appealing to young consumers. Finally, longitudinal studies tracking dietary shifts over time would provide valuable data on whether Gen Z maintains interest in plant-based diets as they transition into different life stages and economic circumstances.

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Developments and disruptions in consumers' co-creation of food quality

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Abstract

Food quality is the outcome of a co-creation process where consumers and marketers employ their respective resources and competences (Akaka & Vargo, 2012). This co-creation is pervasive throughout the food customer journey. Thus, when buying, cooking and eating, food consumers employ a broad set of resources, e.g. cognitive, social and financial, to co-create the food qualities they prefer.

While economic, social and other macro trends make their incremental marks on consumer's food related practices and preferences, market disruptions may have instantaneous impacts. Hence, data collected post hoc have shown that while the Covid 19 lockdowns implied increases in consumer interest in natural foods, healthiness, home cooking and online food purchasing, the inflationary pressures, spurred by the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, increased price sensitivity and spurred more deliberate food buying and cooking practices (Grunert et al, 2023)

With an outset in data from 10 yearly surveys and a conceptualization of food quality as the outcome of consumer-marketer co-creation this presentation traces developments in a set of indicators for Danish food consumer's cooking practices, willingness to pay and food satisfaction before and after the Covid (2020) and Inflationary (2022) disruptions.

The conceptual model is estimated for the full sample as well as for three segments: 'the Quality Minded', 'the Moderate Majority' and 'the Uncommitted' food consumers; for which developments in the mentioned indicators are then compared. The segmentation is based on a Latent Class model, which is shown to be dynamically stable before and after the years (2020 and 2022) of disruption.

Based on a set of Generalized Linear models, with the mentioned indicators as dependent variables, and disruption dummies (2020 and 2022), the segments and the interactions between dummies and segments as independent variables, it is shown the 2020 lockdown impacted on all indicators. Thus, in 2020 positive changes were observed for: satisfaction (especially for the Uncommitted segment) and WtP, and negative changes in the indicators for cooking practices (especially for the Quality Conscious). In 2022 there were no changes in food satisfaction and cooking practices, but a negative development in the WtP of all consumers, were observed. Potential implications for food marketers and policymakers are discussed.

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Advancing sustainability through circular product design in the blue-green bioeconomy

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Abstract

Advancing sustainability in the bioeconomy requires innovative approaches that connect blue and green bioeconomies through circular product design. While both the blue and green bioeconomies hold significant potential on their own, efforts to integrate them within a cohesive circular framework remain underdeveloped. Existing strategies often fall short in effectively utilizing waste streams and by-products from both aquatic and terrestrial resources. This perspective explores how circular product design can drive the integration of blue and green bioeconomies, drawing on insights from case studies focused on sustainable food and feed production. Through this lens, we identify four key 'crystallization points' that offer strategic opportunities to overcome traditional divides between marine and land-based bioresources, supporting their convergence within an interconnected circular system. These insights contribute to a broader understanding of cross-sector resource synergies and highlight pathways toward a more resilient, efficient, and sustainable bioeconomy.

Lack of consumer trust: The double barrier in the green transition of the food sector

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Abstract

A lack of consumer trust in food chain actors can have the consequence that even consumers that are motivated to make healthy and sustainable choices are actually not trying to do so, thus impeding the adoption of new healthy and sustainable products. Previous research has identified more openness of food chain actors as a way to increase trust, but when consumer do not trust food chain actors increased transparency by these may by itself be met with suspicion and be viewed as examples of greenwashing or other unethical practices.

Using survey data from the EIT Food Trust Tracker, collected in 2024 in 18 European countries with a sample size of 18,000, we analyze whether a lack of trust indeed decreases willingness to try new products like cellmeat, dairy based on precision fermentation or insect-based food. We find that trust indeed in most cases moderates the relationship between motivation for healthy and sustainable choices and willingness to try these products, and in some cases even may invert the direction of the relationship. We also find that a lack of trust decreases confidence in information sources about food, and that this also applies to information sources normally regarded as neutral, as scientists and medical professionals. We close with proposal for how this double barrier of low trust can be mitigated.

Quality, price, or trends? Understanding Swedish seafood consumer segments

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Abstract

Introduction

This study examines the variation in fish consumption among Swedish consumers by segmenting them based on decision-making styles and profiling them using individual characteristics. Consumer decision-making styles (Eom et al., 2020; Sproles & Kendall, 1986) reflect consistent cognitive and behavioral orientations in purchasing, such as quality-consciousness, price-sensitivity, and impulsiveness. While widely applied across various markets (Khare, 2016; Makgosa & Sangodoyin, 2018; Rašković et al., 2020; Tarnanidis et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2010, adaptations of the Consumer Styles Inventory (CSI) to food contexts (Anić, et al., 2014; Eriksson and Stenius, 2024) indicate that decision styles are category-specific and complement psychosocial models like the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which focuses on attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 2015; Birch & Lawley, 2014; Conner et al., 2002; Honkanen et al., 2005; Olsen, 2001, 2003; Verbeke & Vackier, 2005).

A decision-styles perspective offers a different yet complementary lens: rather than focusing on *why* consumers intend to buy seafood products (e.g., TPB), it examines *how* they characteristically navigate choices (e.g., by habit, by deliberation on quality, by looking for novelty), which can fundamentally shape their actual purchase decisions ((Hanzaee and Aghasibeig, 2008; Klein and Sharma, 2018; Rašković et al., 2020).

Despite Sweden's strong sustainability focus, little research has explored seafood consumption through a decision-making styles lens. Existing studies primarily address general attitudes rather than holistic purchasing behaviors (Armbrecht et al., 2023; Skallerud et al., 2021). This study fills that gap by applying the CDMS framework to segment Swedish seafood consumers, providing insights into how they balance purchasing drivers. Understanding these segments is valuable for marketers, policymakers, and sustainability advocates aiming to promote sustainable seafood choices. The study is guided by two research questions:

Which consumer segments can be identified based on decision-making styles?

How do these segments differ regarding TPB constructs, food involvement (FI), environmental awareness (EA), fish consumption and shopping behaviors, and socio-demographic factors?

Methodology

The Laboratory of Opinion Research (LORE) at Gothenburg University collected all data. The research is based on The Citizen Panel. In total, the panel includes more than 60,000 active participants. A probability sample (n = 3,600) stratified according to age, gender, and education is used, of which 2,207 participants (61.3%) completed the survey. The sample consists of 48.2% female and 51.8% male participants.

All constructs are assessed by adopting validated scales from the literature and adjusting the wording to the context of food and seafood products. Attitude, PBC, and social norm are framed towards fish in general. Food involvement and environmental awareness are framed towards food in general. All scales are measured on a seven-point Likert type scale (1 = completely disagree; 7 = completely

agree). Consumption behaviors are framed as “During the past year...” and shopping behaviors are framed as: “How often do you buy fish in: ...”.

Results

Consumer Decision-Making Styles (CDMS) were measured using the scale developed by Sproles and Kendall (1986), adapted to the food consumption context, similar to Anic et al. (2014) and Eriksson and Stenius (2024). The study included 27 items measuring eight dimensions. To identify Consumer Decision-Making Styles (CDMS), the 27 items underwent a principal component extraction followed by a varimax rotation of components with eigenvalues greater than unity was applied. This analysis successfully identified eight distinct consumer food decision-making styles (See Table 1). Five items were excluded from the analysis due to their inadequate psychometric properties. The reliability of the scales, as measured by Cronbach's Alpha, ranged from 0.69 for the price consciousness style to 0.90 for the perfectionism style.

To classify the consumers through their shopping styles, K-means cluster analysis was employed. K-means cluster analysis was executed separately for four different cluster solutions, 2, 3, 4, and 5. To assess the internal validity of the cluster results, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted for each of the cluster solutions. To determine the number of clusters, the results for cluster solutions were examined by comparing the ANOVA results. Besides the homogeneity within the clusters, the number of cases in each cluster and the distances between the cluster centers were evaluated (Hair et al., 2010).

The evaluations implied the four-cluster solution, reflecting different combinations of shopping styles (see Table 1). These segments are labeled as follows: “*Quality-Oriented Recreational Food Shoppers*” (29% of the sample), “*Confused and Impulsive Food Shoppers*” (23%), “*Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers*” (24%) and “*Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food Shoppers*” (24%).

Segment 1: Quality-Oriented Recreational Food Shoppers (29%)

This segment prioritizes quality, perfectionism, and enjoyment in shopping. They focus on high-quality products over price and value brands without being strictly loyal. Their high perceived behavioral control (PBC) reflects confidence in purchasing and consuming fish regularly. Social norms moderately influence their choices.

They exhibit the strongest positive attitude toward fish consumption and high food involvement. Their strong environmental consciousness drives frequent fish consumption and preference for sustainably produced seafood, particularly fresh fish from delicatessens. While they occasionally buy pre-packed fish, their focus remains on fresh, high-quality options. No socio-demographic factors (i.e., gender, age, education, income, residence) significantly characterize the segment.

Segment 2: Confused and Impulsive Food Shoppers (23%)

This segment struggles with decision-making and often makes impulsive purchases due to over-choice. They do not enjoy grocery shopping and have low price-consciousness, showing no strong preference for discounts or premium brands.

Their attitude toward fish consumption is the weakest, with low food involvement and the lowest PBC, indicating uncertainty in fish purchasing. Social norms have minimal influence on their behavior. While they show some intention to increase fish consumption, low environmental awareness limits their commitment to sustainability. They consume the least fresh fish from delicatessens, cod, and salmon, aligning with their impulsive and unstructured shopping behavior, which lacks planning and prioritization of quality or sustainability. No socio-demographic factors (i.e., gender, age, education, income, residence) significantly characterize the segment.

Table 1: Cluster results with mean scores on cluster variables.

CDMS:	<i>Quality-Oriented Recreational</i>	<i>Confused and Impulsive Food</i>	<i>Price-Sensitive and</i>	<i>Trend-Conscious and</i>	F (p):

	<i>Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Shoppers</i>	<i>Pragmatic Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Experimental Food Shoppers</i>	
Perfectionism, High-quality consciousness	6.34	5.47	4.46	5.86	403.57***
Price consciousness	2.22	3.19	4.34	3.12	278.42***
Impulsiveness	2.38	4.21	2.75	3.54	254.26***
Confused by over-choice	2.17	4.06	2.49	3.10	251.12***
Brand consciousness	3.73	3.76	2.67	4.47	281.04***
Novelty consciousness	1.52	1.66	1.52	3.42	989.74***
Recreational, hedonistic shopping consciousness	5.20	3.46	4.58	4.90	174.58***
Habitual/Brand loyalty	5.56	5.81	4.85	5.41	69.22***

Segment 3: Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers (24%)

This segment is highly price-conscious, prioritizing affordability over brand recognition or quality. Their low perfectionism and brand-consciousness indicate a focus on value for money rather than premium products. They are neither novelty-seekers nor impulsive buyers, preferring a rational, budget-driven shopping approach.

They have an average attitude toward fish consumption but the lowest environmental awareness. Their PBC is moderate, slightly higher than that of Confused and Impulsive Shoppers, but they remain pragmatic and cost-focused. With low intentions to increase fish consumption or choose sustainable options, price considerations take precedence. They consume moderate levels of cod and salmon but favor frozen and pre-packed fish over fresh options due to cost efficiency. No socio-demographic factors (i.e., gender, age, education, income, residence) significantly characterize the segment.

Table 2: TPB, FI, and EA characteristics for the clusters

Profiling variables:	<i>Quality-Oriented Recreational Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Confused and Impulsive Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food</i>	F (p):

				<i>Shoppers</i>	
Attitude towards fish	5.89	5.36	5.49	5.71	23.23***
Social norm	3.4	3.3	3.0	3.9	22.56***
PBC	6.1	5.5	5.6	5.8	26.41***
Intention to consume fish more frequently	4.1	4.0	3.7	4.5	22.02***
Intention to consume more sustainably produced fish	4.8	4.6	4.0	5.1	30.46***
Food involvement	5.3	4.2	4.3	5.2	94.85***
Environmental awareness	4.6	4.3	3.6	4.7	52.49***

Table 3: Fish consumption characteristics for the clusters

Profiling variables:	<i>Quality-Oriented Recreational Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Confused and Impulsive Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers</i>	<i>Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food Shoppers</i>	F (p):
Consumed cod	4.6	4.0	4.1	4.6	29.28***
Consumed salmon	4.7	4.3	4.3	4.8	18.46***
Consumed other fish	3.9	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.28*
Frozen	4.2	3.9	4.0	4.2	4.55**
Pre-packed	2.9	2.7	2.5	3.1	10.73***
Fresh for the delicatessen	3.4	2.5	2.4	3.3	47.91***

Segment 4: Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food Shoppers (24%)

This novelty-seeking segment is highly receptive to new food trends and enjoys experimenting with different products. While moderately brand-conscious, they associate well-known brands with quality. They exhibit some perfectionism and recreational shopping tendencies but are not strictly driven by price.

They have a strong attitude toward fish consumption, comparable to Quality-Oriented Recreational Shoppers, with high food involvement. Social norms strongly influence their choices, aligning their purchasing decisions with trends and peer preferences. Their PBC is high, indicating confidence in buying fish. This segment shows the strongest intention to consume more fish and prioritize sustainability. They report the highest consumption of cod and salmon and prefer fresh fish from delicatessens but also show a strong inclination toward pre-packed fish, reflecting their interest in convenience and trend-driven food choices. No socio-demographic factors (i.e., gender, age, education, income, residence) significantly characterize the segment.

Discussion and Conclusions

This study confirms the applicability of the Consumer Styles Inventory (CSI) framework (Sproles & Kendall, 1986) to seafood consumption in Sweden, reinforcing the segmentation of consumers based on cognitive and behavioral orientations. The findings align with previous research (Anic et al., 2014), showing that quality and price consciousness are key factors. The study also integrates the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), demonstrating that attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC) influence fish consumption but vary across consumer segments. *Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food Shoppers* are strongly influenced by social norms, while *Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers* prioritize cost-efficiency over social or environmental concerns.

Theoretical Implications

This research advances consumer behavior theory by demonstrating that decision-making styles impact both general shopping and category-specific food choices. It extends TPB by showing that CDMS shapes how consumers interpret attitudes, norms, and control perceptions related to seafood consumption. Additionally, it highlights the importance of multidimensional segmentation when analyzing sustainable food consumption, as different groups balance sustainability with other purchasing criteria such as price, convenience, and novelty.

Practical Implications

These insights offer targeted strategies for promoting sustainable seafood consumption. *Quality-Oriented Recreational Food Shoppers* respond positively to high-quality and sustainability-focused branding, making it essential to emphasize premium attributes and provenance in marketing efforts. *Confused and Impulsive Food Shoppers* benefit from simplified purchasing environments, where clear labeling and pre-packaged options help reduce decision fatigue and make sustainable choices more accessible. *Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers* prioritize affordability, highlighting the need for price incentives and budget-friendly eco-labeling to encourage sustainable purchasing behavior. Finally, *Trend-Conscious and Experimental Food Shoppers* are highly receptive to sustainability messaging, particularly through social media and innovative product offerings that align with their interest in new food trends and experiential consumption.

Policymakers can enhance sustainable seafood consumption through structural interventions (e.g., price subsidies) and behavioral strategies (e.g., public campaigns reinforcing social norms). Raising environmental awareness is particularly crucial for *Price-Sensitive and Pragmatic Food Shoppers*, who demonstrate lower sustainability concerns.

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The impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on stock optimization in the food retail industry and its impact on food banks

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Abstract

Introduction

Food banks are defined as “a non-profit that safely stores millions of pounds of food that will soon be delivered to local food programs, like a food pantry” (Feeding America.org, n.d.). Food banks receive donated products from local retailers, grocers, restaurants, and local community members/partners to then distribute to local food pantries that serve their communities. As of January 2025, 198 U.S. food banks have been established (FeedingAmerica.org, n.d.), helping to reduce food insecurity in the country which is estimated at 13.5% of all U.S. households (USDA Economic Research Service, 2024).

Food waste is an important global challenge with significant economic, social, and environmental implications (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Winkler et al., 2023; Kuruva, 2024). In the food retail industry, optimizing stock levels is critical for reducing waste (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) is gaining recognition for its transformative potential in improving efficiency and reducing waste throughout the food supply chain, particularly through advanced stock optimization techniques (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024). AI technologies, such as machine learning, can analyze large datasets of sales data, consumer behavior, and other relevant factors to predict demand more accurately (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024). This capability enables retailers to make more informed purchasing and inventory management decisions, minimizing overstocking and spoilage that leads to food waste (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024).

The adoption of AI for stock optimization in food retail has an extensive effect on food banks. On the one hand, more efficient inventory management by retailers may reduce the amount of surplus food available for donation to food banks (Winkler et al., 2023). If retailers are more accurate in their ordering and inventory, there may be less unsold food to redistribute. However, AI provides significant opportunities to improve the connection between food retailers and food banks, as well as the overall efficiency of food redistribution systems (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022).

AI-powered platforms can help match food donors, such as retailers, with food banks and other charitable organizations based on need and logistics (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Natural language processing (NLP) can help donors and food banks communicate more effectively, whereas geographic information systems (GIS) can optimize resource allocation based on food insecurity hotspots (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Furthermore, AI can help food banks predict client demands and improve inventory management (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Finally, integrating AI into food retail stock optimization, combined with AI-driven food redistribution systems, has the potential to create a more sustainable and equitable food system by reducing waste and enhancing access to food for those in need (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Kuruva, 2024).

The increased use of AI to optimize stock and produce less excess could lead to the unavailability of products much needed by food banks and other community partners. In this regard, we aim to address the following research question as part of our initial exploratory study: *How does the use of AI-powered stock optimization tools in food retail affect the amount and type of surplus (excess) food available for donations to community partners like food banks?*

Literature Review

The food retail industry faces a significant challenge in food waste, requiring effective stock optimization strategies (Kuruva, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a significant tool for improving inventory management and decreasing waste in this industry by enabling more accurate demand forecasting and efficient operations (Zhang et al., 2022; Wolniak et al., 2024; Kuruva, 2024). Food banks also play a significant role in reducing food insecurity by redistributing surplus food (Rivera et al., 2023).

AI for Stock Optimization in Food Retail

AI technology, particularly machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms can analyze large datasets, such as sales data, consumer behavior patterns, weather patterns, and inventory levels, to forecast food demand more accurately (Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024). This sophisticated forecast enables retailers to optimize their ordering and stocking decisions, ensuring that shelves are well-stocked without overstocking, which leads to spoilage (Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024; Wolniak et al., 2024).

ML algorithms can identify complex patterns in historical sales data and external factors, resulting in more precise demand forecasts than traditional approaches (Zhang et al., 2022; Kuruva, 2024; Wolniak et al., 2024). This allows retailers to match their procurement and inventory levels to projected consumer demand, lowering the risk of unsold products (Kuruva, 2024; Onyeaka et al., 2023). AI can continuously monitor inventory levels and forecast demand for specific products, providing real-time alerts on product availability and recommending alternatives when items are out of stock (Wolniak et al., 2024). This streamlines the purchasing process for consumers while ensuring optimal stock levels for retailers, minimizing both stockouts and overstocking (Wolniak et al., 2024).

AI algorithms can analyze market trends, competitors' prices, and customer behavior to continuously adjust prices (Wolniak et al., 2024). This can assist retailers in encouraging the sale of products nearing their expiration date, hence minimizing waste (Winkler et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022). While analytical and optimization approaches to discounting have yet to be fully implemented in retail practice, they are predicted to become more successful as data and computation power increase (Winkler et al., 2023). AI can help optimize the products available in stores depending on customer preferences and demand, reducing waste from unpopular items (Zhang et al., 2022).

AI, when combined with sensors and image recognition, can assist in forecasting and identifying defective or low-quality products early in the supply chain, preventing them from reaching customers and adding to waste (Onyeaka et al., 2023; Kuruva, 2024). For example, AI image recognition can be utilized in quality control during production and packaging to minimize waste by recognizing defective products (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Biodegradation detection sensors can also track the life cycle of packaged foods (Kuruva, 2024).

Impact on Food Banks

Increased efficiency in stock optimization driven by AI in food retail may have both positive and negative consequences for food banks. If retailers improve their demand forecasting and inventory management, there may be less surplus food available for donation. The primary purpose of AI-powered systems is to reduce unsold or spoiled products (Kuruva, 2024), which are a key source of donations to food banks (Winkler et al., 2023).

Despite the potential reduction in surplus food volume, artificial intelligence provides significant opportunities to improve the connectivity and efficiency of the food rescue and redistribution network. AI can be used to develop systems that connect food donors (including retailers with small surpluses) with food banks and other organizations that distribute food to those in need (Zhang et al., 2022; Onyeaka et al., 2023). These systems can optimize food donation and reduce waste by taking into consideration factors such as the type and quantity of food available, the demands of different food banks, logistical constraints, and geographic proximity (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Geographic information systems (GISs), which are frequently integrated with AI, can map food insecurity hotspots as well as food bank and donor locations. This allows for the analysis of food distribution

patterns to optimize resource allocation and increase food delivery efficiency (Zhang et al., 2022; Onyeaka et al., 2023). Reinforcement learning AI systems can also optimize food logistics and supply chain management (Onyeaka et al., 2023).

AI can help food banks directly by analyzing data on client demographics, food preferences, and nutritional needs to forecast future demand and better tailor food assistance (“AI-FEED: Prototyping an AI-Powered Platform for the Food Charity Ecosystem,” 2024). Machine learning can be used to recognize food and estimate nutrition, allowing food banks to better manage their inventory and provide nutritious options (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence, particularly machine learning and computer vision, can be used to visually recognize and categorize donated food products, assisting food banks and donors in identifying and removing spoiled or contaminated products, and ensuring that only safe food is distributed (Onyeaka et al., 2023).

AI-powered solutions that use natural language processing (NLP) can improve communication between food donors and food banks, making the donation process more efficient and user-friendly (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Blockchain technology can also streamline donation processes and enhance donor engagement and recognition (“AI-FEED: Prototyping an AI-Powered Platform for the Food Charity Ecosystem,” 2024).

Methodology

For this exploratory study, data were collected using a combination of informal interviews, data derived from industry contacts in retail grocery and within food banks across two separate U.S. states on the East Coast, and available data provided on industry websites regarding the U.S. of AI by retail grocers. The data was combined and synthesized by researchers to help determine if AI was being used within retail grocery stores, to what extent the current and future strategic plans are, and to determine if discussions have occurred with their non-profit partners regarding inventory availability. Results are this synthesis provided below as themes with supporting documentation noted.

Theme 1: AI Is Already in Progress for Retail Grocers in The U.S. But Not Fully Developed

As noted in a personal communication on February 03, 2025, one major retail grocer stated:

Like most retailers we are using predictive forecasting tools which help us to ensure we have the optimal inventory in store to meet demand. While the tools are improving, they are far from significantly reducing “waste.”

Personal communication with an additional anonymous grocery partner in February of 2025 indicated the following about their AI development at the present point:

We are probably three to five years out from really leveraging AI fully within our grocery area. Larger companies such as Kroger are doing a better job, but in terms of optimization we still have a long way to go.

Theme 2: AI Improvements May Affect Food Donations from Retail Grocers to Food Banks/Pantries

Confirmed by two U.S. grocers via personal informal communication (January 10, 2025; January 24, 2025; February 03, 2025):

As these (AI) tools continue to improve, they may eventually reduce, the food available for donation to food pantries and food banks. However, I (we) don't think this is an immediate concern as of today given our investment and infrastructure so we are operating as we always do.

There's always a bit of risk involved in fully depending on automation, especially with data integrity and if we can trust what the information says. We wouldn't want the donations to be affected especially on poor data.

Companies will have to think about donations differently and not just in terms of physical stock. Yes, while the goal is to have zero waste, we would “do it differently” in terms of our donations and consider more financial support for our partners instead of specific product-driven donations.

Theme 3: AI Can Aid Food Banks and Other Non-profits Via the Use of Better Modeling of Where to Distribute Donations

When asked about how AI could potentially benefit non-profit organizations, it was suggested via personal communication with a large city U.S.-based Food Bank (January 10, 2025) and online research (University of South Carolina, 2025; Hutchinson, n.d.):

We are investing more time thinking about how AI will help us with product distribution across our various food bank partners. By better modeling of needs across our areas (states), we can be more responsive to ensuring that food won't spoil or be wasted and get into the hands of those who really need it. This is ultimately everyone's goal, right?

Using better AI modeling, universities and other large companies are collecting left-over food from catering events or donating directly to food banks or other non-profits like college campuses to ensure food is not wasted which also promotes a sustainable systems approach.

Discussion

As AI and data automation continue to become a larger part of the strategic planning and operations for businesses like retail grocery, it is important to consider the impacts of factors such as lower stock and demand/assortment optimization on businesses whose model is built on overcapacity. The answer, as noted above, is in the strategic planning where a reduction in physical goods such as grocery stock can be mitigated through additional financial donations or other means to supplement the not-for-profit partners such as food banks. If AI can be used to help predict food shortages or map food deserts in geographic locations (Pressley, 2024), then an opportunity exists to help food banks in their distribution of products and services to reach more individuals in need. The research, in its infancy stage, is currently limited in the amount of data collected from retail grocery partners and strategic decision-makers currently utilizing AI demand planning within their operations. Future research, then, should consider longitudinal work on tracking food bank donations from both the supply side (grocers) and consumption side (food banks) to determine if additional AI usage will result in lowered product donations or negative impacts on food banks as additional resources are vastly needed to fight hunger.

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Examining consumer preferences for chicken breast fillets in the light of the price cap

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Abstract

To mitigate food inflation, the Hungarian government introduced a price cap on several essential food products in 2022, including chicken breast fillet. However, the price cap was abolished in 2023, leading to a significant increase in the consumer price of chicken breast fillet. The aim of this research is to examine Hungarian consumers' preferences regarding chicken breast fillet during the price cap period and after its removal, with particular attention to their economic expectations for the future. To this end, consumer surveys were conducted in 2022 (during the price cap period) and in 2024 (after its removal), with sample sizes of $n_{2022}=500$ and $n_{2024}=510$, respectively. Preferences were assessed using the best-worst scaling (BWS) method in its "object" case, where consumers evaluated key attributes (freshness, availability, origin, taste, brand, healthiness, price) in hypothetical decision-making scenarios. Data analysis was carried out through discrete choice modeling, employing the maximum difference approach within the frameworks of conditional logit (CL) and latent class (LC) specifications. The results indicate that while freshness was consistently ranked as the most important factor when purchasing chicken breast fillet in both survey periods, the perception of price changed over time. In the first survey, price held a similar level of importance as healthiness and taste; however, by the second survey, price had fallen behind these two attributes in the ranking. Latent class analysis identified three distinct consumer preference segments in both survey periods: (1) Pragmatic – Freshness and healthiness were the most important attributes, with taste also gaining importance in the second survey. (2) Price comes first – Price was the dominant factor compared to all other attributes. (3) Quality comes first – In the first survey, all attributes (except brand) were significantly more important than price, while in the second survey, healthiness, origin, and freshness emerged as the key factors. The sources of preference heterogeneity were only partially linked to sociodemographic characteristics and economic expectations, with these correlations becoming more pronounced in the second survey. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers regarding consumer preference shifts in response to economic shocks, which can contribute to the formulation of effective and well-targeted measures.

Nudging consumers towards healthy and sustainable human diets

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Abstract

Numerous opportunities exist around the world to nudge consumers towards choices that support a healthier diet which also has a lower impact on the natural environment. This article outlines an agenda for behavioural science researchers to contribute rigorous and relevant evidence to support this aim.

Consumer choices about food are seen to be influenced by a combination of personal values, social norms, economic factors, and accessibility. Further, while many consumers express concern for health and sustainability, their purchasing decisions are largely driven by price, convenience, and taste. Thus, health often takes a secondary role with sustainability issues being given even less consideration. The challenge for nudging consumers is compounded by their generally limited knowledge, the sporadic availability of suitable products in convenient local retail outlets alongside the difficulty they have in identifying healthy and sustainable food options within these outlets.

Global Dietary Profiles

Famine Diet

The "famine diet" is shaped by economic hardship and limited food availability rather than personal preference. Lack of food (or food insecurity) affects many low-income households in both urban and remote areas. These consumers face significant challenges in accessing healthy and sustainable food products.

Fat Diet

The "fat diet" is characterized by excessive consumption of calorie-dense, nutrient-poor foods, with consumer choices often driven by convenience, affordability, and aggressive marketing of processed foods. Evidence of dietary pattern is shown in obesity and chronic diseases, such as diabetes and cardiovascular issues.

Fit (Healthy) Diet

Consumers following the "fit diet" typically have access to a variety of nutritious food options and possess the knowledge to make informed dietary choices. Their decisions are often influenced by personal health goals, lifestyle preferences, and cultural norms that prioritize balanced eating habits. In many developed countries, this is reflected in the growing interest in whole foods, organic products, and plant-based diets.

Fit (Healthy) and Sustainable Diet

The "fit (healthy) and sustainable diet" represents an aspirational diet that balances human health with environmental responsibility. Consumers in this category actively seek out food choices that align with health-consciousness and environmental values, such as plant-based diets, minimal food waste, and locally sourced products. Globally only a small fraction of consumers actively adhere to this diet.

Challenges for consumer uptake of a Fit (Healthy) and Sustainable Diet

Researchers could engage with influential stakeholders alongside undertaking research which provides evidence to support retail and product options being available to consumers alongside how to

most effectively nudge consumers to make considered choices which support health and sustainability. Specifically, it is proposed to:

Collect empirical evidence on key components of a fit (healthy) and sustainable diet

Identify consumers likely acceptance of each component

Provide guidance on these components to support policy makers and practitioners

Encourage action targeted in high impact areas where consumers are willing to change

Possible components: increasing consumption of fresh vegetables, minimizing consumption of 'junk' food, and reducing food waste

In conclusion, nudging consumers to face, and then make supportive choices as they step towards, the Fit (Healthy) and Sustainable diet is challenging. However, the benefits for human vitality and longevity, alongside environmental sustainability, warrant serious efforts.

The role of consumer knowledge in functional food preferences: Evidence from a discrete choice experiment on omega-3 enriched eggs

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Abstract

The functional food market has experienced significant growth in response to increasing consumer awareness of health and nutrition (Caracciolo et al. 2019; Sgroi et al., 2024). However, despite their recognised benefits, consumer acceptance of functional foods remains uneven, influenced by multiple factors, including knowledge and perception of health benefits. Understanding these determinants is crucial for both market development and effective policy interventions aimed at promoting healthier food choices.

One of the key factors influencing consumer behaviour towards foods is knowledge (Park et al., 1994; Ares et al., 2008, Nuttavuthisit and Thøgersen, 2017), which has been conceptualised into three distinct categories: subjective knowledge, objective knowledge, and prior experience (Brucks, 1985). Subjective knowledge refers to an individual's perception of their own knowledge, while objective knowledge represents the actual information stored in memory. Prior experience, instead, is linked to previous consumption, usage, and shopping expertise related to the product. Previous research has shown that subjective knowledge about healthy foods contributes to healthy lifestyle choices (van der Merwe et al., 2024). Furthermore, higher levels of subjective and objective knowledge correlate with greater engagement with organic food and more frequent use of information provided by shops or labels (Aertsens et al., 2011).

Building on this framework, the present study aims to achieve two main research objectives. First, it examines the role of knowledge in shaping consumer preferences for functional foods, distinguishing between subjective knowledge, objective knowledge, and prior experience. Second, it explores market heterogeneity through a segmentation analysis and assesses consumers' willingness to pay for functional food products.

To address these objectives, a discrete choice experiment was conducted on a sample of 502 Croatian consumers using an online survey administered in autumn 2023 by a professional market research agency. The study focused on omega-3-enriched eggs, chosen as the reference product due to their growing global demand and potential to improve nutrient intake, especially omega-3 fatty acids often lacking in Western diets (Fraeye et al., 2012).

In the experiment, participants were presented with choice sets involving a pack of ten eggs, varying in terms of enrichment with omega-3 fatty acids (absence or presence), production method (floor rearing, cage-free, free-range, organic), and price (€ 1.7, 2.2, 2.7, 3.2, 3.7, 4.2, 4.7, 5.3). The attributes and levels were allocated among the choice sets using an efficient design, resulting in a final design of 24 choice sets, which were blocked into three groups. Therefore, each respondent completed eight choice tasks, selecting their preferred option between two egg alternatives or choosing to opt out in each choice task. The data were analysed using a Random Parameter Logit model to examine the role of knowledge in shaping consumer choices and a Latent Class Model to segment consumers based on their preferences.

The results reveal significant heterogeneity in consumer behaviour. Previous experience with omega-3-enriched eggs positively influences willingness to pay, while subjective knowledge has a negative effect, suggesting that consumers who perceive themselves as informed may be more sceptical of

functional food claims. Objective knowledge, however, does not significantly impact willingness to pay. The segmentation analysis identifies three distinct consumer groups. The first class, comprising 28% of the sample, was labelled "Indifferent consumers," as these individuals do not exhibit a strong preference for any of the products offered in the choice sets. The second class, representing 39% of the sample, was identified as "Functional food adopters" and includes consumers who appreciate the functional attribute and are more likely to choose the product when omega-3 enrichment is present. Consumers in this group are willing to pay up to €0.66 more per pack of ten eggs for the omega-3-enriched product compared to conventional eggs. The third class, comprising 34% of the sample, was named "Functional food sceptics," as their purchasing behaviour does not significantly change based on the presence or absence of the omega-3 claim. However, both functional food adopters and functional food sceptics place a strong positive value on production methods, with free-range being the most preferred attribute, followed by organic and cage-free production.

These findings provide valuable insights into how information-based interventions can be better designed to promote functional food consumption. Addressing consumer scepticism and improving trust in scientifically validated health claims may enhance the acceptance of functional food products, ultimately contributing to their market expansion.

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Using the best-worst scaling method to analyse Czech and Hungarian consumers' preferences for 'Cultured pork meat'

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Abstract

Compared to traditional animal slaughter methods, alternative meat production techniques are widely regarded as eco-friendly and sustainable. Cultured meat, also known as 'in-vitro meat' involves culturing animal cells externally from the original donor animal. The success of cultured meat in the marketplace is contingent on consumer acceptance. Educating consumers about the cultivation process can increase their trust in the product, thus enhancing the potential for cultivated meat to succeed commercially.

Our research aimed to determine the level of interest in 'cultured pork meat' among Czech and Hungarian consumers. The analysis helps us to better understand the factors influencing consumers' preferences for 'cultured pork meat'.

We used a widely applied preference assessment procedure called Best-Worst Scaling and analysed consumer preferences based on seven aspects. These aspects were meat texture, meat from an indigenous breed (not a hybrid or modern breed), meat appearance, meat smell, health impact compared to conventionally produced meat, meat freshness, and taste.

In our primary market research, we used a quantitative online representative questionnaire survey in 2022 involving 1600 people (800 people per country) for Czech and Hungarian consumers. Respondents in both countries ranked meat freshness and taste as the two most important aspects. The third and fourth most important aspects were the health impact compared to traditionally produced meat and the smell of the meat, for which the ranking scores were very close. For Czech consumers, these were followed by the appearance of the meat and whether the meat was from a native breed (not a hybrid or modern breed). The texture of the meat was the least important aspect for Czech consumers. On the other hand, Hungarian consumers rated the texture and appearance of the meat very closely, with the last aspect being whether the meat was from a native breed (non-hybrid or modern breed).

Our analysis showed a difference between the preferences of Czech and Hungarian consumers for cultured meat from animals with indigenous genetics and that meat texture is more critical for Hungarians than Czech consumers. However, our results suggest that the preferences we investigated may change as this industry develops rapidly, and food producers must adapt continuously to meet consumer needs.

Consumer acceptance of vertical farming: A cluster analysis approach

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Abstract

As global food systems face increasing pressure due to climate change, resource scarcity, and soil degradation, alternative and innovative food production methods such as Indoor or Vertical Farming (VF) have garnered significant attention. While VF is not yet capable of producing at the scale of traditional agriculture, it offers distinct advantages, particularly in urban environments. By providing a highly controlled indoor setting, VF can mitigate external risks and ensure more stable yields. This method is particularly well-suited for cultivating leafy greens, lettuce, microgreens, herbs and strawberries. However, beyond the technical challenges of scaling up production, consumer acceptance remains a key barrier to VF's successful market integration. To address this, it is crucial to identify the consumer groups most receptive to this technology, allowing for more targeted and efficient integration efforts.

This pre-registered study investigates the factors shaping consumer perceptions of VF in Germany, with a particular focus on intra-population differences and consumer segmentation based on acceptance levels. A survey-based experimental design (N=1000) was employed, using a structured questionnaire to assess socio-demographic characteristics, shopping and eating habits, attitudes toward food technologies, and familiarity with VF. Next, participants were given a brief informational text about the VF production process, followed by a series of statements outlining its potential risks and benefits. These statements covered aspects such as sustainability, environmental impact, health and safety, regionality, and effects on farmers, as well as naturalness and quality. They were then asked to evaluate these aspects as either opportunities or risks. Psychological constructs, including food technology neophobia, naturalness preferences, psychological distance, and political orientation, were also measured for their influence on VF acceptance. Participants were recruited through a market research panel, ensuring a demographically representative sample.

A multi-step statistical approach was employed to analyze the data. Factor analysis was first conducted to identify key constructs influencing VF perception, followed by cluster analysis to segment respondents based on their acceptance levels and willingness to pay for VF products. The results indicate that consumer acceptance is highly heterogeneous, shaped by behavioral patterns, prior knowledge, and psychological distance. Exposure to balanced information on VF's sustainability, health, and economic implications significantly influences its acceptance. This highlights both opportunities and challenges for market adoption.

Findings from this study provide valuable insights for marketers, policymakers, and food industry stakeholders seeking to promote VF as a viable food production method. Effective communication strategies that transparently present both the advantages and realistic limitations of VF are crucial for building consumer trust. This is particularly important in urban and urbanizing areas and presents an opportunity for smart cities where access to arable land is limited, and technological solutions can complement traditional agricultural systems. By identifying key consumer segments and understanding the psychological drivers of VF acceptance, targeted messaging and strategic positioning—both within the retail environment and through external communication—can enhance market penetration and foster greater public acceptance of VF as a sustainable and accessible food production method.

Sustainable agri-food marketing innovation: Co-Creation and Design Thinking as a research method

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Abstract

In response to the global challenges of today, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) highlight, among others, the need for education for sustainable development (ESD) (Goal 4) and the promotion of sustainable consumption and production (Goal 12). Aligning with these objectives, this research project explores business model innovation for organic box scheme providers, focusing on fruit and vegetable boxes while integrating early childhood ESD through collaborations with childcare facilities.

Organic produce delivery via box schemes is a well-established business model in organic agriculture. Many providers already maintain relationships with childcare facilities, supplying food and occasionally offering educational activities. However, these services are rarely integrated into a cohesive offering. This research investigates whether a structured collaboration between organic box scheme providers and early childhood education institutions can enhance the promotion of organic agriculture and ESD while ensuring economic viability. Specifically, the study examines how combining organic produce deliveries with sustainability education can serve as an innovative marketing strategy for organic box schemes.

Given that both food delivery and educational services are common but rarely combined, this study employs a mixed-methods research approach that gathers diverse stakeholder perspectives while fostering creativity in business model innovation. Co-creation and design thinking principles are central to this approach, ensuring that the needs and insights of all relevant stakeholders – organic box scheme providers, childcare facilities, and parents – are considered in the innovation process.

The presentation outlines how co-creation and design thinking methodologies are applied within the research project, emphasizing a participatory workshop as its core component. Given the complexity of the research topic with the different stakeholder groups being involved, an open but structured approach is crucial to ensure scientific rigor and practical relevance. The research begins with an exploratory phase, using mixed-methods approaches such as online surveys, expert interviews, case studies, and group discussions to capture the diverse perspectives. The insights of this exploratory phase build the basis for the subsequent co-creation phase, where those stakeholders collaboratively develop a prototype business model in a structured workshop employing design thinking techniques. This prototype will later undergo empirical evaluation to assess its feasibility and effectiveness in promoting both organic agriculture and sustainability education. In this presentation, we will examine the research design in detail and explore how academic methodologies can be enhanced to address today's complex challenges.

Even though the research is ongoing, it makes a significant contribution to the academic discourse on sustainable agri-food marketing innovation. By integrating co-creation and design thinking into scientific research, this project not only advances methodological discussions but also demonstrates practical applications for sustainable business models. Ultimately, it offers valuable insights for academics and industry professionals alike, bridging the gap between research and real-world impact in international food marketing.

Feeding the future: Increasing donations to reduce world hunger through karma and mental simulation

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Abstract

World hunger is still a highly relevant social issue with 733 million people experiencing hunger worldwide in 2023 (WHO, 2024). Charitable organisations and programmes aiming to reduce hunger rely on advertisements utilising different types of framing and appeals to spur consumer donations, both monetary and non-monetary (e.g. food and time) (Costello & Malkoc, 2022; Homer, 2021; Silver & Small, 2024). However, it is still unclear which type of message framing can maximise consumer donations (Kulow & Kramer, 2016; Reed et al., 2007; Smith & Schwarz, 2012). This research investigates the effectiveness of karma versus religious appeals to increase donations to reduce hunger.

There is extensive extant literature on donation behaviour resulting from the use of karma (Kulow & Kramer, 2016; Muralidharan, 2022; Sharma, 2021) and religious appeals (Bakar et al., 2013; Dotson & Hyatt, 2000; Zehra & Minton, 2020). However, only Muralidharan's (2022) study examines these appeals together, but not in the donation context. Furthermore, this paper is the first to explore the effects of mental simulation, the creative envisioning of a future scenario (Thompson et al., 2009), and anticipated regret, the negative feeling that arises in relation to not executing a specific behaviour (Abraham & Sheeran, 2003), on the relationship between karma (versus religious) appeals on intention to donate to reduce hunger.

This research adapted an experimental two-study approach. Both studies used a single factor, two level (appeal: karma vs. religious) between-subjects design, with slight tweaks to the advertisements for each study. 151 responses and 147 responses were collected for study 1 and 2 respectively. Belief in karma and religiosity was measured to eliminate these as alternative explanations for our prediction. Furthermore, we controlled for education level, as prior research suggests it influences donations (Converse et al., 2012). A mediation analysis using PROCESS Model 4 (Hayes, 2018) with 5000 bootstrap resamples was conducted for both studies and study 2 also used a moderated mediation analysis.

Study 1 demonstrated that a karma (vs. religious) appeal produced increased mental simulation and led to higher intentions to donate to reduce hunger. Study 2 confirmed the mediating effect of mental simulation on intention to donate to reduce hunger. However, this effect only emerged for respondents who felt low levels of anticipated regret.

One possible reason is that messages using karma suggest a direct cause-and-effect relationship between one's actions and future consequences (Humphreys, 2005), which enables individuals to vividly envision the positive outcomes of donating; in this case, less starving people. Furthermore, those with low anticipated regret do not have a high emotional burden (as those with high anticipated regret), and consequently, full cognitive capability to envision a world without hunger and the impact their donation can have. In summary, the findings of this research indicate that the use of karma can enhance mental simulation, which in turn increases the intention to donate to reduce hunger. It also highlights the importance of minimising negative emotions like anticipated regret to boost the effectiveness of mental simulation in driving donations to reduce hunger.

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The potential role of protein labelling in the green transition - an empirical real-life study on young, German students age 16-22 years

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Abstract

In earlier research we found that the exposition to plant-based food enhances the liking of plant-based food in general (Schober-Schmutz & Grunert 2024). A german-wide representative survey about the preferences of plant-based alternatives to meat proteins by Spicher, et.al. (2025) goes along with this finding: They conclude, that the preferences for plant-based protein alternatives in omnivore groups rise with familiarity of the protein. Exposing omnivore young people on a regular basis to vegetarian food could hence support the green transition.

However, in qualitative research on non-volatile vegetarians, we found compensational behavior: 6-8 times a week the probands were buying meat in the nearby town. Especially members of a fitness club, doing muscle building or a ketose, were not to be satisfied with vegetarian meals. They were very often told they need 3 g protein per kg bodyweight per day, where 1 and max. 1,6 g per kg bodyweight per day is the official recommendation of the German association for Nutrition (DGE). As the main protein source of the traditional meal is meat, they get trainers` diet advice on high meat-consumption plus protein-shakes.

We see two problems that inhibit the satisfaction with vegetarian food and thereby the green transition:

- 1) The probands had wrong information on their need of protein, even unhealthy advice. (Health illiteracy)
- 2) The probands had no idea, which food is a protein source on a vegetarian buffet. (Food-illiteracy). Eating was substitute satisfaction and had to be completed by meat shopping.

A satisfying food choice at the vegetarian buffet could be more likely, if health information and protein-labelling was placed in the decision-making process. Both interventions could enhance the green transition of omnivore young people.

The conceptual relationships:

1) It is hypothesized, that the knowledge on protein sources other than meat is not existent. That even the role of meat in protein supply is more subconsciously available as cultural tradition. Food that is labeled with the protein content on the packaging front is filling this knowledge gap and brings the satisfying key for young leisure athletes. Those in turn are focusing only on those high protein products. If we label the protein value of one portion on the lunch buffet, the experienced tastiness will be higher, than if we don` t declare proteins at the point of sale and the additional shopping for extra meat in the nearby town will be lower.

2) It is further hypothesized, that this missing knowledge is inhibiting the protein shift from meat to plant-based proteins for a more sustainable food consumption, because food without meat is in their mind missing the essential ingredient. Consequently the information of the protein content will make the food more satisfying than without the information. Ergo: The expectation of the tastiness of vegetarian food on the attitude level will be higher with, than without protein information.

The experiment:

8 groups of 16-22 year-old students, that are eating and living in a boardinghouse in Germany near

Heilbronn for a one-week coursework became the focus groups. They all were served one vegetarian meal at the daily lunch-buffet no matter whether they are usually meat-based or vegetarian or vegan eaters. 82% of them reported meat-based eating as their lifestyle and were consequently non-volatile vegetarians. They were “taken away” the meat component. At the end of the week it was questioned whether they are involved in active physical training, how much they care and know about nutrition and proteins and how they liked their meals. In order to measure the effect of the interventions, we introduced the variable “Experienced tastiness of vegetarian food” (5—point-Likert scale), “the expected tastiness of vegetarian food in general” (attitudinal level: 2 Questions with 5-Point -Likert scales as designed by Klaus Grunert and presented in earlier studies) and the number of times the students bought meat out of the boardinghouse in the nearby fast food shop.

The setting:

2 groups (N=56) were administered the questionnaire (control groups)

2 groups (N=56) were given written declaration of proteins next to the meal-plan in the lobby for all meals of the week and protein-declaration on the buffet for cheese, sausage, milk and cereals, salads and dressings bread and spreads such as butter, margarine, jam and honey. (Breakfast and dinner)

2 groups (N=56) given a 15 minutes oral protein & health impulse.

2 groups (N=56) were having the written declaration of proteins and an oral information impulse at health and proteins at the beginning of the week.

Methodology:

It is planned to compare the group of non-volatile vegetarians to the volatile vegetarians in all basic questions on food literacy and health literacy and the conceptual variables experienced and expected tastiness of vegetarian food. (ANOVA)

It is further planned to test the effectiveness of the two interventions of information (oral and written declaration and both) in relation to the conceptual variables “Expected Tastiness of vegetarian food in group comparisons.

Expected Limitations:

It is clearly a risk, that not sufficient cell numbers of probands that are in muscle building or fitness-training aligned with a protein diet. Therefore, we ask for protein knowledge and cumulate the leisure athletes with those who try to eat proteins for beauty (hair and fingernails etc.) and those who know about the need of proteins and their biological function. Eventually we may need an extension of the experiment for more statistical evidence.

It is further possible that cultural backgrounds of international students can change the results, which is why the country of origin is surveyed.

Testing communication strategies for edible insects based on empirical consumer perceptions

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Abstract

Introduction

Contemporary food consumption patterns place a considerable burden on the environment, demanding a dietary change to mitigate these negative effects (Crippa et al., 2021). Edible insects offer a possible solution to alleviate this burden due to their high nutritional value and low environmental impact (Van Huis, 2013). However, despite their benefits and their recent introduction in the European market, consumption of edible insects remains very low among European consumers (Mancini et al., 2019).

In recent years, this issue has sparked interest among researchers. On one hand, several quantitative studies carried out across different countries and with different population samples have found that factors like the novelty of insect products or the aversion that insects cause are some of the barriers preventing the acceptance and adoption of edible insects. On the other hand, intervention studies, where participants were informed about the environmental or nutritional benefits of edible insects, proved that some consumers did change their attitude towards edible insects after the intervention, suggesting that the way we communicate about eating insects can have an effect on their acceptance (Dagevos, 2021).

To further investigate the effects of communication on consumer attitude, we conducted an online survey with an experimental design where we tested a matrix of communication strategies based on the themes of a previous qualitative study. Our results show that a present-focus communication strategy is advantageous in the promotion of edible insects.

Methodology

The study consisted of an online survey with an experimental setup where we asked a representative Danish population sample (N = 501) to answer questions about their attitude towards two different commercial products that contain insects as an ingredient.

The survey started by showing the first product, a crispbread with cricket flour, and randomly assigning participants to one of the four experimental conditions, which consisted of an information message. After they had read the message, participants answered questions related to the measured dependent variables.

The survey continued by showing the second product, date bites with cricket flour, and again randomly assigning participants to one of the four experimental conditions, after which they answered the questions related to the measured dependent variable, this time for the second product.

Additionally, as independent variables we measured different psychodemographics related to the target group's characteristics that previous studies have found to influence consumer attitude to edible insects. These psychodemographics are disgust (Olatunji et al., 2009), innovation focus (Brunso et al., 2021), environmental concern, and health orientation (Dutta-Bergman, 2004), as well as age, gender, education, and residence.

The survey finished with an open box where participants could write their thoughts and feedback.

Regarding the manipulations used in the experimental setup, these were extracted from the themes of a previous qualitative study, where a group of Danish participants reflected on their perception of different commercially available insect products while they conducted an in-house taste trial. The

themes were translated into two pairs of complementary conditions: present-future, and reactive-proactive.

The present-future condition refers to the distance between participants and the choice to eat insects, while the reactive-proactive condition refers to the communication approach companies can take when promoting insect products. Four messages were designed to convey the information corresponding to the pair of conditions, and these messages were the ones presented to participants during the manipulation.

	Present	Future
Proactive	<p><i>[Insects as friends, not foes]</i></p> <p>Do something good for our world TODAY</p> <p>By purchasing this product, you get a high-quality product that shows the role insects play in our ecosystem. Insects are indispensable for biodiversity as they help pollinate our crops and help us keep our world green.</p>	<p><i>[The future is coming]</i></p> <p>Do something good for our world IN THE FUTURE</p> <p>By buying this product you are stepping into the future, because edible insects will be part of our diet as they are the future of food. You will take the first steps towards changing our food system - a journey that has already started.</p>
Reactive	<p><i>[Hide the edible insects]</i></p> <p>Do something good for our world TODAY</p> <p>By buying this product you get a food enriched with a healthy and delicious protein*, making it good for you and your body - without compromising on taste!</p> <p>*Protein from Acheta Domesticus.</p>	<p><i>[Social reactions and norms]</i></p> <p>Do something good for our world IN THE FUTURE</p> <p>By buying this product, you are doing what many other consumers have already started doing - eating insects because of their superior sustainable protein. Eating insects is common in many parts of the world, and it's also becoming more and more common in the Nordic countries.</p>

Regarding the dependent variables, we measured their attitude towards the product using validated scales (Ajzen, 1991), as well as their intention to buy such products using a direct single-question. As mentioned previously, the dependent variables were measured for each of the products.

The observed variables were loaded into factors after performing a principal component analysis. To check the effect of the experimental conditions, the data was analyzed using an ANOVA for each of the products. Additionally, we conducted linear regressions on the dependent variables to check the effect of the measured psychographic variables. We also compared both products using a paired sample t-test.

Results

The results were different for each of the products. For the cricket crispbread, we found that the experimental conditions had a slight significant effect ($F(3,498) = 3.481, p = .016$) on consumer attitude. Further inspection showed that the effect was due to the present-future experimental

condition ($F(2,499) = 5.184, p = .006$), while the reactive-proactive condition did not have an effect. As a result, we concluded that communication messages with a present-focus have a more advantageous effect on consumer attitude regarding insect products.

For the cricket date bites, the experimental conditions did not have a significant effect ($p = .207$). However, further inspection of the ANOVA revealed a trend in the effect of the present-future conditions ($F = 4.226, p = .04$), which was in line with the results of the cricket crispbread.

Regarding the psychographic variables, these were better predictors of product attitude towards both products.

In the linear regression of the cricket crispbread, we found that, contrary to the literature, disgust was not strongly significant ($p = 0.056$), while the main driver of consumer acceptance was innovation focus.

In the linear regression of the cricket date bites, we found that disgust was both significant and the variable with the strongest effect ($F = -4.615, p < .001$). In this analysis we found that the effect of environmental concern was stronger than innovation focus.

The results of the paired sample comparison showed that the consumer attitude towards the cricket crispbread fared better statistically speaking ($p < .001$) than the consumer attitude towards cricket date bites. Further inspection of the comments showed that several participants were not familiar with the category of date snack products, which could explain the difference between both products.

Discussion

We concluded that different communication framings can have an effect on consumer attitude to insect products. In particular, the present-focus communication framing seems to be more advantageous at prompting more positive consumer acceptance. When comparing these results to other theories that have been used for predicting environmental behavior, like the goal framing theory, we can confirm that, at least in the case of novel foods, the hedonic goal, which matches the present-focus communication framing that we used, seems to be more advantageous at influencing consumer attitude in food-related behaviors (do Canto et al., 2023).

We also concluded that other psychographics, like environmental concern or innovation focus, are better predictors of consumer acceptance of insect products.

Additionally, we found that product type can be an important driver of consumer acceptance of novel foods like insect products. In our study, the cricket crispbread, which resembled other similar crispbreads that most consumers are familiar with, had higher consumer acceptance than the cricket date bites, which in itself seemed to be a new product category for some consumers who were not familiar with date-based snack products. The differences in the packaging could have also played an important role, since the cricket date bites displayed the picture of a cricket on the packaging while the cricket crispbread did not, which confirms some of the previous findings in the literature (Dagevos, 2021).

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Keywords: consumer acceptance, edible insects, mixed methods, experimental design

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The effect of social media exposure on prompting sustainable food choices

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Abstract

Over the years, social media have become an integral part of our daily lives, with their significance growing worldwide and playing a pivotal role in influencing interpersonal interactions and relationships, while also serving as powerful sources of information and communication (Ozimek et al., 2023; Simeone & Scarpato, 2020). Among the most innovative tools in digital communication introduced by Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the AI influencer – a digital, non-human character designed to create content and engage with consumers (Mouritzen et al., 2024).

This study aims to explore the role of social media exposure in shaping consumer behaviour, specifically regarding sustainable food consumption patterns. We investigate how socially endorsed food images in social media posts and the use of an AI influencer impact consumer preferences and their willingness to pay for sustainable products.

In addition, this research intends to examine consumer reactions to the introduction of a holistic sustainability certification based on a scoring system that includes two separate indicators: one for the environmental dimension and another for the socioeconomic dimension. This is particularly relevant from a policy perspective since the European Commission is working to harmonise sustainability certifications as part of the Farm to Fork strategy (European Commission, 2020). In this context, the European Economic and Social Committee has explicitly recommended adopting a rating-based system for sustainability labelling at the EU level, incorporating both environmental and social pillars (EESC, 2023).

The research is conducted through an online survey, administered by a professional market research agency, involving a representative sample of 1,000 Italian consumers. We apply a between-subjects design, with participants randomly assigned to one control group and two different social media exposure conditions: Treatment 1 (T1) and Treatment 2 (T2). Respondents in the control group are not exposed to any social media posts. Participants in T1 are provided with an Instagram post promoting the holistic sustainability label. Finally, respondents in T2 are provided with an Instagram promotional post featuring a hypothetical AI influencer, Francesca Giubelli, endorsing the same label. Subsequently, to capture the effect of the different treatment conditions on consumer choice behaviour and willingness to pay for the sustainability holistic label, we conduct a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE). The food product selected for the experiment is pasta, specifically a 500g pack, as its widespread consumption, especially in Mediterranean countries like Italy (Petrontino et al., 2024), ensures familiarity, making it easier for consumers to evaluate its attributes in a DCE. We include the following attributes and levels to describe the pasta alternatives across the choice scenarios: the product's origin (presence or absence of the "100% Italian wheat" label), the environmental sustainability score (low, medium, or high), the socio-economic sustainability score (low, medium, or high), and the price (€0.80, €1.80, €2.80, €3.80). In each choice set, participants are asked to select their preferred option between the two pasta alternatives or to choose neither. A Bayesian efficient design (Scarpa et al., 2007) is used to allocate attributes and attribute levels across the alternatives, resulting in eight choice tasks divided into two blocks. Each participant faces four of these tasks. Prior to the experiment, a cheap talk script (Cummings & Taylor, 1999) is applied to mitigate hypothetical bias. At the current stage, the data collection is ongoing.

To date, no studies have analysed the combined impact of AI influencers and social media exposure on consumer food choice behaviour or their willingness to pay. The findings of this work are expected to provide valuable insights for developing effective digital communication strategies aimed at encouraging sustainable food choices. These insights will guide retailers in leveraging social media to increase their markup, while also assisting policymakers in promoting informed and sustainable consumption patterns through digital engagement.

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Social sustainability in local food supply chains – a “relational view”

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Abstract

Local and short food supply chains are discussed as an important step towards food system transformation and promoted at EU level and globally (Enthoven & Van den Broeck, 2021). Within the scientific discourse on sustainability of local food systems, the social dimension of sustainability is often neglected (Toussaint et al., 2022) or limited to local food security and producer-consumer interactions (Kumar et al., 2019). Yet, the quality of relationship among the supply chain actors as part of social sustainability is – to our knowledge – rarely investigated, but needed for resilient supply chains in the long run (Da Silva et al., 2023).

Thus, the present study aims to fill this gap by exploring cooperation and relationship quality within local food supply chains, using the example of baking wheat. To assess the quality of the relationships, this study draws on the concept of the “relational view” (e.g. Lees et al., 2020), newly applying it to the context of social sustainability. The relational view investigates different dimensions of relationship-specific resources within (food) supply chains (e.g. Zander & Beske, 2014). The well-established dimensions of the relational view, that is “trust”, “commitment” and “satisfaction” (e.g. Lees et al., 2020), were complemented by “goal congruence” and “power” and applied to five focus group discussions (FG). Each FG represented a local food supply chain and consisted of at least one farmer, one miller, and one baker. FGs were transcribed and analysed across supply chains using the dimensions of the “relational view” as main analytical categories.

Results show that the dimensions are intertwined and are partly mutually dependent. The fulfilment of one dimension often also means the fulfilment of another dimension. For example, trust – built through e.g. personal relationships, reliability, and transparency – almost automatically leads to commitment in form of investments (money, time, or knowledge) and adherence to agreements. Furthermore, members of the supply chain “baking wheat” show a high level of satisfaction across all FGs with regard to the quality of their regional trade relations. This is particularly the case when “trust” and “commitment” are present and power imbalances are low or non-existent. Hence, good relationship quality can be seen as an indicator for social sustainability.

Concluding, from a marketing perspective, the benefits of good relationship quality are twofold. First, it facilitates the achievement of e.g. fair prices or long-term contracts for all supply chain actors and with that, potentially improves economic sustainability. Second, good relationship quality could be communicated as an additional value to (ethical) consumers, similar to the concept of “fair trade” (Fairtrade, 2025). Thus, it seems advisable not to neglect social sustainability, as it can maintain and strengthen local food supply chains while the latter can again increase the sustainability in the region.

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What is in a word: Conjoint analysis on framing, promotional method, and wording of vegan products to optimize attractiveness and purchase intention

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Abstract

Background

A vegetarian or vegan (partial) diet seems, compared to an exclusive omnivore diet, to be in the uprise and becoming increasingly present in everyday life (Miguel, 2021). Different motivations contribute to this advancement, ranging from ethical considerations to environmental and health considerations (Clark et al., 2019; Springmann et al., 2016). In a framework proposed by Kerslake et al. (2022) different decision elements when considering substituting meat are classified into facilitators, barriers, and tensions. Furthermore, Kerslake et al. (2022) refer to different marketing and communication tools such as the packaging and labelling of the product as a resource for potential consumers to gain knowledge and be able to make an informed decision based on the key elements included in such a marketing and communication tool.

A first element could be to provide an argument as to why the product should be consumed as to appeal to the motivation of the consumer. As explored by Nijland et al. (2018), consumers have different argument for consuming plant-based foods in favour of meat consumption. In the framework of Kerslake et al. (2022) different influences are mentioned, such as the personal factors concerning health perceptions as well as social norms. Nijland et al. (2018) compared the arguments for two different European counties (i.e., The Netherlands versus Turkey) and found that they vary from animal welfare arguments to arguments related to health, taste, money, religion, and environmental impact. Arguments thus included factual arguments as well as arguments driven by emotions. A clear pattern or single explanation for whom which argument is most prominent, could not be found. Further research on which argument will be most appealing, is thus necessary.

A second significant barrier towards a vegan diet is the price, referred to by Kerslake et al. (2022) as the vegan tax. More specifically, this expectation that meat substitutes have a higher price is being referred to in multiple studies (e.g., Clark & Bogdan, 2019; Collier et al., 2021). A possible (albeit short-term) marketing action to alleviate this barrier of a higher expected price, might be to adopt a promotional strategy in the key communication message. Different promotional strategies exist such as the “Buy 1 get 1 free” method (i.e., quantity discount method) or the price discount method (i.e., % discount on the sale of a single product). Bhatt and Phai (2023) compared both discount methods (i.e., price versus quantity) in their perceived favourability and perceived value. The “Buy 1 get 1 free” method appeared to demonstrate a lower favourability, a lower perceived transaction value and acquisition value. These results tend to signal that the use of “Buy 1 get 1 free” method may result in a lower intention to purchase compared to the price discount method or even compared to the situation when no promotional method is being employed. Evidence on the most advisable promotional method for specifically vegan products, however, is scarce.

The third barrier studied here is the specific wording (or labelling) to refer to the product as being a non-meat product. While currently the legal basis for the use of certain words is not yet clear (e.g., whether the noun meat may be used to refer for non-“meat” products is a matter which is still to be decided in courts and legislation) (Ketelings et al., 2025), the chosen wording may be an important information element for consumers. As Hobbs and Goddard (2015) declare, for relatively new products trust needs to be build up in consumers’ minds and choosing the most appropriate wording

that signals the core elements of a product may thus be an essential information element. A study of Ruby et al. (2024) tested different plant-based labels (i.e., vegetarian, vegan and plant-based) for five different food products (i.e., cookies, sausages, cheese, chocolate, and pasta). The “plant-based” label was slightly more appealing than the “vegetarian” or “vegan” label, but this effect was not moderated by the pre-existing attitudes towards plant-based foods nor the tendency for a consumer to seek information. However, as Ketelings et al. (2025) indicate, while there is an absence of clear policy guidelines, guidelines still need to be founded in scientific research. In this study therefore different alternatives, without any claim on their legal basis, are being investigated as to understand which alternative wording is most appealing to the consumer.

Based on the current insights found in literature, the study proposed in this paper concerns a conjoint analysis where it is explored how the three factors discussed above (i.e., framing, promotional method and wording) could be most effectively included in a marketing communication message (i.e., a promotional poster). In particular, for each factor (i.e., referred to in conjoint analysis as an attribute) different variations (i.e., referred to as levels of the attribute) are combined in a promotional poster referring to a vegan product. By measuring the attractiveness of the poster as well as the purchase intention towards the product, it can be determined to what extent each variation contributes to the overall attractiveness and purchase intention and which combination of variations will lead to the highest level.

Methodology

A traditional full-profile conjoint method was thus chosen to be able to determine how a sample of Belgian higher education students value three different attributes of a communication message concerning a vegan burger or a vegan margarine cup. For each attribute three levels were chosen resulting in the following attributes and levels: 1) the framing of the message (i.e., health framing vs social framing vs taste framing), 2) the promotional method employed (i.e., no discount vs quantity discount vs price discount) and 3) the chosen wording to refer to the product (i.e., artificial vs plant-based vs vegan).

Of the total of 27 possible communication messages (i.e., 3x3x3 combinations of the levels of the three attributes), nine combinations were selected by use of the orthogonal method. By applying this method, of the 27 possible combinations those nine combinations were selected that resulted in each level of each attribute being present in three of the nine messages and no combinations of two levels of two different attributes appearing together more than once. Next, for each of the nine messages – also referred to as profiles in conjoint analysis - a commercial poster was created featuring either a picture of burger or a margarine cup and making use of the attributes of that profile (see figure 1 for an example of a burger poster as well as two margarine posters; providing information on how each level of each attribute was presented in the overall poster). In conclusion, a total of 18 possible promotional posters (i.e., nine for burger and nine for margarine) were created to serve as stimuli in the study.

Figure 1: Examples of stimuli

In line with a traditional conjoint analysis, each promotional poster was subsequently presented in a random order to the participants. Participants were asked to rate each poster separately on the attractiveness of the poster as well as their purchase intention towards the product. Ratings were collected by means of a slider representing a zero to 100 scale. The higher the rating, the higher the perceived attractiveness or purchase intention.

Results

A sample of 246 students enrolled in a Belgian institute for higher education (53.3% male; 45.5% female and 1.2% non-disclosed) participated in the study. Of this sample, 82.9% indicated that they follow primarily an omnivore diet. Only 1.6% of the sample indicated that they follow a vegetarian or vegan diet while 8.1% indicated to follow a pescatarian or flexitarian diet. The remaining 7.3% did

not choose a specific diet. Of the total sample 27.7% indicated to be interested in consuming more vegan products compared to 48,8% who indicated to have no interest.

A conjoint analysis, based on the principle of multiple regression analysis, was performed with the attractiveness of the poster or the purchase intention serving as the dependent variable and each level programmed as a dummy independent variable. The output provided for each level its part-worth which indicates the degree and direction of influence a level has on the independent variable whilst considering the influence of the other levels of that attribute. The total sum of the influences of all levels of one attribute is thus zero. In table 1 the part-worths are presented. In addition, for each attribute its importance value is presented in Table 2. The importance value of an attribute signals its relative importance in influencing the dependent variable compared to the other two attributes. The sum of the importance values of all three attributes should thus always be 100%.

Table 1: Part-worths of levels

Attribute	Level	“Burger”		“Margarine”	
		Attractive-ness	Purchase intention	Attractive-ness	Purchase intention
Framing	Health	-0.526	-0.436	0.294	0.370
	Social	-2.964	-3.818	-3.693	-4.863
	Taste	3.490	4.254	3.399	4.493
Promotion	No discount	1.108	1.582	0.582	1.478
	Quantity discount	-1.715	-2.978	-0.914	-2.378
	Price discount	0.606	1.396	0.332	0.900
Wording	Artificial	-4.169	-4.248	-3.188	-3.908
	Plant-based	0.393	-0.428	-0.658	-0.939
	Vegan	3.776	4.676	3.847	4.848

Table 2: Importance values of attributes

Attribute	“Burger”		“Margarine”	
	Attractive-ness	Purchase intention	Attractive-ness	Purchase intention
Framing	37.477	37.448	45.396	42.591
Promotion	16.390	21.154	9.578	17.550

Wording	46.133	41.398	45.027	39.859
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With respect to the “Burger” the wording attribute is the most important attribute as when asking participants to rate the attractiveness of the poster as when asking them to rate their level of purchase intention, while for the “Margarine” the most important attribute is the framing. Both attributes, however, are close together in their relative importance, with the promotional method being least important in all four contexts. When the objective is to boost purchase intention, however, the promotional method becomes slightly more important than when the objective is to create an attractive poster.

When considering which level or variation of each attribute is most advisable, results also seem to align between the two product categories. For both products, social framing is the only level that has a negative part-worth for as well the attractiveness of the poster as well as purchase intention. Health framing has a negative score in case of the “Burger” while for the “Margarine” it is positive. The most advisable level in case of framing seems to be taste framing due to its highest and most positive score in all four contexts.

With respect to promotional method, based on the results, providing no discount seems to be the best choice. If a promotional method is to be chosen, then the choice should be for a price discount instead of a quantity discount. This last result seems to be in line with the results presented by Bhatt and Pai (2023) that quantity discount would lead to less favourable results when compared to price discount.

Finally, for the attribute wording the use of the word “artificial” has a negative score in all contexts and should thus be avoided. For the word “plant-based” most scores signal towards not using this wording when compared to the alternatives included in this study. Wording the product as a “vegan” product has the highest score of the three levels and is thus the most suited in all four contexts. This result, however, contradicts the results reported by Ruby et al. (2024) that the label of “plant-based” was considered as more appealing than the “vegan” or “vegetarian” label.

In conclusion, based on the results of this study and the highest scores of the part-worths, the combination which provides the highest utility (and thus preference) for the consumer is a commercial poster with taste framing (instead of health or social framing), no promotion method applied (instead of a price or quantity discount) and where the product is referred to as vegan (instead of artificial or plant-based). The least appealing combination would be a poster with social framing, a quantity discount, and a reference to the product as being artificial.

Conclusion

The effect on attractiveness and purchase intention of variations of three communication elements (i.e., framing, promotion, and wording) for a vegan product were studied by use of conjoint analysis. The least important element was found to be the promotional method, with the other two elements being comparable in importance. Results indicate the most effective method of heightening purchase intention and attractiveness of the communication is to frame the product from a taste perspective (instead of a health or social perspective), to refer to the product as being vegan (instead of artificial or plant-based) and to no use a promotional method such as price or quantity discount. The primary limitation of this study is that – due to the inherent nature of conjoint analysis – the importance and influence of each element and its variations is always relative to the other elements and their variations included. No absolute conclusions can thus be drawn from these results. The results, however, do contribute to further understanding how communication messages with respect to non-meat products can be optimized.

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To discount or not to discount - evaluating the effectiveness of price reduction for food waste reduction

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Abstract

Introduction

Food waste is considered one of the major sustainability challenges, associated to environmental, social and economic consequences (Reynolds et al. 2020). Estimates indicate that households waste the largest amounts of food globally (UNEP 2024). The further down the supply chain food is wasted, the higher is the impact of that waste, due to the accumulation of used resources (Williams & Wikström 2011). To reduce this inefficient use of resources and thus its negative impacts, food waste needs to be prevented in households as well as in the earlier stages of the food system (Papargyropoulou et al. 2014).

Retailers' marketing practices influence what and how much food is wasted by retailers themselves and their customers, i.e. households (Koskela-Huotari et al. 2024). Price promotions and consumer expectations lead to overstocking, resulting in food surplus that risks being wasted before the food is sold.

However, marketing practices can also be used to reduce food waste (Calvo-Porrall 2019). A common practice amongst retailers is reducing the price of food nearing its expiration date or which has visual imperfections, so-called suboptimal food. A price discount aims to attract consumers to purchase suboptimal products whilst avoiding food surplus being wasted in-store. Discounted suboptimal food (DSF) has been explored by scholars (Aschemann-Witzel 2018a; Bech-Larsen et al. 2019; Cicatiello et al. 2019; Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2020; Chang et al. 2024; Pandey et al. 2024) and viewed as a potentially successful tool in reducing food waste (Rohm et al. 2017; Wikström et al. 2024).

However, scholars also point to the risk of overconsumption due to promotions (Ailawadi & Neslin 1998) and avoided food waste in-store being wasted in households instead (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017b), hence moving responsibility from the retailer to the consumer (Evans 2011; Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2023). Additionally, there is the risk of DSF being used reactively to handle surplus and waste rather than implementing more preventive actions (Koskela-Huotari et al. 2024).

With this ongoing study, we answer the call for evaluating food waste reduction initiatives (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017a; De Laurentiis et al. 2020). Evidence is lacking on if retailers' discounting of suboptimal food leads to waste being relocated from supermarkets to households, whether the action is effective in achieving food waste reduction, and how the practice influences consumption practices. We examine this by following specific purchases of DSF through an exploratory two-stage survey, determining whether discounted products have been wasted or consumed by households. Hence, this study aims to answer:

To what degree are discounted suboptimal food consumed and which factors influence purchase and post-purchase behaviour of such products?

Theoretical considerations

There are different parameters determining consumers' purchase decisions of suboptimal food (Aschemann-Witzel 2018b), such as products' perceived quality (Grunert 2007), altruistic motives (Sautron et al. 2015; Swedish Food Agency 2025), food safety concerns (Tsiros & Heilman 2005) and price (Grunert 2006; Swedish Food Agency 2025). Before purchase, quality is valued in the

shape of intrinsic and extrinsic quality cues (Grunert 2007). The perceived value of these cues in relation to the price will determine whether the consumer buys the product or not (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017b). A discounted price could motivate a purchase (Grunert 2006) whilst also making products be perceived as of lower value and quality than if offered at a regular price, and therefore risks being wasted (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017a). Post-purchase, situational factors in combination with sensory characteristics will result in an experienced product quality (Grunert 2007). Quality expectation pre-purchase and quality experience post-purchase will determine product satisfaction.

Price promotions can lead to a purchase or an over-purchase resulting in either consumption, overconsumption or food waste (Tsalis et al. 2021). Purchasing more than the household requires is associated with waste (Stefan et al. 2013; Stancu et al. 2016; Le Borgne et al. 2018). Multiple studies have tried to determine if food discounts lead to higher food waste levels in households. However, the results are ambiguous (Graham-Rowe et al. 2014; Silvennoinen et al. 2014; Ponis et al. 2017; Tsalis et al. 2021, 2024; van Lin et al. 2023).

Yet, the relationship between DSF and household waste remains relatively unexplored. Discounting suboptimal food is predicted not to contribute to waste in households provided that they are still of good quality and that advice on usage is given to consumers (Rohm et al. 2017). Furthermore, consumers have been shown to account for if and how the product will be used post-purchase when considering buying DSF (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017b). The consumer preferences of product-related (e.g. quality) and household-related (e.g. household demand) factors need to be fulfilled if the discounted price or the food waste-reducing possibility will be considered as a motive for purchase. Similarly, households reporting high price-proneness (including buying DSF) reported lower food waste levels (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017b). On the other hand, Giordano et al. (2019) found no positive nor negative relationship between buying discounted food products (including suboptimal food) and food waste levels.

Discounting suboptimal food differs from discounting “optimal” food as the products need to be consumed or treated to prolong shelf life shortly after purchase to avoid becoming spoiled. This limits the option of stockpiling compared to non-perishable discounted food. As a discounted price could lead to over-purchasing and a lower perceived food value, risking overconsumption or waste, we explore which post-purchase behaviours DSF products result in.

Method

Data was collected through a pilot study in a retail store located in southern Sweden from March to May 2025. We draw on a two-stage survey to generate data that captures the purchasing decisions and consumption of DSF in households. As the few previous evaluations on how DSF relates to household food waste rely on self-reporting of waste levels (Aschemann-Witzel et al. 2017b; Giordano et al. 2019), to minimise the risks of underreported food waste levels (van Herpen et al. 2019) and over-estimations on promotion-proneness (Tsalis et al. 2024), we trace the course of individual DSF item, similar to van Lin et al. (2023).

The survey method applied is partially exploratory and aims to determine consumers’ purchase and post-purchase behaviour of specific DSF items in two interrelated parts. The initial survey is distributed through stickers on DSF products and information posters in participating retail stores in Sweden. Respondents are asked about motives for purchase, how planned the purchase was and how it affected the shopping amount in whole. Furthermore, the survey covers demographics and how familiar the respondent is with the DSF practice. The respondents are asked to provide specific information about the product, either by uploading a photo of the product or providing the information in text. The product information is used to remind the respondent of its purchase in the follow-up survey.

The follow-up survey entails prompting the respondents from the initial survey to answer the second part. We send the respondents an invitation via email or SMS six days after the purchase. In the follow-up survey, we ask respondents what has happened to the specific product. If stated as wasted, reasons for this are inquired. Furthermore, we ask about purchase satisfaction and to what degree they perceived that the purchase resulted in consuming more or less than intended.

Results and implications

This ongoing study aims to evaluate to what degree the practice of DSF contributes to food waste reduction. The methodology and preliminary results of the pilot study will be presented and discussed during the conference. The future findings can serve as an indicator for stakeholders of the future relevance of DSF and how it can be used to efficiently reduce food waste. Additionally, the implementation of the exploratory method provides insights for the development of consumer surveys and evaluations.

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Testing the effectiveness of functional versus sustainability message framing in enhancing consumer acceptance of imperfect produce

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Abstract

UK retailers discard approximately 30% of all produce before it reaches the shelves due to aesthetic imperfections, significantly contributing to the country's annual food waste total of 9.5 million tonnes (FAO, 2024; WRAP, 2020). To combat this, retailers have launched 'imperfect produce' lines, offering aesthetically imperfect produce at a lower price. However, the advertising campaigns promoting these lines often rely on uniform messaging that overlooks how socio-demographic factors influence the effectiveness of the message, creating a gap in efforts to promote wider acceptance of imperfect produce (Aydinli et al., 2023; de Visser-Amundson et al., 2023)

Drawing on Construal Level Theory and Value-Basis Theory, we investigated how socioeconomic status (SES) moderates message effectiveness by examining how different consumer groups cognitively process and interpret message promoting the consumption of imperfect produce (Castagna et al., 2021; Coffino et al., 2020; Florence et al., 2022). We examined whether effectiveness of functional versus sustainability message in promoting imperfect food consumption differ depending on individuals' SES.

In a between-subjects experiment with 120 UK consumers, participants were randomly assigned to view product information framed either functionally ("Same taste and nutrition") or with a sustainability focus ("Reduce food waste"). The results revealed a significant interaction between message framing and SES ($p = .0323$). Using the Johnson-Neyman (J-N) technique, we found that the sustainability-focused message was more effective at an SES value of 1.72 SD above the mean ($b_{J-N} = .97$, $SE = .49$, $p = .05$) or higher. Our findings indicate that message type significantly impacts only high-SES individuals, with food waste reduction messages proving more persuasive. In contrast, there was no significant difference in message effectiveness among low-SES individuals. Thus, our findings establish SES as a critical moderator of message effectiveness, challenging the assumption that sustainability-framed communications are universally persuasive across segments. These insights highlight the need for targeted marketing strategies that account for socio-demographic diversity when promoting imperfect produce.

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Timing matters: Cognitive depletion and the effectiveness of benefit-focused messaging for insect foods

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Abstract

The global demand for sustainable protein alternatives has positioned insect-based foods as a promising but challenging opportunity in Western markets. Despite strong nutritional profiles and minimal environmental impact, consumer acceptance remains a primary barrier (Miglietta et al., 2025; Pozharliev et al., 2023; Puteri et al., 2023). Prior research suggests that highlighting the benefits of consuming edible insect (health and environmental benefits) can increase consumer willingness to consume edible insect products (Meng et al., 2024). However, our study introduces a critical temporal boundary condition to this effect, offering more nuanced understanding on the persuasiveness of different benefit-focused (health vs. social) across different time of day (morning vs. evening).

Study 1 involved 288 undergraduate students randomly assigned to four conditions: depleting task versus non-depleting task, and no benefit versus benefit message. After removing incomplete responses ($n = 17$), the final sample size was 271. Participants viewed an insect-based product advertisement with either health and social benefits or no benefit message, then reported their intention to consume. ANOVA results showed no significant effects for depletion task ($F(1, 267) = 2.45, p = .12$) or benefit message presence ($F(1, 267) = .57, p = .45$), but a significant interaction effect was found ($F(1, 267) = 4.94, p = .027$). In the non-depleting condition, benefit messages increased intention to consume ($M = 3.86, SD = 1.82$) compared to no benefit messages ($M = 3.20, SD = 1.78; F(1, 267) = 4.39, p = .037$).

Study 2 examined how time of day influenced the impact of health versus social benefit messages on insect-based food consumption. Data were collected in the morning ($n = 147$) and evening ($n = 147$) from U.S. adults recruited via CloudResearch Connect. After removing mismatches between local time and session time ($n = 7$), the final sample was 287. Participants were randomly assigned to no benefit, health benefit, or social benefit message conditions. ANOVA showed a significant effect for message type ($F(1, 281) = 3.18, p = .043$), but not for time of day ($F(1, 281) = .02, p = .89$) or interaction ($F(1, 281) = .13, p = .88$). In the morning, social benefit messages increased intention to consume ($M = 3.06, SD = 2.09$) compared to no benefit messages ($M = 2.28, SD = 1.76; t(142) = 2.03, p = .044$). No differences appeared between health and no benefit messages in the morning or among any message types in the evening.

These findings contribute to sustainable food marketing by identifying time-of-day as a moderator of message effectiveness. Marketers should focus on morning messaging to highlight social benefits and use sensory appeal for evening campaigns, offering insights into promoting environmentally beneficial yet unfamiliar foods.

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The protein transition from the consumer perspective: Speeding up or slowing down?

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Abstract

Aim

The evolution towards a more sustainable, equitable and balanced protein system – also referred to as the ‘protein transition’ or the ‘protein shift’ – figures high on many agendas, including the socio-economic, political, ethical and food technological ones. This contribution focuses on the consumer perspective and discusses the role of health and sustainability – amongst others – as possible drivers of food choice while accounting for diversity in terms of personal characteristics, attitudes, interests and motivations. Scrutinising the case of Flanders, Belgium, where the ambition is to reverse the animal-to-plant ratio of protein contribution in the diet from 60/40 to 40/60 by 2030, the aim is to find an answer to the question whether the protein is speeding up or slowing down.

Method

Findings from selected consumer studies are shared taking the recent evolution of meat consumption and the Green Deal protein strategy’s ambition as points of departure. The selected consumer studies address the citizen attitude – consumer behaviour gap, the mapping of consumer perceptions and attitudes, the perceived importance of health and sustainability relative to other interests and food product attributes, as well as determinants of purchase intentions and behaviour in relation to alternative proteins. Market segmentation studies address diversity among consumers and willingness-to-pay studies reveal the market potential for foods with a health and sustainability benefit.

Results

Empirical findings illustrate that the concepts of health and sustainability match each other for a large majority of consumers, although only about one third may be strongly interested in both concepts while making food choices. Since favourable attitudes towards health and sustainability do not systematically translate into according behaviours, the attitude-behaviour gap is discussed, providing insight into why individual consumers may not consistently act in line with their attitude as a citizen. The addressed cases concern plant-based foods, foods with microalgae protein, insects and cell-culture derived meat, each with their factors of appeal or repel from the consumer perspective. Specific challenges emerge with respect to the ultra-processed status of foods with alternative proteins, micro- and macro-economic evolutions, as well as product branding and labelling.

Conclusions

This contribution argues that the protein transition has been on-going for at least a quarter century in Western societies and that – from a consumer perspective – it tends to slow down rather than to speed up recently. Based on the presented insights, implications and challenges for food policy, public and private communication, food technology and innovation, and food marketing will be discussed.

How many claims are too many? The moderating role of claim diversity in food advertising

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Abstract

In 2024, global advertising expenditures reached approximately \$1.1 trillion, with 22 % stemming from the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods, including food products (Statista, 2025). To maximize the return on these investments, advertising messages must be persuasive (Wang *et al.*, 2022; Shu and Carlson, 2014; Cacioppo and Petty, 1979). Research indicates that the number of positive claims—unverified assertions from the seller, such as "no added sugar"—is a critical factor in advertising persuasion (Raju *et al.*, 2009; Kwon and Nayakankupam, 2015; Chrysochou and Grunert, 2014). Despite its importance, research on the optimal number of positive claims remains limited and yields conflicting results. For instance, Shu and Carlson (2014) identified a persuasive effect with three claims—termed the "charm of three"—whereas Wang *et al.* (2022) found that up to six claims may be optimal if mental imagery is activated. Building on persuasion theory, the present research contributes to the literature by demonstrating that the optimal number of positive claims in food advertising depends on the nature of the combined claims, which can be homogeneous (focusing on a single benefit, such as healthiness) or heterogeneous (addressing multiple benefits like healthiness, hedonism, food safety, or environmental friendliness).

The main study employed a 4 (number of positive claims: 1, 2, 3, or 4) × 2 (nature of claims: homogeneous or heterogeneous) between-subjects experimental design. Two pretests were conducted to select a neutral cereal brand (n = 71) and to identify homogeneous and heterogeneous claims (n = 151), respectively. A quota-based sample, representative of the province of Quebec, Canada (age, gender, region), consisted of 761 participants from the Léger Opinion LEO panel. The main effect of the ANOVA indicated that perceived quality was higher when three claims were presented in the advertisement compared to a single claim, replicating the "charm of three" (Shu and Carlson, 2014). However, the interaction effect revealed that the optimal quantity depends on the nature of the claims: four for heterogeneous claims and one for homogeneous claims. A moderated mediation analysis using the structural equation modeling tool SmartPLS 4 (bootstrap sample of 5,000) explained this impact, showing that adding heterogeneous claims increases consumers' cognitive load more than adding homogeneous claims. In line with the literature, increased cognitive load, intensified by the growing complexity of various elements, reduces consumers' mental resources, reducing counter-argumentation and increasing perceived product quality through heightened persuasion (Pantoja *et al.*, 2016). Brand managers should strategically select the claims they combine in their advertisements. It is advisable not to accumulate homogeneous claims focused solely on healthiness, such as "excellent source of fiber," "low in saturated fat", "low in cholesterol", or "no added sugar"; a single claim is sufficient. This is particularly important in the context of advertising clutter (Pieters *et al.*, 2010). These findings extend persuasion theory by showing that cognitive load is shaped not only by the number of claims but also by their conceptual diversity. This nuance invites further exploration of how heterogeneous content affects consumer information processing.

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Cheese over steak? The role of milk and dairy products in a flexitarian diet

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Abstract

Introduction

The role of meat and milk is increasingly changing in Western societies (Strässner and Wirth, 2024). An increasing number of people are reducing their consumption of animal-sourced foods (ASF), especially meat (Dagevos, 2021; Adamczyk et al., 2022), motivated by environmental, ethical, and health concerns (Dhont and Ioannidou, 2024; Strässner and Wirth, 2024). For instance, in Germany, meat consumption decreased by 11 kg per capita between 2010 and 2023 (BZL, 2024), while liquid milk consumption also declined by 8 kg per capita in the same time period (BLE, 2024). Although reducing meat consumption is often viewed as key addressing environmental and health challenges (Dagevos, 2021), dairy consumption can make an important difference in solving environmental problems (Springmann et al., 2018; Dagevos, 2021; Autio et al., 2023). Due to CO₂e-emissions, the reduction in the consumption of milk and dairy products is as essential in order to achieve internationally set climate goals. Yet, the focus of the vast majority of studies is on meat consumption only.

Parallel to these developments, flexitarianism is gaining in popularity (Dagevos, 2021; Strässner and Wirth, 2024). It is described as a diet in which people are open to reduce their meat consumption and/or are actively considering reducing their meat consumption (Kemper et al., 2023). Especially in Germany it has become more common: 30% report eating less meat. Compared to the European average, where 16% of the population describe themselves as flexitarians (Perez-Cueto et al., 2024), this is a large share of the population. Nevertheless, flexitarians are a heterogeneous group with varying subjective motives and behaviors regarding eating ASF (Strässner and Wirth, 2024). A study by Bayudan et al. (2025) found that flexitarians reduce their average meat consumption, yet consume hardly any less milk, yogurt, and cheese.

A conscious reduction in animal products typically starts with the elimination of meat, with milk and dairy products often being questioned at a later stage (Autio et al., 2023). Despite the growing popularity of plant-based products in a flexitarian diet, it remains unclear to what extent and in what ways flexitarians might substitute milk and dairy products for meat, and what role milk and dairy products play in their diet generally. The aim of this study is to investigate how a deliberate reduction in meat consumption affects the consumption patterns of milk and dairy products in everyday diets of self-declared flexitarians in Germany. In particular, the following research questions will be analyzed:

RQ 1: Does the consumption of milk and dairy products change among flexitarians when they consciously reduce their meat consumption?

RQ 2: Which milk and dairy products do flexitarians prefer to replace or supplement meat, and why?

RQ 3: What are the factors that influence the change in milk and dairy product consumption among flexitarians?

Data and method

The pre-registered study (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/W7529>) was approved by the University's Ethics Committee.

In order to better understand flexitarians' food choices and decision-making processes during mealtimes, a qualitative explorative approach was chosen. One-to-one narrative interviews were conducted in February 2025, as they allow open conversations about personal experiences (Anderson and Kirkpatrick, 2016). This method allows deeper insights into individual diets that are difficult to capture using quantitative methods.

Participants were recruited through flyers posted around the university. To participate, individuals had to be between 18-30 years old (as they are often "early adopters" who accept new products and ideas more quickly) and follow a flexitarian diet. A total of 20 participants took part in the study, including 13 men and 7 women. To ensure anonymity, each participant was given a pseudonym for identification purposes.

The interviews were transcribed using NoScribe. The data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach of reflexive thematic analysis. Using MAXQDA, we created initial codes that address the data and subsequent overarching "themes" that capture the essential content of these codes. The following themes were searched for, reviewed, defined, and named: *Consumption changes*, *Justifications*, *Influencing factors*, and *Personal advantages*.

Results and discussion

The first theme *Consumption changes* highlights the effect of meat reduction on the consumption of milk and dairy products. The theme of *Justifications* identifies participants' main concerns and their reasons for continuing to consume milk and dairy. Next, the theme *Influencing factors* outlines the external factors that influence participants' food decision-making. The final theme *Personal advantages* identifies the main reasons for consuming dairy products.

Consumption changes

The total sample consciously reduces its meat consumption, yet milk consumption remains very high among some respondents:

"But I've just generally always consumed lots and lots of milk and lots and lots of dairy products too." (Leo).

"As far as dairy products are concerned, I would say that I consume a lot of them." (Max).

A major part of the flexitarians surveyed stated that their consumption of dairy products had not changed as a result of meat reduction and that they do not consider milk and dairy products as substitutes:

"My consumption of dairy products hasn't really changed as a result, no." (Liv).

"I don't have the feeling that I'm substituting reduced meat consumption with more dairy products." (Max).

Kemper et al. (2023) support this, as they show that flexitarians are most likely to favor plant-based substitutes and often replace meat with plant-based alternatives. Participants also agreed that they eat fish almost once a week and described it as an adequate substitute for meat. However, some participants are increasingly opting for organic or pasture-raised milk in order to take environmental and animal welfare aspects into account:

"I always buy pasture milk at home." (Eva).

"When it comes to dairy products, I actually always buy organic products in order to [...] take animal welfare into account a little more and also other environmental aspects." (Liv).

Some flexitarians consume more dairy products, especially for cold meals such as breakfast and dinner, yet notice this change only after a brief reflection:

"It's possible that I [...] eat more cheese for breakfast." (Karl).

"Because I don't put salami on my bread now, it's more likely to be the cheese or some kind of spread. [...] That would be silly if it wasn't. I have to substitute it somehow, in that sense. That means I buy more cheese, no doubt about it." (Ben).

“Yes, just thinking about it now, my fridge is already rather fuller with dairy products than usual.” (Tilda).

Nevertheless, a few participants reduce their consumption of dairy products and are turning to alternatives, especially cow's milk and yogurt:

“Well, I [...] always drink soy milk or almond milk or oat milk.” (Fritz).

“I actually prefer oat yoghurt or soy yoghurt.” (Elias).

Justifications

Many interviewees are aware of issues associated with dairy farming; especially ecological issues are expressed. In this context, the negative impact of milk production on climate is often mentioned, in particular methane emissions by dairy cows:

“I absolutely see the disadvantages, so I'm very aware that [...] the climate impact from methane, that those are big with dairy products.” (Liv).

Indeed, livestock farming contributes significantly to direct greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In Germany, in 2023, around 35.5 million tons of CO₂e-emissions were directly attributed to livestock farming, which accounts for around 68% of agricultural emissions and around 5% of Germany's total emissions. In 2022, methane emissions from ruminants' digestive process accounted for 76% of agricultural methane emissions and were caused almost entirely (95%) by cattle and dairy farming (UBA, 2024). Other interviewees are also aware of the environmental footprint, but relativize it:

“There is a lot of talk about how much of a carbon footprint a liter of milk has. My personal opinion is that milk is “climate-damaging” in quotation marks. But [...] it depends a bit on the husbandry system.” (Linus).

Despite the expressed ecological concerns, it does not necessarily lead to anyone actively reconsidering or changing their own consumption behavior with regard to dairy products. Eva, for example, admits:

“Climate-wise, of course, it's already a factor that I like to ignore, if I'm honest.”

In addition to the environmental aspects, the ethical dimension of milk production is also discussed, in particular the cow-calf separation:

“For example, that the calves are taken away from the cows [...] is a problem.” (Liv).

Literature also shows that in cattle farming, the early separation of cow and calf is particularly criticized, especially because of the presumed emotional consequences after separation (Placzek et al. 2021). Yet, an ambivalent attitude towards this issue became clear in the interviews:

“Of course, there is also such a discussion around the issue of separating cows from calves [...]. So, I can kind of understand the idea, but for me it's not a crucial point to say I'm not going to consume dairy products anymore.” (Linus).

Furthermore, the question of transparency in milk production was raised:

“Can you look behind the scenes? Is it so comprehensible? I really don't know that much about it.” (Ava).

“But I do know that it is ultimately difficult to understand the conditions under which milk is produced.” (Ben).

Others are acknowledging problems coming from dairy husbandry, yet they are not drawing any personal conclusions from it and continue consuming dairy products:

“I could think of reasons why it might make sense not to take dairy products, such as animal rights or animal welfare. But if I'm honest, that's less of an issue now.” (Wolf).

“There are certainly problems associated with it. But I don't find the production of milk [...] problematic at all.” (Leo).

This could be due to the fact that dairy farming is generally viewed less critically than pig and poultry farming (Christoph-Schulz et al., 2018). Moreover, the further removed a product is from its animal origin, the more likely it is to be consumed (Docherty and Jasper, 2023; Benningstad and Kunst, 2020). This was strengthened by Lea's statement:

„It just doesn't look so animalistic. Instead, you say, yes, it's just cheese.“

Nevertheless, individual health concerns can limit the consumption of dairy products. Few respondents reported having digestive problems or skin irritations related to milk consumption.

“If I consume too many dairy products, I sometimes have problems with digestion.” (Calle).

“I've had pretty bad acne for the last few years and have tried to reduce my dairy consumption so much” (Erik).

Influencing factors

For flexitarians, social factors (family, friends) and the eating context (eating out/at parental home) do not play such an influential role on the consumption of dairy products:

“I have many friends who are vegan, but [...] I would say that I still eat dairy products in such situations because it is still socially accepted [...] and with meat, there are actually social contexts in which I avoid it for these reasons.” (Liv).

As signaled by Liv, social factors and the eating context have a greater influence on meat consumption, making it more challenging to reduce meat in social gatherings (Kemper and White, 2021).

Social media is playing an increasing role, especially influencers promoting e.g., vegan dishes:

“Instagram is also an inspiring source, because I've also seen people making pasta from scratch and then the sauce was usually just with soy cream.” (Alba).

Indeed, social media has a substantial influence on consumer behavior, giving users access to a wide range of rich content on food-related topics (Rini et al., 2024).

The marketing of dairy products also appears to be more successful than that of meat, which gives them a better image:

“Do meat products have a different image than dairy products?” (Ava).

“They also have really good marketing. When I see the advertising, it appeals to me.” (Tom).

Milk alternatives often seem harder to obtain, which could make the switch more difficult:

“I've also tried vegan cheese, but I think the availability is very limited.” (Finn).

“Yes, and also the availability. The nearest supermarket to us is Netto [...]. It just doesn't have that many vegan products [...].” (Zoe).

In addition, many consumers lack satisfactory alternatives, in terms of taste and consistency. Participants were critical of vegan cheese's taste or perceived the range as insufficient.

“And the cheese substitutes didn't really pick me up either.” (Ben).

“What I don't like so much is vegan cheese. [...]. Either it doesn't melt at all, or you can taste it and you can taste it very strongly.” (Tom).

Personal advantages

Looking at the personal advantages, for many interviewees the taste of dairy products is the main reason why they continue to consume them:

“Unfortunately, I am actually an advocate of cow's milk for taste reasons. [...]. I find the taste a bit more authentic.” (Ava).

“Yogurt and skyr, because I like the taste.” (Calle).

Cheese in particular is seen as essential by all interviewees, as it is often seen as a flavor enhancer:

“I think sliced cheese or parmesan are really awesome.” (Alba).

“Well, if someone would ask me why I couldn't become vegan, I would always say it's the gratinated cheese. It's just a way of life.” (Ben).

“I would say because it gives a bit of flavor.” (Ole).

Respondents are torn between the desire to translate their ethical and environmental concerns about dairy production into their consumption behavior and the satisfaction that cheese offers in terms of enjoyment. In this regard, cheese could cause difficulties in switching to an all-plant diet (Docherty and Jasper, 2023), similar to the findings of Bryant (2019), who found that taste was a barrier to limiting meat. Many flexitarians continue to consume dairy products because they grew up with it and it has always been an integral part of their daily diet:

“It's more of a habit thing. When I have breakfast, I eat a cheese roll.” (Lea).

“But I also think it's a taste that you've known since you were a child.” (Ava).

Another key factor in the consumption of dairy products is their perceived health benefits. Many see it as a valuable source of a natural protein or appreciate the probiotic effects of products such as yogurt or kefir:

“[Dairy products are] healthy to a certain extent, for nutrients like calcium [...]” (Liv).

“And I think I was in the mood for kefir again, because [...] they say probiotics or something like that.” (Alba).

“One benefit would be the natural protein intake.” (Ava).

Conclusion

The results of this study show that dairy products, cheese in particular, continue to have a firm place in the diet of flexitarians despite a conscious reduction in meat. Although environmental and animal welfare concerns towards dairy farming are expressed, they rarely lead to a change in behavior when it comes to the consumption of milk and dairy products. Taste, habit and positive health perceptions prevail.

In order to promote more sustainable food-related decisions, improved plant-based cheese alternatives should be made available in terms of taste and consistency. Moreover, transparency in milk production should be strengthened and communicated more specifically (medially) alongside animal welfare standards. Furthermore, the distribution of additional costs of sustainable production along the entire value chain should also be considered. Finally, it is clear that especially cheese will continue to be a central part of many flexitarians' diets in the future.

References available upon request.

Assessing high-fibre food product launches and claims between 2021 - 2025 in the UK marketplace: Findings from the MINTEL Global New Products database

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Abstract

Introduction

Dietary fibre plays a critical role in gastrointestinal health and is linked to a reduced risk of chronic diseases (Reynolds et al., 2019). In the UK, however, fibre intake remains alarmingly low. Government guidelines recommend approximately 30g of fibre per day for adults, yet the average intake is around 18–20g, which is only 60% of the target (Food and Drink Federation, 2021). In fact, only about 9% of UK adults meet the 30 g/day recommendation (Food and Drink Federation, 2021), highlighting a substantial “fibre gap” in the population. This shortfall represents a public health concern and an opportunity for food and drink manufacturers to address consumer needs through new product development (NPD). By developing and promoting high-fibre products, companies can help bridge this nutritional gap while tapping into a growing market of health-conscious consumers.

From a marketing and consumer behaviour perspective, fibre content claims on packaging have become a pivotal tool for influencing purchase decisions and shaping brand perceptions (Talati et al., 2017). Nutrient content claims such as “high in fibre” are increasingly used as powerful marketing differentiators, as health-conscious shoppers actively seek products that support wellness. Emphasising added or high fibre on the front of a pack can confer a health halo effect, a single healthy attribute creating an overall perception of a healthier product, thereby boosting a product’s appeal. Despite the growing prevalence of fibre claims, there is a lack of insight from a consumer behaviour and marketing perspective into how these claims are being used across different product types and how visibly they are displayed. Many gaps persist in terms of categories leading the high-fibre trend, how companies present fibre claims (textually, visually, or numerically) to grab consumer attention, and do products with different claim types vary in actual fibre content. Furthermore, there is a gap in terms of analysing the interplay between price and fibre content.

To address these gaps, this study examines high-fibre product launches in the UK from May 2021 to April 2025 using Mintel’s Global New Products Database (GNPD). This study utilises big data to quantify market trends, leveraging the GNPD as a rich source of product information to generate consumer and competitive insights. Big data analytics can reveal patterns that strengthen firms’ innovation capabilities and competitive advantage by guiding product development decisions (Jagadish et al., 2014). The research focuses on three key questions: (1) Is there an upward trend in high-fibre food and drink product launches meeting recommended fibre levels? (2) How are fibre claims presented on packaging (position and format)? (3) How do fibre content and price vary across product categories and claim types? Answering these questions provides an evidence-based understanding of the high-fibre segment’s evolution and offers guidance for marketing strategies. The following sections present a brief literature background, outline the methodology, and discuss the results, before examining implications for marketing, consumer behaviour, and industry strategy.

Literature Review

Dietary Fibre and Consumer Health

Dietary fibre is broadly acknowledged for its health benefits, including improved digestive function, better glycaemic control, cholesterol reduction, and enhanced satiety (Reynolds et al., 2019). A high-fibre diet is associated with a significant reduction in risk of non-communicable diseases, yet most UK consumers fall far short of the recommended intake (Food and Drink Federation, 2021). This discrepancy is partly attributed to dietary habits and limited consumer awareness of fibre's importance (Food and Drink Federation, 2021).

On-Pack Nutrition and Health Claims

Food packaging is a primary communication channel through which consumers learn about a product's nutritional attributes. Nutrition claims, such as "high in fibre," describe the presence of a nutrient, while health claims link a nutrient to specific health outcomes (Talati et al., 2017). In the UK and EU, such claims are regulated (EU Regulation 1924/2006) to ensure that they are substantiated, which enhances consumer trust. Front-of-pack (FOP) labels, in particular, are more likely to be noticed by consumers and have been shown to influence purchase decisions by creating a health halo effect (Peltier et al., 2015; Oostenbach et al., 2019).

Trends in High-Fibre Product Development

Recently, food manufacturers have shown a growing interest in high-fibre product innovations. Industry initiatives like the Food and Drink Federation's "Action on Fibre" campaign (Food and Drink Federation, 2021) have spurred companies to reformulate products and introduce fibre-enhanced lines. Big data analytics platforms like Mintel GNPD enable firms to identify trends, benchmark competitors, and target white spaces in the market, reinforcing fibre fortification as a competitive strategy (Jagadish et al., 2014). This study builds on these insights by systematically analysing the high-fibre product landscape in the UK over a four-year period.

Methodology

This study utilised Mintel's Global New Products Database (GNPD) to track UK food and beverage product launches from May 2021 to April 2025. The GNPD is a comprehensive market intelligence platform that records detailed product information, including nutritional content, ingredient lists, pricing, and on-pack claims, making it an invaluable resource for analysing market trends.

A search was conducted in the GNPD for all UK product launches during the study period that featured a high-fibre claim. Two inclusion criteria were applied: (1) the product must contain at least 6 g of fibre per 100 g (or 6 g/100 mL for beverages), in line with EU definitions of a "high in fibre" claim; and (2) the product must feature an on-pack fibre-related claim (e.g. "high in fibre" or "added fibre"). From an initial pool of 269,423 UK product entries, 1,997 products met these criteria and were included in the analysis. Two products were subsequently excluded as they were categorised as pet food.

Each product was coded for category (e.g. snacks, breakfast cereals, bakery, and healthcare), fibre content (g per 100 g), launch type (new product, new variety/range extension, new packaging, relaunch), price (in GBP per unit), and the style of fibre claim on the packaging. Fibre claims were further categorised based on: (1) Claim position (Front-of-pack, back-of-pack, or side-of-pack), and (2) claim format (text only e.g. high in fibre, text with an image, text with a tick, text with a numeric figure, or text enclosed within a box or design element).

Descriptive statistics were used to summarise the launch trends by year and product category. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare mean

fibre content across product categories, claim types, packaging positions, and launch types, with Tukey's post-hoc tests to identify specific group differences. A Pearson correlation test was used to examine the relationship between fibre content and price. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Analyses were conducted using SPSS (v27).

Results

A total of 1,997 high-fibre products were launched in the UK during the study period. The annual number of launches increased steadily: 278 in 2021, 451 in 2022, 530 in 2023, and 584 in 2024, indicating robust market momentum for high-fibre products. The overall analysis revealed that snacks (39.3%) and breakfast cereals (21.1%) dominated the high-fibre product market, while healthcare products (e.g., chia seeds and berry blends) exhibited the highest mean fibre content (27.19g/100g, $p < 0.05$). Overall, products averaged 12–13 g of fibre per 100g. Significant differences were observed among product categories. Healthcare products, due to their concentrated nature, far exceeded other categories. Snacks and bakery products typically ranged from 10 to 12 g per 100 g, while breakfast cereals, though traditionally associated with fibre, often met only the minimum criteria. Moreover, new-to-market product launches exhibited higher fibre content (mean = 13.37g/100 g) than new variety or reformulated products ($p < 0.05$).

Further analysis categorised the claims into five distinct types of fibre claims: (1) Phrasing only (33.4%), (2) Phrasing enclosed within (25.5%), Phrasing plus an image (22.6%), Phrasing with a tick (17.1%), and Phrasing with numbers (1.3%). Products featuring combined phrasing and numerical claims demonstrated the highest fibre content (16.23g/100g) compared to those with generic claims ($p < 0.05$). Most categories showed a tendency to use combined claim styles (e.g. text plus one variable such as visuals), on a majority of their high-fibre products; for instance, bakery and snacks used imagery or icons on 70% of products. However, products from the sugar and gum confectionary and soup categories did not make a combined claim on any product. Most products placed their fibre claims on the front- of-pack, with a smaller portion displayed on the side or back. This strategic placement aligns with evidence that FOP claims enhance consumer attention and perceived product healthfulness.

The analysis identified a weak but statistically significant positive correlation between fibre content and price ($r = 0.10$, $p = 0.001$). While specialised nutritional drinks and supplements commanded the highest average prices (approximately £14.78 per unit), products in categories such as fruit & vegetables were priced lowest (£1.65 unit). The modest correlation suggests that although higher fibre may attract a premium, many high-fibre foods remain competitively priced in the market.

Discussion

This analysis highlights substantial variation in the fibre content and pricing of newly launched high-fibre products across different categories and claim strategies. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for both marketing professionals and public health advocates.

Fibre claims

Fibre claims are increasing year on year, with new-to-market products more frequently adopting front-of-pack claims. The steady increase reflects a broader industry trend towards meeting consumer demand for healthier options. The data indicate that fibre fortification is not limited to traditional cereal and bakery products but is expanding into innovative categories, including functional foods and beverages. This evolution underscores the importance of product innovation in addressing the fibre gap (Jagadish et al., 2014).

The dominance of front-of-pack fibre claims is in line with previous research showing that FOP labels significantly influence consumer perceptions (Peltier et al., 2015). By ensuring that the fibre benefit is visible at a glance, brands create an immediate impression of healthfulness. However, the varied claim formats suggest that there is no one-size-fits-all approach. Whilst combined claims (e.g., text with

visuals) are common in categories such as bakery and snacks, certain types of fibre claims remain underutilised, particularly in categories such as sugar and gum confectionary and soups. In particular, numeric fibre claims (explicit statements of fibre quantity, such as “contains 8g of fibre”) are relatively rare on packaging. This is despite our observation that products using numeric claims often have higher fibre content than those with more general claims and may pose a missed opportunity for enhanced transparency. Numeric claims can provide consumers with concrete information about fibre levels, thereby facilitating informed choices. In contrast, generic text-only claims, though more prevalent, might not fully convey the nutritional advantage, particularly to the increasingly health-literate consumer. These insights suggest significant opportunities for manufacturers to refine marketing strategies, optimise claim presentation, and differentiate products in competitive markets.

Consumer behaviour and pricing

The weak yet significant correlation between fibre content and price indicates that while higher fibre content can be associated with a premium, this premium is modest. This suggests that high-fibre products can be made accessible across different price tiers. From a consumer behaviour perspective, a modest price premium for additional fibre is unlikely to deter purchases, especially if consumers perceive a tangible health benefit. However, companies should be cautious; if consumers begin to associate high-fibre products exclusively with high prices, they may opt for lower-priced alternatives. A tiered pricing strategy that offers both premium and value high-fibre options may therefore be most effective.

Innovative product development

The finding that new-to-market product launches tend to have higher fibre content compared to reformulated products suggests that companies are using innovation to differentiate new offerings. This aligns with the notion that significant product innovations, rather than minor tweaks, are more likely to meet the evolving demands of health-conscious consumers. The integration of fibre into novel product categories, such as ready meals or non-traditional snacks, represents an important area for future research and development. Leveraging advancements in food technology (e.g. the development of soluble fibres that do not compromise taste or texture) will be crucial to sustaining this trend (Reynolds et al., 2019).

Marketing implications

For marketers, these insights translate into actionable strategies. First, positioning fibre claims prominently on the front-of-pack can enhance consumer trust and attract attention in a competitive marketplace. Second, including numeric information where feasible can differentiate a product by quantifying its benefits, even if this approach is currently underused. Third, marketing communications should reinforce the overall health benefits of fibre, linking it to modern concerns such as gut health, satiety, and even mood regulation. This can be particularly effective when combined with educational campaigns to raise consumer awareness about the daily fibre requirement and the associated health advantages.

Industry and public health impact

The strategic implications extend beyond marketing to public health. Given that a significant portion of the UK population fails to meet daily fibre recommendations, the promotion of high-fibre products can contribute to closing the fibre gap. Industry stakeholders, including manufacturers and retailers, should therefore consider not only the commercial benefits of fibre innovation but also the broader societal impact. Public health campaigns, in collaboration with the food industry, can amplify the message that increasing fibre intake is both a health imperative and an achievable goal through everyday dietary choices.

Strategic implications for food industry stakeholders

Based on these findings, several strategic recommendations emerge for food industry stakeholders. Companies should invest in R&D to develop high-fibre versions of products in fibre-poor categories (e.g. ready meals, dairy alternatives, and confectionery). Leveraging advanced fibre ingredients can enhance product appeal without sacrificing taste or texture. The enhancement of on-pack communication could be utilised to educate consumers and differentiate products in the marketplace, by creating consistent and prominent fibre claims. Consideration should be given to incorporating numeric fibre claims on the packaging to convey precise information. Furthermore, marketers should capitalise on the strong, positive associations with fibre by linking claims to broader health benefits, such as improved gut health and weight management, while ensuring that the products deliver on these promises.

To appeal to a broad consumer base, manufacturers should offer both premium and value high-fibre options. Maintaining affordability for staple products is key to encouraging widespread dietary fibre consumption, particularly among price-sensitive consumers.

Collaborative campaigns between industry, public health bodies, and government can help raise awareness of the benefits of fibre. Clear, transparent communication about fibre's role in supporting digestive health, satiety, and overall wellness can strengthen the credibility of fibre claims and boost consumer confidence.

Conclusion

The study contributes to marketing research by providing empirical evidence on the interplay between product innovation, claim presentation, and consumer perception in the high-fibre segment. The findings advance theoretical understanding in consumer behaviour and brand strategy, offering a foundation for future research into the role of nutritional claims in influencing purchase decisions and fostering brand loyalty.

The period from 2021 to 2025 has witnessed a substantial increase in high-fibre product launches in the UK. This trend reflects a broader shift in consumer preferences toward healthier, functional foods and underscores the potential for fibre fortification to play a pivotal role in product innovation. The study demonstrates that, while high-fibre claims are effectively used to enhance brand perception and consumer choice, there is scope for more precise communication, particularly through numeric claims, that could further boost consumer confidence.

For industry stakeholders, these insights highlight both challenges and opportunities. By embracing innovative product development, standardising on-pack fibre communication, adopting inclusive pricing strategies, and investing in consumer education, companies can not only capture a lucrative market segment but also contribute to public health objectives by closing the fibre gap. As consumers increasingly seek healthier options and as regulatory pressures push for more transparent nutritional information, the convergence of commercial and public health interests will ensure that high-fibre products remain a dynamic and growing segment of the food industry.

In conclusion, the robust growth in high-fibre product launches is a promising sign for both industry and public health. Strategic actions that integrate innovation, clear communication, and value pricing will be essential to sustain and accelerate this momentum, ultimately helping consumers make healthier choices and ensuring that the benefits of fibre are accessible to all.

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Heroes and villains: Investigating the narratives of plant-based meat alternative brands

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Abstract

This study explores the narratives developed and disseminated by companies selling novel plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA). Targeting flexitarian consumers, these products have been introduced to the marketplace to help reduce meat consumption under the premise of food system sustainability. Despite initial rapid growth, PBMA have failed to meet market predictions. Narratives, as persuasive marketing tools, have the potential to facilitate a shift in food consumption behaviours; therefore, examining narratives could give insight into why the sector struggles to move from niche to mainstream.

Research concerning PBMA narratives has focused on the protein transition and the sector's promised narrative that claim PBMA are healthier, kinder, and better for the environment than meat. This study investigates the narratives of individual companies and how their narratives are used to compete with other PBMA and traditional meat producers to grow both the market of PBMA and their market share within the sector. New Zealand serves as the backdrop for this research, as it is a nation that depends on its agricultural sector for economic growth but is also under pressure to address the adverse effects of its food system.

Data have been collected from interviews with various stakeholders (e.g., startups, established companies, advocacy groups) and marketing and communications materials. The data was analysed using an inductive approach to identify narrative themes, storytelling elements (e.g., characters, plot), and their meanings.

Preliminary findings show that PBMA companies use a range of narratives to differentiate themselves and engage consumers. All refer to a central 'hero' in their narratives. This hero is either (or a combination of) the founder(s), the brand, or the consumer. There are, however, differences in the narratives created by startups and established companies. Startups are typically motivated by personal values portraying animals and the animal agriculture sector as the villains, with the government and supermarkets in supporting roles. The climate, environment and humans (and their health) are depicted as victims. In contrast, the established companies (that also sell animal-based foods) emphasise the substitutability of PBMA, its taste, and its convenience, steering clear of values-based claims.

Our findings outline the different approaches that different PBMA companies take to communicate with consumers to grow the market and their share of the PBMA market. The 'underdog' hero approach taken by startups is typified by their drive to 'stay true to their values'. Conversely, more established companies take a more traditional marketing approach to market growth, leveraging the more tangible factors associated with PBMA consumption. Regardless of the narratives used, the market fails to grow at the expected rate, showing that neither tactic is currently paying dividends.

This research contributes to the academic literature on marketing narratives' role in novel food adoption and the protein transition. The findings will help inform marketing practitioners, academics, policymakers, and investors to understand and improve current narrative strategies.

Harnessing the effect of portion size on food consumption towards consumers' well-being: A first glance and the role of defaults

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Abstract

Introduction

Obesity and overweight levels have risen continuously worldwide over the past two decades, with 43% of adults currently considered to be overweight and 16% obese, while (WHO, 2024). Healthy eating is a major factor for avoiding chronic diseases, and obesity (Maksimenko et al., 2024). While obesity and overweight rates are constantly rising, it is important to identify the underlying reasons and to identify policies towards healthy eating. Food packaging is required by governmental laws to include information about nutrients, energy either per serving or per 100 grams. These laws aim at assisting consumers towards optimal portion sizes and ultimately healthier food consumption (Maksimenko et al., 2024, Papagiannaki et al., 2024).

The role of portion size in guiding healthy eating has received some research scrutiny. Interestingly, the “super-sized” or “king-sized” portion trend seems to prevail and evolve despite portion size guidelines and insights towards healthy eating (Young & Nestle, 2012). More specifically, portion size control provides several benefits including getting all the necessary nutrients from food without overeating and ultimately having an overall healthy eating lifestyle (Maksimenko et al., 2024).

From ready-to-eat meals to take-outs but also home-cooked meals, portion size are continuously growing, and people consume even more calories, making portion control even more challenging. Portion size effect refers to the effect of portion size on energy intake. Portion size and its effect on food consumption is the focus of this paper. The goal of this paper is to review extant knowledge regarding portion size effect. Next, we present extant knowledge regarding the effect of defaults food consumption. This paper is the first step towards examining default portion size effect on consumer perceptions and preferences.

Extant knowledge about portion size and food consumption

Portion size exerts a significant influence over energy intake. Through their meta-analysis of 211 studies Zlatevska et al. (2014) supported that a doubling of portion size leads to an average 35% increase in the amount consumed.

Portion Size can Favor Healthy Consumption

Overall, when a food package includes clear instructions about portion sizes, people are better at guessing how many actual portions the package contained, and higher accuracy was recorded when participants were given guidance (Maksimenko et al., 2024). Szmigin et al., (2017) suggest the adoption of policies that ensure realistic portion sizes and clearer nutritional information. Maksimenko et al., (2024) showed that the biggest error in portions, was in products that consumers had high familiarity, due to implications with emotional connections (Maksimenko et al., 2024). Overall, through the study, it was concluded that having clearly displayed portion size information on food packaging, can be effective for consumers, when guessing how much to eat, but its effectiveness depends on whether they are familiar with the food or not and to what extent (Maksimenko et al.,

2024). However, this does not always lead to the intended result, as many individuals misinterpret the “healthy” aspect of the food labeled and consume more food than required (Maksimenko et al., 2024).

Healthy foods and maintaining a healthy diet include the consumption of vegetables. In the United States, people don’t eat enough vegetables both because they cannot access them and because they simply don’t like them (Vandellen et al., 2019). Through a study, researchers found that when vegetables were served into smaller portions, people were more likely to eat them than if served all together in one plate (Vandellen et al., 2019). This study suggests that in order to encourage healthy eating and increase vegetable consumption, presenting them in smaller portions can help people eat them (Vandellen et al., 2019). It is worth noting that Bui et al. (2017) supported that healthy foods tend to be consumed more when servings are not partitioned. The smaller portion effect was also examined by Van Kleef et al. (2013) who showed that smaller snack portion can lead to equal levels of satisfaction compared to larger ones. Food granularity offers another perspective relevant to portion size. Interestingly, consumers tend to eat more when tempting foods are grouped into more, smaller packages as opposed to fewer, larger packages (Roose et al. 2017).

Newton et al. (2017) found that anthropomorphized health warnings have a significant influence in the portion size preference, especially among those who feel powerless. The study claims that those kinds of people are sensitive to social influences therefore, if there is a warning from their own body, they will be more cautious (Newton et al., 2017). Moreover, they were the ones that were more likely to choose smaller portions when the message was delivered by a human like digestive system, therefore it is suggested that health messages could be more effective if they are somehow connected to personal health and particularly for those who feel less powerful and encourage healthier eating habits (Newton et al., 2017). Anthropomorphic messages though can also take another form that can also affect the perception of food, but also the self-image.

Framing has also concentrated some research attention. Cornil et al. (2014) suggest that framing foods as vices leads to a more accurate portion size estimation among health-conscious consumers. On the other hand, words on the food labels such as “thin cookie” aim to become more appealing to the consumer, with many choosing it because they believe that its less as a portion (Kee et al., 2023). The study overall indicates that obese/overweight people were more likely to order from the menu something with the label slim/regular (Kee et al., 2023). While also the words slim/thin are commonly used in marketing practices, words that indicate a less attractive body mass type could also be effective in lowering calorie consumption, especially in extreme cases (Kee et al., 2023).

Practices that Favor the Super-Size Trend

Zlatevska et al. (2014) showed that supersizing does increase consumption, but from a marketer point of view, it does boost sales (Zlatevska et al., 2014). Similarly, Szmigin et al., (2017) criticized marketing practices for confusing consumers regarding the healthiness of food choices and how it affects their food consumption. The modern food environment creates confusion regarding the portion sizes that ultimately contribute to overconsumption that leads to obesity and other diseases (Szmigin et al., 2017). The study argues that marketing practices contribute to consumer confusion regarding portions and nutritional content (Szmigin et al., 2017). Obesity is not only an individual responsibility, but a collective one, since marketing shapes consumption behavior (Szmigin et al., 2017).

Interestingly, Petit et al (2017) found that people who imagined eating large portions (i.e. simulated eating), felt less hungry afterwards and ended up choosing smaller amounts of food. Thus, simulated eating reduced although did not eliminate portion size effect (Petit et al. 2017). This finding has important resulting implication especially in cases of “king-size” or “super-sized” default portion.

Concluding Remarks and the Role of Defaults

While recently, marketers have been using “supersizing” as a marketing tool, to encourage and attract customer purchase intention, a lot of concern has been expressed due to the belief that larger portion sizes encourage unhealthy portion consumption, which can lead to several health problems

(Zlatevska et al., 2014). Is the Super-Size the default portion today? Can a smaller default portion engage less food intake? Which are the conditions under which default practices in portion size can engage healthier food consumption?

Defaults is a ubiquitous and powerful nudging tool that has lately received research scrutiny. Default refers to the alternative the consumer will receive unless he/she explicitly requests otherwise. The effectiveness of defaults in engaging healthier food consumer options and health-related decisions has lately received increased research scrutiny (Kuhn et al. 2020; Hansen et al. 2021). Setting the healthier option as the default and making it more convenient and accessible, engages higher compliance with healthier food options (Downs et al. 2009; Reinholdsson et al. 2023). More precisely an optimal default leads to healthier options that also seem to stick (Radnitz et al. 2018; Dalrymple et al. 2020; Radnitz et al. 2023). Ferrante et al. (2022) provided a different value of optimal defaults by supporting that they do not result in an increase in healthier options but to a decrease in unhealthy ones.

Although there is limited research regarding the superiority of specific default policies, the opt-out seems to engage higher consumer compliance accompanied though with lower levels of freedom of choice and higher levels of negative feelings (Van Herpen et al., 2021). Regarding consumer demographics, Radnitz et al. (2018) did not find a significant difference on the effect of default on consumer food choices between males and females. Still, Hansen et al (2021) showed that males had a tendency to deviate from the default, when the default was a vegetarian option but not when the default was a non-vegetarian.

This is a first glance towards the examination of the intersection between default options and portion size. Following this literature review approach, the authors will empirically measure the effectiveness of default portion size in engaging healthier food consumption.

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Rural food producers' support for local versus regional branding efforts: A focus on place identity effects in Romania

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Abstract

The importance of local brands is widely accepted by industry practice and well researched by academics. While there are no exact definitions of the meaning of local products or brands, consensus revolves around the existence of geographical and social proximity, whether congruent with political and administrative borders or not. Since retailers have shown interest in fulfilling the demand of consumers who desire a greater number of local products, recent studies have focused on identifying consumer motivation for such behavior. These motives range from personal functional motives such as better product quality (e.g., fresh organic foods) to more public altruistic benefits such as supporting the local economy and emotional/symbolic motives such as regional/national pride. Further, a specific stream of research focuses on consumers' local-global identity and states that consumers generally prefer brands that are congruent with their identities. While there is an increasing trend for consumers' identification as global citizens there is also an opposite trend of strengthened awareness of local citizenship identity. Research has shown a strong association of consumer identities with preference for local vs. more global brands. However, the main effects can be confounded by contingency factors. For example, a recent publication in the *Journal of Marketing Research* shows that while under states of certainty, consumers with a relatively stronger global identity prefer global brands, under states of uncertainty, consumers with a relatively stronger global identity prefer local brands, and vice-versa. Therefore, much is still left to explore in terms of conditions and contingencies.

Even less research is focused on the businesses producing the products and their owners/managers' attitudes and behavioral intentions for collaborating and supporting the development of such local brands as opposed to broader regional or even national brands. A brand represents a promise or guarantee of quality for place-provenance products such as foods sourced and produced in a certain geographical area. Therefore, producers of foods across a variety of categories within a certain region need to collaborate and come to agreements in terms of provenance associations in order to build a coherent brand that would cover a portfolio of local products. Producers are likely to differ in the extent to which they identify with the local geography, their perceptions of what makes the region distinctive and the goals of promoting the association's products versus their individual business products. In the creation of place brands there are multiple stakeholders with competing interests, including private businesses and local community public administrations, regional governments and non-profit organizations, all with their own agendas that affect their willingness to collaborate. These complexities cannot all be studied at once so this paper will carve a specific area of inquiry and attempt to contribute to the understanding of how business owners/managers' sense of place identity defined at multiple levels, from local to regional to national, impacts their attitudes and behavioral intentions regarding the development of local versus regional place brands. The tradeoffs between developing specific local brands at the village/city level versus developing broader regional brands which require a larger collaborative effort that cuts across multiple communities and geographies has not received adequate attention.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored in place branding, country-of-origin or "made-in" branding and social identity theory. Place branding represents a strategic holistic effort to project a distinctive "overall identity" for a geographical entity that could be as narrowly defined as a local

community, a village or city, or as broadly defined as a nation, with a regional level somewhere in between. Place branding leverages multifaceted characteristics of the place such as history, culture, cuisine, geographical landscape, peoples' lifestyle, etc. The strategic goal of place branding is to formulate and maintain the reputation of the place and build an image that would be promoted broadly to stimulate tourism, business investments, and the overall economic development of the place that would benefit all its inhabitants. For successful place branding it is important to identify key characteristics that make the place distinctive, that are perceived as authentic and that are memorable, not unlike business branding principles. However, unlike business branding, which is usually controlled by a single organization, place branding requires the cooperation of many agents who need to co-create this brand for the benefit of all players. This cooperative effort is often impeded by competitiveness and rivalries among the local players. Therefore, the communities and businesses that comprise a certain place need to embrace a higher goal of "place making" that overcomes all these internal tensions.

Concerning "made-in" branding, there is a vast literature on country-of-origin and the multitude of factors that influence local versus global brand buying behavior. However, there is less academic research that addresses the unique characteristics of "Made-in-Place" branding, where consumers are not just supporting a local brand by choosing it over a global brand, but are buying into and supporting the community values, norms and traditions. This direction of inquiry ties into the social identity theory which harks back to the in-group/out-group research. The literature on professional associations indicates that individuals and organizations may be motivated to join associations because they identify with the values of the association, perceive that they gain credibility and an enhanced image from it, and are therefore motivated to invest resources and to commit to building together that common identity. This is very similar to the phenomenon of businesses located in geographical proximity coming together and collaborating in the development of place brands.

The theoretical model that guided the study reported in this paper comprises the factors that drive food producers' attitudes and behavioral intentions regarding the development of a hypothetical Local or a Regional place brand that would cover their product categories. A local brand would be defined at the level of the specific village/town in which their business is located. The regional brand would cover a larger area that comprises many communities which share a certain history, culture and broader geography, but is smaller than a province or a nation. The antecedents are grouped in three categories: Place Attachment includes the business owner's place identity, which is measured at local (village/town), region, county, province and national level, and their perception of the local or the region's place distinctiveness. Business Environment encompasses the perceived level of uncertainty or risk in which they operate their business and their relationship with the place administration. Business Characteristics include the business' resources (financial, human), business size and current performance, and level of sophistication (range of product lines, promotional and distribution channels used, etc.) A set of hypotheses predict the valence of these factors' effects on the Local and Regional brand outcomes.

Methodology and Sample Profile

The study presented in this paper was conducted with the collaboration of the organization entitled "GAL Marginimea Sibiului" in Romania. GAL is the acronym for a Local Action Group which represents the interests of producers in a specific rural area, in this case "Sibiu Borderlands", a geographical zone in Transylvania bordered by the Carpathians. There are approximately 80 GALs in Romania, all part of a national program of providing funding for rural development. The GALs are responsible for selecting and funding programs based on the competence of producers, fit with the unique capabilities of the respective areas and the need for business diversification in areas of too much concentration in one industry. The GAL this study focuses on is well known for traditional husbandry activities, specifically sheep and sheep milk products, which were conducted uninterrupted over millennia.

The sample consists of 149 small and medium sized business owners located in 12 different town/village communities within the boundaries of the identified GAL. Due to the interest in researching the effects of local identities questionnaire design was customized to match the specific

town/village where data collection was conducted. Printed questionnaires were distributed and collected in person by the researchers with the help of the local administration at the request of the GAL representative. Of the total sample, 76.5% responses showed a perfect match between the place of data collection and the producer's primary location for business activity. Producers were 90% in sole ownership, evenly distributed between small, medium and relatively large, based on reported annual revenue. The owners/managers who responded were relatively young (40% under 45), educated (35% college degree) and 46% female. The business activity profile indicates that 70% of the businesses captured in the sample are food producers, primarily milk and cheese products (46%) followed by fresh meat and meat products such as sausages (25%). The rest (30%) is represented by businesses that have a predominant hospitality service activity (90% bed and breakfasts) which have a small food production operation on the side (such as bread and patisserie and fruit and vegetable preserves).

The food products are distributed mostly directly from point of business to consumers (72%) followed by produce markets (27%) and local stores and B&Bs (22%). Only 14% of the sampled businesses used distributors to reach their markets. In terms of marketing communications, 85% of the samples businesses use direct personal connections (word-of-mouth), 42% use social media, and 28% promote their products at fairs and festivals. Only 18% use their own website. This shows that in general, the rural food producers are small, traditional, unsophisticated businesses that would benefit from collaboration in developing local brands to help promote their products in larger markets farther afield.

Results and implications

Overall sample, paired-sample t-tests indicated no difference in brand attitudes and buying intentions between a hypothetical Local and Regional brand but a significant higher intention to support the development of a Regional brand than a Local brand ($p < .05$). In order to capture the concept of Place Identity the variables measuring the extent to which respondents identified as members of the village/region/county/province/country were factor analyzed to result in three dimensions: a local, regional and a broad dimension of identity. These dimensions were used in cluster analysis to break down the sample into three identity profiles: "fiercely local" ($N=22$), "non-local" ($N=26$) and "all-inclusive" ($N=67$). ANOVA group comparison indicated that that the "fiercely local" respondents had significantly higher attitudes and intent toward supporting the development of a Local brand while the non-locals had a significantly higher intent for the regional brand. Interestingly, the "all inclusive" group had equal attitudes and intent to support a Local or Regional brand.

Hypothesis testing with the regression models indicate the following results for Regional Branding. Perceived environmental uncertainty/risk has a strong negative effect, relationship with the local administration has a strong positive effect, perceived uniqueness/differentiation of the region has a strong positive effect (all $p < .01$). Interestingly the identity cluster variable shows a weak main effect but a strong interactive effect with business size. The strongest supporters of a Regional brand are business owners of either very small or large businesses (but not medium sized) who identify as "non-locals" or medium sized business owners who have "all inclusive" identities. For Local Branding, the strongest effects are the positive impact of perceived uniqueness/differentiation of the local community ($p < .001$) followed by the identity clusters ($p < .05$). Interestingly, the owners with an "all inclusive" identity have a higher support of and intent to buy a Local brand than the "fiercely locals", with "non locals" the lowest scores.

In conclusion, the study indicates that a hypothetical Regional food brand is better supported across all respondents, especially by the "all inclusive" group, so those business owners who identify as much with the local as with the regional and national place definition. Regional brand development is also significantly less risky, as it avoids alienating fiercely local groups, and more economical as it pools resources across participating businesses in the entire region. Across both types of place brands (Local or Regional), branding efforts would be more supported by business owners who have a stronger relationship with the local administration of the community and who perceive their place as more distinctive. Therefore GAL and local community administrations are encouraged to focus their efforts on collaborating in the creation of Regional place brands rather than investing efforts in Local

brand building, that is brands at the level of one village or town. Further, it is suggested that they develop strong positive relationships with the business owners in their area and that they promote the common characteristics and traits that make the entire region different from other regions in the country but that are perceived as shared, common characteristics for the communities that make up the region. This is often easier said than done, given the historical rivalries among communities located fairly close together like in neighboring valleys among mountains. However, the common good that Regional food brands can contribute to all producers should prevail over the small local rivalries when trying to grow and build access to larger national and even international food markets.

Do consumers want specialised breeding goals for organic dairy cows – and how much are they willing to pay for individual breeding traits?

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Abstract

Introduction

Denmark has one of the highest shares of organic dairy production in the world (Willer et al., 2024). To keep that position, it is important to consider ways to develop organic dairy production, including an optimal breeding programme to improve specific traits in future generations of organic milking cows. Today, organic and conventional farmers use the same breeding material (i.e., the same pool of bulls) originating from conventional dairy production. This poses a potential problem because breeding material from the conventional breeding programme may not be optimal for the organic production system. Considering that consumers – particularly consumers of organic products – might have concerns regarding climate impact and animal welfare, we present the following two research questions:

RQ1. Is there an interest among Danish consumers to pursue an independent organic breeding programme?

RQ2. What are consumers willing to pay for various breeding traits in organic dairy production?

Method and material

Material

An online survey was carried out in September 2024 among 1,500 Danish consumers in an online panel hosted by Norstat. Informed consent was collected and handled by Norstat. A pilot study involving 50 respondents was used to adjust question formulations and the choice experiment design. The final sample was representative in terms of gender and covered three age groups and five regions. To address RQ1, the following base description was provided to all respondents:

‘There is currently no independent organic breeding programme, so organic dairy farmers largely use semen from conventional bulls. An independent organic breeding programme is under consideration so that organic dairy farmers can avoid using semen from conventional bulls.’

Respondents were randomly assigned to nine informational groups receiving different information about an organic breeding programme. The design included two different dimensions of information. One dimension, referred to as ‘Technologies’, involved two variations of information about advanced reproduction technologies used in a conventional breeding programme. The other dimension, referred to as ‘Breeding’, highlighted two variations of the potential advantages or disadvantages of using an organic breeding programme. This set-up resulted in a 3x3 information matrix with a total of nine formulations of information, as shown in Table 2 in the results section. Hence, all respondents were provided with base information + a Technology element + a Breeding element. The respondents were then asked the question ‘do you think an independent organic breeding programme should be developed?’ with five response categories (Yes, definitely; Yes, maybe; No, definitely not; Don’t know).

A choice experiment (CE) was used to address RQ2. The respondents were randomly assigned to choice sets concerning two different dairy products: 1 L of organic skimmed milk or 500 g of organic

cheese. Only respondents who stated that they buy organic milk or organic cheese were included in the analysis. The scene was set with the following information:

‘Danish organic dairy farmers can breed to improve specific traits in future generations of organic dairy cows. For the following eight questions, please imagine that you are in the supermarket to buy one litre of organic milk (500 grams of organic cheese). You can choose between organic milk (organic cheese) from different farms with different focuses in their breeding management.’

A short budget reminder and cheap talk script were also included to reduce hypothetical bias (Penn & Hu, 2019). The levels and attributes included in the CE are shown in Table 1 and a choice set example is shown in Figure 1.

Table 1: Description of choice experiment

Attributes	Description of attributes (breeding traits) and possible level
Higher yield	Breeding focuses on cows that can produce more milk Possible levels: Yes / No
Better animal welfare	Breeding focuses on healthier cows that are better suited for outdoor life, displaying natural behaviour and with easier calvings Possible levels: Yes / No
Reduced climate impact	Breeding focuses on improving the cows’ digestion and feed efficiency, thus allowing for a reduction in climate gas emission Possible levels: Yes / No
Healthier milk and meat	Breeding focuses on achieving a healthier composition of fatty acids in milk and beef to benefit consumers Possible levels: Yes / No
Price for 1 L of skimmed milk/ 500 g of cheese	Eight different price levels for organic milk: from EUR 1.7 per litre to EUR 3.1 per litre Eight different price levels for organic cheese: from EUR 7.2 per piece to EUR 13.3 per piece

Figure 1. Choice set example for milk

Which organic skimmed milk do you choose?

	Organic skimmed milk A	Organic skimmed milk B	Neither of these
Breeding focuses on cows with a higher yield	No	Yes	
Breeding focuses on cows with better animal welfare	No	Yes	

Breeding focuses on cows with reduced climate impact	Yes	No	
Breeding focuses on cows with healthier milk and beef	Yes	No	
Price (Euros per litre)	1.7	2.2	

I choose:

Organic skimmed milk A

Organic skimmed milk B

Neither of these

Statistical method

To address RQ1, we used descriptive statistics to identify the proportion of respondents who were in favour of an organic breeding programme. In particular, we identified the distribution of respondents in the nine groups who answered ‘yes, definitely’ or ‘yes, maybe’ to the question about whether an organic breeding programme should be developed.

To address RQ2, random parameters logit models were used to model the respondents’ preferences for the individual breeding traits for organic milk and cheese, respectively. The models included a dummy variable for respondents in favour of an organic breeding programme (versus not being in favour of an organic breeding programme). Four dummy variables controlled for gender (identifying as female versus having another gender identity), education (having a Bachelor’s, Master’s or PhD degree (tertiary education) versus having another type of education), region (living in the Capital Region versus living in another region) and age (under 40 years old versus older). Estimations were carried out using NLOGIT6.

Willingness-to-pay (WTP) for the breeding traits was estimated as the marginal utility of the breeding attribute relative to the absolute value of the price parameter. To enable comparison of WTP estimates for milk and cheese, the WTP is presented as percentage price premiums relative to the standard price of organic milk (EUR 1.9 per litre) or cheese (EUR 8.1 per 500 grams), respectively.

Results

The socio-demographic distribution of the sample was as follows: 53% of the respondents identified as female, 52% had a tertiary education, 34% lived in the Capital Region and 34% were under 40 years old. In relation to RQ1, Table 2 highlights the share of respondents in each of the nine informational groups who were in favour of a specific organic breeding programme.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents answering ‘yes, definitely’ or ‘yes, maybe’ to the question ‘do you think a specific organic breeding programme should be developed?’

Technology Information	Base (only base information)	Technology1 The semen used was from conventional bulls that were conceived using advanced methods, such as hormone treatment and in vitro	Technology2 The semen used was from conventional bulls that were conceived using advanced methods, such as hormone treatment, in vitro fertilisation and
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Breeding Information		fertilisation.	genetic modification.
Base (only base information)	51%	53%	51%
Breeding1 An advantage of a purely organic breeding programme is the possibility to improve specific characteristics of dairy cows that are suitable for organic production.	70%	50%	62%
Breeding2 A disadvantage of a purely organic breeding programme is that it may become more expensive and more difficult to improve certain traits because there are fewer organic bulls and dairy cows from which to choose.	43%	47%	44%

Note: All respondents received the base information formulated in the method section.

Table 2 suggests that without information about the pros or cons (Base), or with only negative information about an independent breeding programme (Breeding2), there seems to be no effect of the technology information. Furthermore, the negative information has little influence on attitudes towards an independent organic breeding goal. However, positive information about an independent organic breeding goal (Breeding1) tended to prompt more favourable responses to the question of an independent organic breeding programme.

Results related to RQ2 are shown in Table 3. We found that improved animal welfare was the most important reason for paying a price premium for both organic milk and organic cheese – and even more so for respondents identifying as female. On average, respondents were willing to pay a price premium of 15% and 9% for healthier milk and cheese, respectively. There was very little interest in paying extra for breeding for higher milk yield, as only respondents under 40 years old were prepared to pay a small price premium, and only for cheese. No significant effects were found for education or region. The WTP for breeding for reduced climate impact was 11% for milk, while only respondents who were positive about an organic breeding programme had a higher WTP than other respondents for reduced climate impact for both products. This group also had a higher WTP for animal welfare for cheese.

Table 3. Willingness to pay compared to the standard¹ price of milk or cheese

Traits	Base WTP all respondents	Additional WTP for specific groups of respondents		
		In favour of organic breeding programme	Female gender identity	Under 40 years

Milk				
Yield	-	-	-	-
Welfare	25%	-	12%	
Climate	11%	9%	-	-
Health	15%	-	-	-
Cheese				
Yield	-	-	-	9%
Welfare	23%	17%	11%	-
Climate	-	11%	-	-
Health	9%	-	-	-

Note: ¹ The standard price of organic milk was EUR 1.9 per litre while the standard price of organic cheese was EUR 8.1 per 500 grams.

Discussion

Information about technology used in conventional breeding programmes only affected attitudes towards an independent organic breeding programme when it was combined with positive information about an independent organic breeding goal. This indicates that the respondents on average were not put off by the technology used in conventional breeding programmes, which may pave the way for using these technologies to increase genetic gain. However, it could also reflect a lack of understanding of the rather technical formulations.

The respondents were, on average, willing to pay the highest price premium for improved animal welfare. This is in line with results from a review by Madududu et al. (2024) as well as a cross-country study by Denver et al. (2023) investigating WTP for four sustainability traits of pig meat (animal welfare, carbon emissions, food safety and protection of rain forests) among consumers in Denmark, Sweden, the UK and China. In particular, Denver and colleagues estimated that 11% of the Danish respondents were willing to pay 20% more for more sustainable pig meat, and that the highest WTP for animal welfare was observed in Western countries, while the highest WTP observed in China was for food safety.

A recent choice experiment study by Richter et al. (2025) investigated Swiss consumers' preferences for attributes related to the production of milk and butter. Richter and colleagues found that the respondents were willing to pay the highest price premium for welfare related to loose-housing of dairy cattle. A positive but lower WTP was found for welfare related to slaughter on farm compared to abattoirs, and for reducing climate impact. Interestingly, they found a negative WTP for a reduction in carbon emissions if this was accompanied by reduced animal welfare. These results highlight that reduced climate impact must not be at the expense of animal welfare and that respondents' WTP for animal welfare depends on the type of welfare. We presented animal welfare as a bundle of attributes including animal health, easier calving and improved suitability to outdoor conditions, but future studies could test other attributes related to improved animal welfare, e.g. longevity.

A potential source of uncertainty regarding interpretation of the WTP is whether consumers stated their WTP for additional improvements in organic dairy production through breeding, as intended, or whether they stated their WTP for improved organic milk compared to conventional milk (which is what they frequently do in supermarkets). The use of hypothetical behaviour is another potential source of uncertainty related to market implications, as other studies have found that WTP identified in a hypothetical setting tends to be overestimated (Haghani et al., 2021). Furthermore, only consumers who at least occasionally consume organic milk or cheese were included, which could also potentially lead to an overestimation of WTP.

In terms of policy relevance, the results suggest that respondents who were in favour of implementing a specific organic breeding programme were prepared to pay a higher price premium for lower carbon emissions. This indicates that an organic breeding programme should place more weight on improving climate efficiency than a conventional breeding programme should, while naturally taking into account the costs involved.

Conclusion

We found that approximately half of the respondents representing buyers of organic food were in favour of a specific organic breeding programme in dairy farming. The breeding trait with the highest WTP was improved animal welfare, while lower WTP was found for reduced carbon emissions and healthier milk and cheese, and there was very little WTP for a higher yield. Interestingly, respondents who were in favour of an organic breeding programme had higher WTP for reduced carbon emissions for both milk and cheese and for improved animal welfare for cheese.

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Non-organic consumers see more barriers to climate-friendlier diets than organic consumers

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Abstract

There is an increasing focus on the climate impact of food consumption [1]. Organic consumers tend to be more concerned about the climate impact of their actions [2] and to have dietary habits that include more vegetables and less meat than other consumers [3]. In order to encourage a behavioural shift towards more climate-friendly eating habits, we address perceived barriers for consumers with different levels of organic consumption from the Danish context.

We used data from a 2022 online survey among 2,000 representatively selected respondents. Questions pertained to organic consumption and the perceived importance of different food attributes and barriers to a more climate-friendly diet. Descriptive statistics and a principal component analysis (PCA) were used to identify barriers for respondents with the highest versus lowest organic consumption.

We found that both groups of respondents considered good intrinsic product attributes (e.g. taste, freshness, etc.) to be the most important attributes of food. Animal welfare and organic production were also important for respondents with high organic consumption, whereas low prices were important for respondents with low organic consumption. Climate impact was one of the least important attributes for both groups. Moreover, three meaningful barriers were identified in the PCA. Firstly, *Attitudinal Barriers* were linked to intrinsic product attributes, implying that respondents opt out of climate-friendly purchases because they do not like the taste of climate-friendly food and do not believe that food consumption has a climate impact. This barrier was mainly found for low organic consumption. Secondly, *Practical Barriers* was related to a lack of knowledge about which food products to eat, where to find them and how to prepare them. This barrier was not related to organic consumption. Thirdly, *Price Barriers* indicated that climate-friendly products are rejected because of perceived higher prices. This barrier was mainly found for low organic consumption.

The perception that climate impact is not important when choosing food constitutes an important barrier in moving towards more climate-friendly diets in addition to the three barriers identified in the PCA. Interestingly, both groups of consumers recognised practical problems related to climate-friendly food, but the consumers with low organic consumption also saw the lack of intrinsic value and higher price of climate-friendly food as barriers. This suggests that different regulatory tools are needed to assist in a shift towards more climate-friendly eating habits.

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Explaining intention to consume cultivated seaweed in Norway. A reasoned goal pursuit approach

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Abstract

Seaweed is a nutrient-rich food source, offering essential minerals, vitamins, trace elements, and dietary fiber, along with bioactive compounds linked to various health benefits. Certain species are prized for their distinct flavor and texture in culinary applications. Additionally, seaweed is highly sustainable, requiring no soil, fresh water, or fertilizers while also capturing and storing atmospheric carbon dioxide. Despite these advantages, seaweed remains an underutilized food source in Europe, though interest from the food industry is growing.

This study examines Norwegian consumers' intentions to consume cultivated seaweed using the Theory of Reasoned Goal Pursuit (TRGP; Ajzen & Kruglanski, 2019) as its theoretical framework. The TRGP integrates elements from the Theory of Planned Behavior and Goal Systems Theory to emphasize the goal-driven nature of human behavior. A two-stage structural equation modeling approach was employed to test the hypotheses. This research is the first empirical study to apply TRGP in the context of food consumption, offering insights into the factors influencing motivation and intention to consume cultivated seaweed in Norway.

The results indicate that while Norwegian consumers generally hold positive attitudes toward incorporating seaweed into their diets, their motivation and intention to consume these products remain low. Specifically, the study finds that active procurement goals positively influence attitudes, while active approval goals positively influence subjective norms.

Further, the findings reveal that attitude and subjective norms significantly and positively influence motivation, which in turn strongly predicts intention. Perceived behavioral control (PBC) plays a crucial role, directly affecting both motivation and intention while also moderating the motivation–intention relationship. Other interaction effects indicate that active procurement goals strengthen the attitude–motivation link, whereas the moderating effect of active approval goals on the subjective norm–motivation relationship was not significant. PBC moderates the motivation–intention link only when the original model constraints are relaxed.

Alternative model specifications that relaxed some constraints yielded improved fit indices, suggesting refinements to the TRGP framework. Model 3, which introduced direct paths from attitude and subjective norm to intention, provided the best fit, explaining 90.6% of the variance in intention and 72.7% in motivation. This model underscores that while motivation remains the strongest determinant of intention, attitude and subjective norms also exert direct influences.

Descriptive findings indicate that Norwegian consumers exhibit low motivation and weak intentions to consume seaweed, despite relatively positive attitudes. Subjective norms are low, and PBC is moderate. These results suggest that while consumers are open to seaweed consumption, various barriers hinder their motivation and intention to integrate it into their diets.

The study highlights the need to address both motivational and control-related barriers to enhance consumer acceptance. Policymakers and the food industry can leverage these findings to develop targeted interventions and marketing strategies that promote seaweed as a sustainable and healthy food source. Future research should explore the TRGP framework across different cultural contexts and emerging food categories to further validate and refine the model.

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Co-evolving livestock futures: Farmers' role in shaping sustainable transitions

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Abstract

Food is entangled in the nexus of food-energy-water and widely accepted as being central for sustainability, as food production, transportation, and consumption all contribute significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and other environmental problems, including dominating land use. The transition toward more sustainable food systems is increasingly pressing, particularly in emerging economies where traditional livestock production remains dominant. The Multi-Level Perspective conceptualizes dynamic patterns of transition and innovation in sociotechnical systems and views transitions as non-linear processes that result from the interplay of developments at three analytical levels: the niche, regime, and landscape. Some authors suggest that “fractures” indicate the small cracks that start to appear in practices at the micro-scale regime, offering the opportunity for moving towards shifts at the meso-scale.

Therefore, this study investigates the attitudes of Brazilian livestock producers toward Alternative Proteins (AP), which could represent a “micro-fracture” in the animal-based protein dominant regime. A structured questionnaire (informed by previous research on sustainability perceptions by different stakeholders and innovation adoption in agri-food systems) was administered to livestock producers in one of the largest agricultural fairs in Brazil, yielding a sample of 401 valid responses. The instrument included 23 items covering key themes such as perceived risks, sustainability comparisons between alternative and conventional proteins (environmental, economic, and social indicators), general attitudes toward AP, perceived external pressures, and basic demographic and farm characteristics. Using hierarchical binary logistic regression, we tested the influence of selected predictors on the likelihood of perceiving AP as more sustainable. Control variables and moderators were included in Model 1, followed by the main predictors in Model 2 and interaction terms in Model 3.

Environmental awareness was the strongest positive predictor, while economic concerns – related to profitability and product quality/healthiness - reduce the support for AP. Social sustainability factors (e.g., food sovereignty) showed no significant influence. Larger herd size and older age significantly increased the likelihood of farmers perceiving AP as more sustainable, likely due to experience and operational capacity.

Farmers who perceive higher risks are more likely to support AP, reflecting openness to innovation despite uncertainties. Indirect pressures (e.g., NGO advocacy, environmental legislation) positively influence attitudes, whereas direct pressures from industry or retailers do not, likely due to resistance within the conventional meat sector.

Interaction effects further revealed that indirect pressures (e.g., NGO advocacy, environmental regulation) combined with economic concerns may suppress positive perceptions of AP, while the positive effect of “standalone” environmental indicators is significantly stronger for younger farmers.

In sum, this study contributes to transitions literature by integrating farmer-level perspectives within MLP. It underscores the importance of engaging farmers as co-creators of sustainable transitions. Moreover, for emerging economies with entrenched animal-protein regimes, supporting ‘fractures’ - such as openness to AP - requires coordinated efforts across stakeholders. Strategies should be tailored to inform farmers within different age groups, address economic uncertainties, and elevate the visibility of social sustainability benefits to accelerate the transition.

Expectation or experience? Exploring the factors influencing willingness to buy insect-based food products in a pre- and post-product tasting study

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Abstract

Introduction

In striving to balance the growing demand for nutritious and protein-rich food with environmental sustainability, food scientists and producers have increasingly focused on developing alternative protein sources, including products containing invisibly processed edible insects (Onwezen et al., 2021; van der Weele et al., 2019). However, due to disgust and food neophobia, the lack of consumer acceptance in Western countries remains a major challenge for the commercialisation of insect-based food (IBF) (Sogari et al., 2023; van Huis & Rumpold, 2023). At the same time, recent studies from different European countries indicate that parts of the population show a general openness towards eating insects (Khalil et al., 2024; Puteri et al., 2024; Valesi et al., 2024), confirming the existence of potential early adopters and indicating growth potential for IBF within Europe's alternative protein market.

To encourage increased purchase and consumption of IBF among potential early adopters and close the gap between general openness and actual buying behavior, tasting activities can be an effective strategy. As highlighted in a literature review by Puteri et al. (2023), several studies confirmed that people with previous taste experience have more positive attitudes towards insect consumption and are more likely to eat IBF again. However, no study has yet investigated the effect of a tasting activity in a real supermarket context, comparing quality expectation without product tasting with quality evaluation after product tasting and how this influence the purchase intention. This represents an important research gap to better understand how consumers' purchase intention is built for unfamiliar food products for which the majority of consumers have no first-hand experience.

The specific objectives of the present study are two folds: First, to determine the factors that influence the willingness of potential early adopters to buy IBF, before and after product testing. These include factors such as motivation to eat new foods, attitude towards insects and product quality expectation/evaluation. Second, to explore how these factors and the willingness to buy (WTB) insect-based product differ between groups of people who had tasted the insect-based product and those who have not (yet) tasted the product.

Material and methods

Study design and measures

The insect-based products used in this study were developed as part of a larger project (Puteri et al., 2024) in collaboration with the Swiss start-up Essento. Two products (insect-based meatballs and insect-based crackers) were selected to compare consumer preferences for different types of IBF that cover different meal situations, namely meat alternative and savoury snack products.

The study employed a between-subject design. Participants, who had tasted one of the products, received a product quality evaluation question about the product they had tasted. Participants, who had tasted both products, were randomly assigned to evaluate one of the two products. Participants, who had not tasted both products prior to the survey, were randomly assigned to only one product quality expectation question.

Based on previous research on quality dimensions in the evaluation of meat products and savoury snacks, the following dimensions were selected for the study: Overall liking, appearance, taste, price-quality ratio (3.49 Euro for meatballs and 2.99 Euro for crackers), naturalness, juiciness (for meatballs) or crunchiness (for crackers), and interestingness (adapted from Saeed & Grunert, 2012). These dimensions were measured using 7-point bipolar scales, for example from ‘not at all natural’ to ‘very natural’. The same quality dimensions were employed for the before-tasting and after-tasting groups. For the before-tasting groups, participants rated the expected quality of the product, while the after-tasting groups evaluated the experienced quality of the product they had tasted.

Other purchase motives included were attitudes towards edible insects and motivation to eat new foods. The motives were measured using a total of seven items. The items were presented in randomised order and were rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘strongly agree’, with higher scores indicating more positive attitudes and greater motivation to eat new foods.

Prior to the survey, the insect-based products were already sold in the supermarkets where the data collection took place. To account for both people who had never purchased the products and those who had previously bought the products, the purchase intention was asked by means of their willingness to buy in the future. Participants rated their likelihood to buy *both* insect-based meatballs and insect-based crackers in the future on a 7-point Likert-scale from ‘very unlikely’ to ‘very likely’.

Data collection and participants

For this study a self-administered computer-assisted survey was conducted in five supermarkets in Germany in October 2024, including tasting activities for both Essento insect-based products, i.e., meatballs and crackers. Participants were recruited randomly on site near the tasting stand, ensuring that they could see the Essento products. Screening questions on general willingness to eat IBF were implemented and quotas were set for age and gender as well as product trial and product type to facilitate comparisons between the different groups (before-tasting meatballs, after-tasting meatballs, before-tasting crackers, and after-tasting crackers).

A total of 564 people completed the survey. During data cleaning, 166 cases were removed due to failure in the attention check question, errors in the captured data or age below 18 years. The final sample consisted of 398 people (see Table 1 for the characteristics of the sample in each group).

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample in each group ($N = 398$).

	Insect-based meatballs		Insect-based crackers	
	Before-tasting ($n = 85$)	After-tasting ($n = 101$)	Before-tasting ($n = 78$)	After-tasting ($n = 134$)
Gender:				
Female	57.6%	55.4%	60.3%	54.5%
Male	42.4%	42.6%	34.6%	43.3%
Diverse	0.0%	2.0%	0.0%	2.2%
Age groups:				
18-29 years	49.4%	28.7%	43.6%	39.6%
30-39 years	15.3%	18.8%	15.4%	15.7%
40-49 years	10.6%	18.8%	15.4%	17.9%
50-59 years	10.6%	14.9%	7.7%	8.2%
60-69 years	11.8%	13.9%	14.1%	11.2%
Above 70 years	2.4%	5.0%	3.8%	7.5%
Prior experience of eating insects and/or insect-based food:				
No	69.4%	64.4%	71.8%	70.1%
Yes	30.6%	35.6%	28.2%	29.9%

Data analysis

To investigate the underlying factor structure and identify the number of latent factors, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA; principal component factoring, promax rotation) was conducted for the items related to attitudes towards edible insects and motivation to eat new foods. Barlett's test of sphericity was significant ($p < 0.001$) and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin criterion value was higher than 0.8 (KMO = 0.801), indicating no problem with multicollinearity and good sampling adequacy for factor analysis.

To determine the number of factors retained, a Visual Scree test and Eigenvalues were used. Only items with rotated factor loadings of at least 0.50 were considered meaningful for interpretation. Of the seven items, two factors were extracted, representing attitudes towards edible insects and motivation to eat new foods. See Table 2 for descriptive statistics and factor loadings of the items.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics and factor loadings of the items of the questionnaire based on exploratory factor analysis for 398 participants.

Items	Descriptive statistics Mean \pm SD	Factors	
		1 Attitude	2 Motivation to eat new food
MENF1	I enjoy trying foods that I have never eaten before.	5.85 \pm 1.38	0.81
MENF2	I am interested in trying familiar foods that have been prepared with new ingredients.	5.69 \pm 1.34	0.77
MENF3	I get sort of excited when I know I am going to eat some new types of food.	5.33 \pm 1.44	0.83
ATT1	When prepared properly, insects can taste good as food.	5.76 \pm 1.40	0.56
ATT2	The use of insects should definitely be promoted in food production in Germany.	5.11 \pm 1.62	0.59
ATT3R	I do not need insects as a protein source since there are already plenty of other protein sources on the market. (reversed)	3.66 \pm 1.72	0.88 (removed)
ATT4	I think more people in Germany should consume insects.	4.46 \pm 1.65	0.59

Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients were calculated to assess the internal consistency of each extracted factor from EFA. The results showed an acceptable internal consistency for motivation to eat new foods ($\alpha = 0.79$) and attitudes towards edible insects ($\alpha = 0.77$) after removing the reversed item ATT3R (see Table 2).

Internal consistency tests were also conducted for the product quality dimensions. The tests were carried out separately for each product and for each before- and after-tasting group. The Cronbach's alpha reliabilities of the four groups were between $\alpha = 0.75$ and $\alpha = 0.85$, indicating acceptable internal consistency. For further analyses, the expected product quality dimensions and experienced product quality dimensions were averaged to obtain mean results, resulting in product quality expectation and product quality evaluation, respectively.

Unpaired sample t-tests were employed to test the influence of product tasting on WTB insect-based meatballs or crackers, attitudes towards edible insects, motivation to eat new foods, and product quality expectation/evaluation of insect-based meatballs or crackers. The analyses were performed separately for each product (before-tasting meatballs vs. after-tasting meatballs; before-tasting crackers vs. after-tasting crackers).

The mediating role of attitude and product quality expectation/evaluation on WTB insect-based products was assessed by means of parallel mediation analysis using PROCESS v4.3 macro Model 4 in SPSS as recommended by Hayes (2018). The analysis was conducted separately for each product and for each before- and after-tasting group. The four analyses were performed using WTB insect-

based meatballs/crackers as the dependent variable, motivation to eat new foods as the predictor, attitudes towards edible insects as the first mediator, and product quality expectation (for before-tasting groups) /product quality evaluation (for after-tasting groups) for meatballs/crackers as the second mediator. These variables were analysed in z-standardised format and results are based on 10,000 bootstrap samples.

Results

The results of the unpaired t-test analyses are shown in Table 3. Overall, the same pattern of results can be found for both products with significant differences between the before-tasting and after-tasting groups. Participants who had tasted either the insect-based meatballs or crackers were observed to have a higher WTB the product, a more positive attitude towards edible insects, a higher motivation to eat new foods and a better product quality perception compared to those who had not (yet) tasted the products.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics and unpaired sample t-test

	Insect-based meatballs			Insect-based crackers		
	Before-tasting (n = 85)	After-tasting (n=101)	<i>p</i> -value	Before-tasting (n = 78)	After-tasting (n=134)	<i>p</i> -value
WTB insect-based meatballs	3.45 ± 1.70	4.27 ± 1.84	0.0020	-	-	-
WTB insect-based crackers	-	-	-	3.49 ± 1.77	4.60 ± 1.45	< 0.001
Attitude towards edible insects	4.49 ± 1.64	5.089 ± 1.29	0.0063	4.31 ± 1.57	5.019 ± 1.34	0.0006
Motivation to eat new foods	5.51 ± 1.13	5.94 ± 0.91	0.0046	5.29 ± 1.20	5.76 ± 1.044	0.0030
Product quality expectation / evaluation	4.68 ± 1.11	5.37 ± 0.95	< 0.001	4.75 ± 0.98	5.70 ± 0.81	< 0.001

Figure 1 presents the results of the mediation analyses. Again, there are considerable similarities between the two products and between before-tasting and after-tasting groups. First, for none of the four groups a significant direct relationship between motivation to eat new foods and WTB insect-based products was found. But the statistical tests show significant indirect effects via product quality expectation (only for crackers: $a'b' = 0.14$, 95% CI [0.028, 0.29]) and product quality evaluation (for meatballs: $a'b' = 0.29$, 95% CI [0.12, 0.50]; for crackers: $a'b' = 0.077$, 95% CI [0.013, 0.15]) on the relationship between motivation to eat new food and WTB insect-based products. Such indirect effect via attitude towards edible insects is found only in the cracker after-tasting group ($ab = 0.11$, 95% CI [0.039, 0.21]).

Further, for both products in the before-tasting and after-tasting conditions, participants with a higher motivation to eat new foods were found to have more positive attitudes towards edible insects and better product quality expectation/evaluation. For crackers, this better product quality expectation and product quality evaluation was in turn associated with an increase in their WTB insect-based crackers. The meatballs show similar results, although the effect of product quality expectation on WTB insect-based meatballs is only significant at the 10% level. The most obvious difference between the results concerns the relationship between attitudes and WTB. For meatballs, no significant effect was found either before- or after-tasting. Whereas for crackers, a more positive attitude towards edible insects was associated with an increased WTB insect-based crackers, albeit again in the before-tasting group only at the 10% significant level.

Figure 1: Parallel mediation analyses for a) before-tasting insect-based meatballs, b) after-tasting insect-based meatballs, c) before-tasting insect-based crackers, and d) after-tasting insect-based crackers.

Discussion and Conclusions

The results confirm the great relevance of tasting activities for increasing the acceptance and marketing of IBF. Both the perception of product quality and the WTB increased significantly after tasting. At the same time, neither the motivation to eat new foods nor attitudes towards edible insects (in the case of meatballs) were able to encourage early adapters to buy insect-based products. Only the concrete quality experience or the quality expectation derived from the product packaging was constantly able to achieve this. For producers of IBF, this implies that besides a convincing product quality, an appealing product packaging is equally essential.

In terms of product types, crackers received a better quality rating and a higher willingness to buy than meatballs. This confirms the results from a previous online study (Puteri et al., 2024) and can be considered as another indication that the snack segment with ready-to-eat products has greater market potential in Germany than the meat alternatives segment.

Data collection in connection with product tasting in the supermarket context faces some practical challenges, e.g. defining the number of participants to be reached in advance. Possibly clearer results and further statistical analysis such as SEM would have been possible with a larger sample size. Nevertheless, the supermarket offers great potential for consumer studies, especially for novel products such as IBF, as they take place in the normal shopping setting, thus reducing the risk of hypothetical bias.

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Navigating the protein transition: Insights from citizen innovation living labs in Norway

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Abstract

The transition to sustainable protein sources is a critical component of food system transformation in Europe. The EU-funded project LIKE-A-PRO (Grant Agreement No. 101083961) has established citizen innovation living labs (Hossain et al., 2019; Xhelili, 2024) across 11 countries to investigate consumer perceptions, preferences, and behavioral responses to alternative proteins. These real-world research environments also facilitate consumer engagement in co-creating governance mechanisms that help food decision-makers promote and adopt alternative protein products, providing empirical insights into barriers and drivers of dietary shifts.

Using the Consumer Choice Framework (Xhelili & Nicolau, 2021), the project explores four key dimensions influencing dietary decisions:

Choice Editing – Reducing access to less sustainable and unhealthy food options.

Choice Expansion – Increasing the availability, accessibility, and promotion of sustainable and healthy alternatives.

Choice Environment – Designing food environments that guide consumers toward alternative proteins.

Beyond Choice – Examining macro-influencers such as education, social norms, and communication strategies that impact consumer choices.

This study focuses on findings from Norway's LIKE-A-PRO citizen innovation living labs, particularly on choice editing. While additional insights were collected for the other dimensions, they are not addressed in this study.

Findings and implications

The results reveal varying consumer reactions to choice editing strategies. While some recognize that reducing unsustainable options can encourage healthier, more environmentally friendly diets, concerns about autonomy, product availability, and substitution effects persist. Three key themes emerge:

Acceptance & Positive Reinforcement – Consumers were more receptive to change when suitable, affordable, and tasty alternatives to conventional proteins were available. Social influence, targeted marketing, and media campaigns proved effective in shifting preferences.

Resistance & Consumer Autonomy – Many respondents expressed concerns over choice editing, fearing loss of autonomy, dissatisfaction with substitutes, and potential economic burdens.

Policy & Market Implications – A sustainable food transition requires balancing regulatory interventions with market-driven approaches. Consumers preferred gradual transitions, price incentives, and educational campaigns over abrupt measures such as product removal or significant price hikes on conventional proteins.

Conclusion

Findings from Norway's citizen innovation living labs highlight the complexity of protein transition strategies. While interventions like subsidies, awareness campaigns, and improved product quality can facilitate change, restrictive, non-gradual measures risk significant resistance. A consumer-centered, stepwise approach prioritizing affordability, choice, and familiarity is essential for a just and inclusive protein transition. These insights contribute to broader discussions on effective policy design, behavioral interventions, and sustainable food system transformations across Europe.

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Upgrading domestic and downgrading imported food products regarding their perceived environmental impact

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Abstract

Consumers often perceive locally produced food as more environmentally friendly, safer, and of superior quality compared to imported alternatives (Feldmann & Hamm, 2015; Thøgersen, 2023). Marketing strategies and political campaigns reinforce this belief, often associating domestic products with sustainability and regional identity (EDEKA, 2024; Kögl & Tietze, 2010).

However, empirical research challenges this assumption, demonstrating that imported food can sometimes have a lower environmental footprint due to economies of scale, involving efficient production processes and optimized logistics (Avetisyan et al., 2014; Brodt et al., 2013; Edwards-Jones, 2010). As Thøgersen (2023) points out, consumers in high income countries tend to prefer domestic products, partly due to environmental concerns. Lazzarini et al. (2017) found that Swiss consumers primarily rely on a 'our country is best' heuristic to assess the environmental impact of food products. While this behavior can sometimes lead to accurate sustainability assessments, it can also lead to systematic bias. Addressing these misperceptions is crucial to promoting more sustainable food choices among consumers.

Although country-of-origin (COO) information is usually present on food packaging, prior research suggests that many consumers do not actively consider it when making purchasing decisions (Pedersen et al. 2018). This raises an important question: How do consumers evaluate the environmental impact of food products when no COO information is provided? Do they assume an unknown origin to be foreign and less sustainable, or domestic and more sustainable? Understanding whether the absence of a COO label mitigates or reinforces heuristic-driven biases provides valuable insights into consumer decision-making and the role of COO labeling in sustainability communication.

While previous studies have examined COO effects on consumer preferences, there is a research gap regarding how these effects differ between plant- and animal-based products, particularly in comparison to products without an explicit COO declaration. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing more effective labeling strategies and promoting sustainable food choices.

This study investigates the extent to which COO influences consumer perceptions of the environmental impact of food products. Specifically, we address the following research questions:

RQ1: To what extent do consumers rate domestic food as more environmentally friendly than imported food?

RQ2: Compared to food products without COO declaration, do consumers upgrade domestic and downgrade imported food products in terms of their perceived environmental impact?

With regard to existing literature, we developed the following hypotheses:

H1: Consumers rate domestic food products as more environmentally friendly than imported food products.

H2: Consumers rate food products from the EU as more environmentally friendly than food products from non-EU countries.

H3a: Consumers perceive the environmental impact of domestic food products more positively compared to food products without COO declaration (upgrading).

H3b: Consumers perceive the environmental impact of imported food products more negatively compared to food products without COO declaration(downgrading).

Methodology

Data collection

We conducted an online survey with 998 participants after data cleansing in Germany in September 2024. The questionnaire was approved by the Ethics Commission at the University of Göttingen. A professional online access panel provider recruited respondents that voluntarily participated in the study using quota sampling to reflect the German population (18-80 years) by gender, age, net-income and education (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample description

Variable	Characteristics	Sample (%)	German Population* (%)
Gender	Female	51.1	50.6
	Male	48.7	49.4
	Divers	0.2	
Age-groups	18-29	14.5	15.9
	30-39	16.7	15.8
	40-49	15.1	14.5
	50-59	18.9	18.3
	60+	34.7	35.5
Net Income	- €1249	13.6	13.0
	€1250 - 2499	30.9	30.9
	€2500 - 4999	39.5	37.9
	€5000+	16.0	18.2
Education	No school degree (yet)	1.6	5.2
	Lower school degree	27.2	25.4
	Medium school degree	33.0	31.3

	Higher school degree	38.3	38.1
*German Federal Office of Statistics (2023)			

Study design

Participants were randomly assigned to one of three products: Bell pepper, apples or beef. These products were chosen because they vary in terms of the degree of self-sufficiency in Germany (bell pepper: low (about 4 % in 2022); apples: medium (50.1 % in 2023/24); beef: high (108.9 % in 2023)), in terms of their environmental impact (bell peppers: 0.15 mPt/kg, low; apples: 0.06 mPt/kg, low; beef: 2.27 mPt/kg, high (Agribalyse documentation, 2021)) and in terms of Germany's biggest EU- and non-EU import countries of these products. Spain is the biggest EU- and Morocco the biggest non-EU-import-country of bell peppers; Italy is the biggest EU- and Chile the biggest non-EU-import-country of apples; the Netherlands are the biggest EU- and Argentina the biggest non-EU-import-country of beef. Further, beef was chosen to compare an animal product with non-animal products. Each participant assessed the perceived environmental impact of the respective product versions:

Bell Pepper: without COO declaration, Germany, Spain, Morocco

Apples: without COO declaration, Germany, Italy, Chile

Beef: without COO declaration, Germany, Netherlands, Argentina

We assessed the perceived environmental impact using the following two measurements: First, participants rated the following four items on a 7-level likert scale (1= I totally agree to 7 = I do not agree at all):

[Food product] [without declaration or from COO] ...

is bad for the environment.

is more harmful to the environment than other foods.

does not harm the environment at all.

is particularly problematic for the environment.

Second, participants rated the environmental impact on a constant scale from 0 to 100.

Data analysis

We recoded the 7-point likert scale to a 100-point scale. We calculated the perceived environmental impact for each product version as a mean of the five items. Using ANOVA with repeated measures and Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons, we compared the perceived environmental impact of the different product versions to assess the extent of an upgrading effect of domestic products and of a downgrading effect of imported products.

Results

According to ANOVA with repeated measures, the COO influences the environmental impact perception of all three products. For bell peppers (n=309), the violation of sphericity (Mauchly's $W(5) = .519, p < .001$) led to the use of Greenhouse-Geisser correction, resulting in a significant effect of COO ($F(2.09, 642.72) = 220.68, p < .001, \eta^2 = .417, f = 0.85$). Similarly, for apples (n=348) sphericity was violated ($W(5) = .484, p < .001$) and Greenhouse-Geisser correction revealed a strong effect ($F(1.99, 687.45) = 468.91, p < .001, \eta^2 = .575, f = 1.16$). For

beef (n=341), sphericity was also violated ($W(5) = .705, p < .001$), and Huynh-Feldt correction yielded a smaller but still a strong effect ($F(2.43, 826.36) = 62.95, p < .001, \eta^2 = .156, f = 0.43$). In all cases, effect sizes indicate a substantial impact of COO on environmental impact perception.

Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons confirm further that German consumers generally perceive domestic products as more environmentally friendly than imported alternatives (H1 confirmed). This effect was the strongest with apples from Germany compared to Chile and the smallest with beef from Germany compared to the Netherlands (Figure 1, Table 2).

Results further confirm that consumers rate food from EU countries as more environmentally friendly than food from non-EU countries at a statistical significance level of $p < 0.001$ (H2 confirmed). This effect is the biggest between apples from Italy and Chile and the smallest between beef from the Netherlands and Argentina.

Figure 1: Boxplots showing the upgrading and downgrading effects of the perceived environmental impact of different products from different COOs in comparison on a scale from 0=no environmental impact to 100=large environmental impact.

Compared to the same product without COO declaration, consumers do not rate domestic labeled products as more environmentally friendly (H3a rejected). For bell pepper, a slight opposite effect (downgrading instead of upgrading) was measured, which was not statistically significant. For apples, this opposite effect was larger and statistically significant at a $p < 0.001$ level. Only for beef from Germany vs. beef without declaration of COO, a very small upgrading effect was found, which was not statistically significant. In contrast, consumers rate imported products more negatively than the same product without a COO declaration (H3b confirmed). This effect was the strongest with apples without declaration of COO compared to Chile and the smallest with beef without declaration of COO compared to the Netherlands.

Table 2: Mean values and Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons of perceived environmental impacts

COO	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean difference	Significance after Bonferroni correction
Bell pepper				
Undeclared	30.84	19.63		
Germany	32.71	17.18		
Spain	49.49	19.62		
Morocco	55.12	21.00		
COO comparisons				
Germany vs. Spain			-16.77	<.001
Germany vs. Morocco			-22.41	<.001

Spain vs. Morocco			-5.63	<.001
Undeclared vs. Germany			-1.87	.302
Undeclared vs. Spain			-18.65	<.001
Undeclared vs. Morocco			-24.28	<.001
Apples				
Undeclared	19.95	17.77		
Germany	23.66	16.22		
Italy	45.66	19.44		
Chile	59.51	23.27		
COO comparisons				
Germany vs. Italy			-22.00	<.001
Germany vs. Chile			-35.84	<.001
Italy vs. Chile			-13.84	<.001
Undeclared vs. Germany			-3.71	<.001
Undeclared vs. Italy			-25.71	<.001
Undeclared vs. Chile			-39.55	<.001
Beef				
Undeclared	51.59	25.10		
Germany	50.24	23.06		
the Netherlands	56.6	21.54		

	1			
Argentina	60.89	23.17		
COO comparisons				
Germany vs. the Netherlands			-6.37	<.001
Germany vs. Argentina			-10.66	<.001
The Netherlands vs. Argentina			-4.28	<.001
Undeclared vs. Germany			+1.36	.430
Undeclared vs. the Netherlands			-5.02	<.001
Undeclared vs. Argentina			-9.30	<.001

While we found no significant upgrading effects for domestic COO, downgrading effects for foreign COO differ between product types with largest effect sizes for apples, second largest for bell pepper and smaller effects for beef.

Discussion

Our findings are consistent with Lazzarini et al. (2017), who found that Swiss consumers rated domestic apples and bell peppers as the most environmentally friendly, followed by EU products, with Spanish apples receiving the lowest ratings. Our study extends these findings in two key ways:

First, we included products without COO declaration in our survey to evaluate the impact of COO labeling. This is interesting as consumers often do not consciously pay attention to the origin label (Thøgersen, 2023). We found that domestic products are not upgraded compared to products without COO declaration, while foreign products were always downgraded. The results suggest that considering COO labels do not necessarily improve the perceived environmental friendliness even if the product is labeled domestic. COO information provides no automatic advantage for domestic products. For apples, which were considered very environmentally friendly without COO information, domestic COO labeling even significantly worsened the environmental impact perception. Thus, COO marketing may even have negative effects. This finding contrasts with prior research that suggests consumers using COO labels as a heuristic to buy more domestic and thus environmentally friendly (Thøgersen, 2023). One reason for this may be that consumers do not necessarily consider domestic production to be the most environmentally friendly.

Second, we included beef as an additional product category in our survey. Thus, we could compare environmental perceptions of animal-based and plant-based products. Unlike Yeh and Hirsch (2023), who found a higher willingness to pay for domestic animal-based products than for plant-based ones,

our results suggest COO information influence the perceived environmental impact of beef less compared to apples and bell peppers. This suggests that consumers differentiate between food categories, with the COO effect playing a weaker role for environmental judgements of meat products. Regarding the findings of Yeh and Hirsch (2023), consumers might prioritize domestic animal-based products for other reasons than environmental concerns.

Further, our results support Thøgersen (2023), who argued that in high income countries like Germany, consumers favor products from geographically and culturally closer nations while rating those from distant and unfamiliar countries less favorably. Consistent with Lazzarini et al. (2017) we confirmed this for environmental perception: We found environmental downgrading effects of more distant non-EU imports compared to closer EU imports compared to domestic products. However, we found that these effects of COO vary for different products, especially between animal and non-animal products. Comparing the subjective environmental impact perceptions with objective data (Agribalyse documentation, 2021, Reinhardt et al., 2020), we find that consumers tend to overestimate the COO in this environmental assessment, consistent with Lazzarini et al. (2017).

Our findings have important implications for policymakers and marketers: Consumers often misjudge the environmental impact of food based on its origin. COO information can reinforce these misjudgments. Sustainability campaigns should emphasize factors like product type, best practice production methods, and transportation efficiency instead of domestic production. Policymakers should ensure support for local production does not lead to resource inefficiencies. Further research is needed to explore the reasons behind consumers environmental perception of food products from different COOs. It should also be explored whether COO labels that highlight counterintuitive results improve sustainable consumption or rather lead to distrust.

Conclusion

This study confirms that consumers perceive domestic food products as more environmentally friendly than imported alternatives. However, this perception is primarily driven by a downgrading effect of foreign products rather than upgrading domestic products. The extent of these biases varies across food categories, with a smaller effect for beef than for plant-based products. Overall, the biases far exceed the objective environmental impacts of the assessed products, overestimating the origin effect. Interestingly, domestic COO declaration was found to negatively influence environmental impact perceptions in the case of apples—possibly because consumers recognize that domestic production is not necessarily the most environmentally friendly. Whether such reflections shape consumer judgments is a subject for further research.

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Nutrition labelling and healthier eating: Evidence from a meta-analysis of 31 experimental studies on shaping dietary behavior

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Abstract

Introduction and Background

Imagine standing in a grocery store, faced with countless food choices - some promising health, others masked in ambiguity. In a world where dietary decisions are increasingly complex, could a simple label influence consumer behavior and promote healthier eating?

The effectiveness of food labelling remains a contentious issue in scientific discussions. Various labelling formats exist (e.g., classical nutrition tables, Nutri-Score, MTL, ENL, SENS, mRI), yet differences in structure, threshold values, and country-specific regulations contribute to consumer confusion and distrust (Chimedtseren et al., 2022). Food labelling is intended to provide a transparent representation of a product's nutritional quality, supporting consumers in making informed choices. However, traditional nutrition tables can be difficult to interpret, requiring either prior knowledge or reliance on ingredient lists. Since this cannot be expected from all consumers, regulators - often pressured by citizen initiatives and consumer protection groups - have introduced simplified labelling systems worldwide.

While previous research has largely focused on consumer attitudes toward labelling, there is still a lack of conclusive evidence on its real-world effectiveness. Do these labels genuinely lead to healthier food choices, or are they merely informative without real behavioral impact? Understanding whether labelling results in measurable dietary improvements is crucial for policymakers and public health strategies.

To address this gap, this study conducts a meta-analysis of 31 experimental studies spanning the last two decades, investigating whether nutrition labelling improves consumers' ability to assess nutritional and energy content and whether it influences actual purchasing behavior. By synthesizing empirical data, this research provides a robust evaluation of how food labelling impacts dietary choices and contributes to a broader understanding of its role in public health.

Materials and Methods

A meta-analysis was conducted following PRISMA guidelines and the intervention protocol by Crockett et al. (2011). Studies were sourced from PubMed, limited to English-language publications between 1992 and 2025. Only quantitative studies that measured behavioral outcomes related to nutrition labelling were included. The type of label used (e.g., Nutri-Score, warning symbols, calorie info) was not an exclusion criterion, provided the label was clearly defined and the terms "healthy" and "unhealthy" were operationalized. To investigate the impact on dietary behavior, acquired/purchased macronutrients were included in the analysis.

Three core dimensions of label effectiveness were assessed:

1. Label noticeability (perception),
2. Influence on decision-making (behavioral change),
3. Accuracy in nutritional assessment compared to control conditions.

To ensure robustness, standardize effect sizes (Cohen's *d*), chi-square tests, and normalized contingency coefficients (*c*) were calculated. Sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the influence of large-sample studies.

Results

Caloric Intake

Seventeen out of the 31 identified studies used calorie intake as outcome parameter. Only eight demonstrated significant differences between intervention and control groups. Across all studies, the average reduction was -21.0 kcal ($p < 0.0001$). A chi-square test yielded a value of 11.86 (critical value: 37.65), indicating a lack of statistically significant heterogeneity across studies. Excluding the outlier study by Petimar et al. (2021), the mean difference remained nearly unchanged (-20.36 kcal; $p < 0.000001$).

The effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.17$) suggests a small but statistically significant impact on reducing calories. Subgroup analysis of studies conducted in standardized university settings (Harnack et al. 2008; Roberto et al. 2010; Hoefkens et al. 2011; James et al. 2015; and Grummon et al. 2019) showed a stronger reduction of -56.79 kcal ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the context may play a moderating role.

Macronutrients

In addition to calories, studies also measured effects on key macronutrients:

Fat: -2.0 g ($p < 0.0001$; Cohen's $d = 0.338$, small effect),

Carbohydrates: -1.7 g ($p < 0.0001$; Cohen's $d = 0.30$, small effect),

Sugar: -0.5 g ($p < 0.0001$; Cohen's $d = 0.15$, very small effect),

Protein: -1.8 g ($p < 0.0001$),

Sodium: -80 mg ($p < 0.0001$),

Fiber: $+0.2$ g ($p < 0.0001$).

While reductions in fat and sodium appeared consistent, some effects (e.g., on sugar) were heavily influenced by large-sample studies. After excluding Petimar et al. (2021), several effects lost statistical significance, emphasizing the need for sensitivity analyses in interpreting aggregated results.

Consumer Acceptance of Nutrition Labelling

Using Kollmann's (1998) model of technology acceptance, the study examined whether consumers noticed and used nutrition labels. Although this model originates from technology acceptance research, it is suitable for illustrating acceptance during the introduction of new labeling systems such as the Nutri-Score. Kollmann (1998) distinguishes three phases of acceptance: the attitude phase, the action phase, and the usage phase.

The first phase, attitude, describes behavior prior to the purchase or acquisition of a product or innovation. A major role is played by characteristics that influence potential purchase and usage behavior and are fed by both rational and emotional decisions. One component of this is becoming aware of the innovation and the product and registering it before interest and expectation exert further influence on the entire phase (Kollmann 1998). The outcome parameter equivalent, which was chosen as a representative of the attitude phase, is registering/perceiving a nutritional label. The second phase of acceptance is the action phase, which is characterized by encountering the product or innovation. The product is then tested and tried out, and possibly even purchased. The benefit is therefore the focus of this phase (Kollmann 1998). For this phase, the information on the benefits of nutrient labeling was used as an outcome parameter in the studies. In the use phase, the user will attempt to put the product or innovation into context with the intended use (Kollmann 1998).

Label Perception and Behavioral Change

To examine acceptance, we first examined the extent to which consumers perceived the logo in the first two phases, i.e., whether it was able to attract their attention at all, and then, in the second phase, whether it contributed to changing behavior in favor of the product. For further statistical testing of the data, e.g. for independence of the data, the studies with information on the sample sizes of consumers who both saw a label and stated that they had been influenced by it were combined (e.g. Hammond et al. 2013). To conclude, the variables have a moderately strong relationship, and the results can be well explained by the variables ($X^2 = 2590.27$, $c = 0.28$, strong association).

On average, 58.7% of consumers noticed the nutrition label and 29,3% reported changing their behavior due to it.

Calorie-based labels were statistically more associated with visibility ($\chi^2 = 2140.96$, $c = 0.31$), but interpretative formats such as Traffic Light Labels ($\chi^2 = 310.59$, $c = 0.121$), were more frequently noticed, indicating higher practical effectiveness.

Label Utility

Three studies (Roberto et al., 2012; Hammond et al., 2013; Mora-Plazas et al., 2024) demonstrated the effectiveness of nutrition labelling for evaluating caloric intake. Consumers using Front-of-Pack (FOP) labels were twice as likely ($OR = 2.04$) to correctly identify healthier products compared to control groups. While the difference in correct identification rates was not always statistically significant ($p = 0.0897$), the effect size was meaningful (Cliff's Delta = 0.5). A non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test supported this trend ($p = 0.279$), suggesting moderate interpretative benefit of front-of-pack labeling for consumer understanding.

Studies from Dumanovsky et al. 2011; Auchincloss et al. 2013; Brissette et al. 2013 demonstrated an average calorie reduction of 94.9 kcal per meal among consumers who actively used labelling ($p < 0.0001$). The strongest effect ($r = 0.24$) was observed in Auchincloss et al. (2013), confirming a moderate association ($c = 0.5$) between label use and energy reduction.

No significant differences were observed regarding perceived taste between intervention and control groups. Labels such as the Healthy Choice Logo or Smart Choices Logo did not negatively affect taste ratings or purchasing preferences (Roberto et al., 2012; Steenhuis et al., 2010).

Discussion

This meta-analysis highlights both the promise and limitations of nutrition labelling. While statistically significant reductions in calorie and nutrient intake were observed, the effect sizes were small (Cohen's $d \approx 0.2-0.3$), indicating limited real-world impact. For instance, a reduction of ~21 kcal per meal is unlikely to generate substantial health improvements without complementary interventions.

Setting matters. Studies in fast-food settings (6 out of 17 on calories) likely reflect more time-pressured decisions and different heuristics compared to retail environments like supermarkets, where no studies were conducted. This restricts generalizability and underlines the importance of context-sensitive evaluations. Moreover, most prior studies have focused on consumer perceptions of food labelling rather than actual behavioral changes.

The Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) provides a useful framework for interpreting these findings. Highly motivated or health-conscious consumers may process labelling information via the central route, leading to meaningful dietary adjustments. In contrast, less motivated consumers may rely on heuristic cues (e.g., color-coded systems like the Traffic Light Label), which might explain why Traffic Light Labelling ($c = 0.73$, strong association) had a greater influence than calorie-based labels ($c = 0.45$, moderate association).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This meta-analysis provides strong statistical evidence for the modest impact of nutrition labelling on dietary behavior. While FOP labels improve nutritional understanding and influence decisions, the absolute effects are limited. To maximize their potential, label design must prioritize clarity and

salience (e.g., color-coded systems outperform numeric calorie info). Moreover, implementation context matters. Supermarkets and digital environments offer untapped potential.

Nutrition labels should be viewed not as standalone solutions but as components of integrated public health strategies, including advertising restrictions, taxation policies, and consumer education programs, to maximize its impact as demonstrated by Chile's successful implementation (Reyes et al., 2020). Policymakers must ensure that labelling is not just an isolated intervention, but part of a larger effort to encourage healthier eating behaviors. Future research should differentiate consumer responses by motivation and health literacy to develop targeted communication strategies.

The reconfiguration of consumer meanings and practices of local food consumption through digital platforms

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Abstract

Introduction

Digital food platforms have been increasing in popularity over the past decade and more, reshaping consumption practices (Atkinson, 2013; Strahle and Graff, 2017; de Almeida Oroski, 2020). Within the context of local food consumption, digitalisation has introduced various new modes of food provisioning, such as meal box schemes, consumer-to-consumer food networks, food-sharing apps, and online food marketplaces that seek to enable connections and interactions between food producers and consumers. The Covid-19 pandemic heightened consumer interest in such platforms, at least in the short term. Advocates often present these digitally enabled modes of food provisioning as sustainable alternatives to mainstream food retailing, claiming they increase sales of ecological products, reduce food waste, and promote healthy lifestyles. Thus, digital technologies have been viewed as a means of reconfiguring and shifting consumer consumption patterns towards more sustainable practices (Geels et al., 2015; Borrello et al., 2020).

There is a growing literature on the emergence and functionality of digital food practices and platforms (Schneider et al., 2019; Lupton and Feldman, 2020). However, an understanding of how digital platforms can reconfigure local food consumption practices (Anib et al., 2019; Dale and Christian, 2022) and influence consumers' local food consumption patterns towards greater sustainability remains limited (Fuentes et al., 2021). The focus of research has primarily been on marketing strategies and the technical aspects of platforms rather than their usage by consumers (Martín et al., 2019; Kolesova et al., 2020). Research on food consumption practices has shown that increasing uptake of digital platforms means changing consumer practices, which is challenging because these platforms need to be deeply ingrained in established routines, rhythms, and the overall organisation of daily life (Warde et al., 2007; Yates and Warde, 2017; Southerton, 2020). This implies the need for platforms to be embedded and deeply connected to social interactions and daily life within particular locales (Barney, 2013; Parigi and Gong, 2014; Punathambekar, 2018).

This research uses the Social Practice Theory (SPT) lens to explore how and under what conditions digital food platforms shape existing local food consumption practices. Social practice theory (SPT), also known as practice theory, is based on Reckwitz's (2002b) and Schatzki's (2002) fundamental principles of practice, which has had some prominence in food consumption studies (Warde, 2014, 2016; Heidenstrom and Hebrok, 2022). SPT emphasises the social structuring of routine consumption (Gronow & Warde, 2001), where individual choices in the broader social context shape their routine behaviour. Thus, we propose that SPT can help to understand how local food consumption is reshaped through integrating digital platforms into daily practices. To understand this further, the paper addresses the key research question: How do digital local food platforms change and indeed reconfigure consumer digital local food consumption (DLFC) practices?

Methodology

This study used a qualitative methodology, conducting semi-structured interviews to explore digital local food consumption (DLFC) practices. Consumers from two UK regions—East Midlands

(England) and Northern Ireland—were interviewed to capture differing food shopping habits, preferences, and attitudes toward local produce. Using purposive and snowball sampling, interview participants (IP) were recruited through personal networks and visits to farmers' markets and farm shops. Participants were selected based on prior experience purchasing local food via digital platforms. A total of 37 interviews were completed (20 in East Midlands, 17 in Northern Ireland), conducted face-to-face and via Microsoft Teams. A brief pre-interview survey gathered demographic data. Interviews were transcribed, coded using NVivo 12, and analysed following an adapted version of Miles et al.'s (2014) framework, allowing emergent themes to be developed and examined against existing literature and secondary data.

Findings

The following findings section will firstly explore the Digital Local Food Consumption (DLFC) practices observed within our consumer dataset, structured according to the three elements of SPT identified by Shove et al. (2012) (see Figure 1). These include: the meanings of local Food (cultural significance, emotions, and shared understandings that shape practices); competencies associated with DLFC (abilities, techniques, and understandings required to carry out a practice effectively); and the materials associated with DLFC (tangible and intangible aspects that enable and shape practices). In examining these elements, the section will finish with a discussion of digital local food consumers' types based on their practice patterns.

Figure 1: Elements of Digital Local Food Consumption Practices

Meanings of DLFC

The interviews began by broadly exploring consumer interpretations and constructions of the term 'local food' and how associations with local food were possibly shaped by interaction with digital food platforms. For these consumers, the meaning of local food extends far beyond geographical proximity and embodies a multifaceted value system that includes empathy, provenance, personal identity, ethical values, and sustainability. This reflects a conscious lifestyle choice that involves community support, trust-based relationships, and environmentally responsible practices and an appreciation for the freshness and quality of food:

"Maybe I expect it to be of better quality, it is the fact that you are supporting a local business or a small business, especially." (IP19)

The interviewees' testimonies thus revealed a multi-layered, value-based perspective in their constructions of the meaning of local food. Here, transparency, provenance, and traceability promote familiarity and trust. Personal values and ethical considerations around local food shape perceptions of authenticity:

"My choice is always cage-free animals. So, I would not go specifically to buy eggs that were not cage-free, and I know where I get my eggs; I have that choice. Free-range, it's called, not cage-free. So yeah, that would always be the choice. And then how far it has travelled is my second choice." (IP21)

Similarly, another participant stated:

"That is how they gain my trust." And also, those animal welfare things give you more confidence. They have had a good life, and yeah, so that, to me, is important." (IP17)

Materiality

Our interviewees referred to the influence of convenience, accessibility, and situational factors (such as the COVID-19 pandemic) in stimulating DLFC. Convenience is a particularly important factor driving the decision to purchase food online. For instance, the following interviewee articulates that online food shopping is used when there is a lack of time or opportunity to visit local food stores:

“Convenience mostly. It was just that when you are quite busy with things like work and other kinds of commitments in life, you do not really have a lot of...going out and spending a lot of time actually going to a bunch of different shops, trying to pick up the best food can be quite time-consuming. So, it’s quite handy to have everything delivered to your door.” (IP34)

Other interviewees illustrated how convenience acts both as an initial motivator for using digital platforms and represents a key reason for continuing to use platforms, reducing time pressures, and enhancing accessibility to local food products:

“To gain convenience, and it comes to my doorstep, and then I do not have to worry or think I am about to run out and drive 15 miles to the supermarket or whatever it happens to be.” (IP31)

IP2’s perspective reinforces the overall theme that convenience and associated cost savings are important considerations:

“Well, I think it is convenient. It can be cost-effective in that you are perhaps sparing yourself from buying additional products if you are there, so it’s a little bit more convenient and cost-effective from that point of view. And, of course, it is delivered to your door, so it reduces any hassle of transportation, and it tends to fit into a busy family lifestyle, so from that point of view, I think it is very convenient.” (IP2)

Gaining access to seasonal and diverse produce is a further enabler of DLFC. An interviewee noted that the platform she uses allows her to access unique seasonal, local products, and this encourages her to cook with fresh, in-season ingredients:

“So, a local producer might often have a different range of products you would not necessarily get in a big supermarket. For example, rainbow chard. I think the opportunity to sample and buy those slightly more unusual products, I think there is very much something about being made to cook seasonally, which is a good thing, is another advantage. Flavour. Oh, I will click on those buttons anyway. It will be delivered tomorrow. I do not have to go to the supermarket. I think those are my main benefits.” (IP29)

Beyond these enabling factors, further analysis of the interviewees’ responses highlighted the role of trust in formulating attitudes towards DLFC. Knowledge of the origins of the food is important here, and respondents provided examples of the measures they took to assure themselves of the veracity of the produce, including through their own personal initiatives, such as visiting farms or participating in organised activities, such as farm visits offered by box scheme operators.

“Well, as you say, knowing the people, visiting maybe or being in the local area, where you can see where it is produced and grown. Some of those box schemes, I think it was Helen’s Bay Organic Box Scheme, and they organise farm visits for people.” (IP28)

Competencies

A third component of Social Practice Theory is competencies, which refers to the skills, knowledge, and capabilities individuals require to engage in practice effectively. Clearly, proficiency in DLFC involves several competencies, primarily the technical skills required to use digital platforms, select products, place orders, and manage online payments. A second competency relates to knowledge aspects based on prior experiences, familiarity and the individual’s understanding of the benefits of local food. Again, this concerns trust in the legitimate quality of products available through the digital platform.

The respondents’ testimonies highlight adaptive practices that leverage technology to maintain loyalty to local businesses even when time constraints prevent in-person visits. This level of adaptation illustrates how consumers integrate technological tools into their shopping or consumption routines, ensuring that the convenience of online shopping complements rather than replaces the traditional in-store experience. For instance, Kathryn refers to the critical role of technological skills and adaptability in sustaining local shopping practices within an increasingly digital marketplace:

“...if you have a website that’s friendly and user-friendly and has the same stuff on it as if you went to the shop, then you would use that sometimes. It doesn’t mean that it replaces it, but if I’m busy one week and I want to get the same stuff from my local shop from their website, I would rather do that than go to a supermarket and order online.” (IP20)

Familiarity, rooted in prior knowledge, enhances the sense of convenience, where positive past experiences increase the likelihood of future purchases, particularly when consumers are reminded of products they have previously enjoyed.

“...when you buy online, you often probably sign up for a newsletter or you know, whatever...and I think it is that every so often then you get that reminder and you’re like, oh yeah, we actually haven’t had that for a while, we really loved that, I’d go back and purchase that again. So, I think those reminders and those kinds of things as well. I don’t purchase every time I get a reminder, but every so often.” (IP33)

IP33’s mention of signing up for newsletters and receiving reminders highlights how prior knowledge, gained from previous purchases, shapes her online shopping behaviour. Her familiarity with certain products, reinforced by these reminders, is crucial in her decision-making process. When she receives a notification about a product she has enjoyed, her prior knowledge and positive experiences trigger a sense of recognition and desire, prompting her to consider repurchasing the item. This familiarity reduces the uncertainty and effort associated with decision-making, as she already knows the product meets her expectations. From this quote, familiarity built over time allowed the respondent to transition to online purchases, reinforcing her trust in the butcher despite the digital nature of the transaction.

Changing Practices

An analysis of the interview data provided some further insights into the changing nature of practices and the relationship between traditional and digital forms of local food consumption over time. We were particularly interested in exploring the reasons behind changing behaviours. We identify two forms of changing practices related to engagement in DLFC – ‘lapsed users’ and ‘blended practice’.

We define a lapsed user as someone who previously engaged with digital platforms to purchase local food but has gradually reduced or ceased the practice over time. This shift may result from factors such as lifestyle changes, increased convenience of general online delivery services, or challenges accessing digital local food. For lapsed users, the significance of local food consumption through digital platforms reduces and their competency (knowledge of where and how to find local food digitally) declines, leading to disengagement from DLFC practice. Interview participants referred to the COVID-19 pandemic, which directly influenced their engagement in DLFC. During the pandemic, DLFC was mainly adopted by these consumers for convenience, as it was timely and necessary, as the availability of delivery services aligned with their radically changed lifestyle. However, once the pandemic subsided, the demands of the post-pandemic lifestyle shifted:

“I used it during Covid... stopped it after Covid, so I haven’t used it since. The company that was organising it stopped as well; it stopped because of COVID-19. Everyone was home during COVID-19, and it was convenient and appropriate. But at one stage, the company that was doing it was part of the Irish network, and they delivered for collection in a local shop. That stopped, but he delivered to another town nearby in a shop where we could collect.” (IP5)

Blended practice refers to the integration of traditional and digital local food consumption where consumers uphold the ethos of supporting local producers and value the authenticity of local food. In this hybrid model, *material elements* (such as tools and resources) expand to include digital platforms, while *competency elements* (skills and habits) encompass online ordering and face-to-face interactions:

“I suppose I do know, if I think of my local shops, and those guys pay rent and rates and electric, and all of that is going up. I think that’s where I’ve gone back to cash and going through those stores and those sites. I am kind of in there as well, but as I say, it is not that I don’t use online; I absolutely still do. But yeah, I think I have done a bit of a full circle; I am going around in a bit of a circle. Yeah, at

the minute, I would say my purchase, I am moving more towards the store, and I still absolutely do kind of use online as well.” (IP33)

This flexible approach extends the meaning of supporting local food, demonstrating an adaptation of social practices to suit contemporary needs and support for local food production through both traditional and online purchasing practices. Thus, consumption practice has evolved according to lifestyle changes, and where DLFC shifts as consumers seek to reassess and rekindle their relationship with producers in more traditional channels.

Conclusion

The evolving nature of local food consumption discussed here reflects shifting lifestyle patterns, with users of digital platforms for local food seeking convenience whilst preserving traditional values such as support for the local food economy. Two key forms of practice may be observed: lapsed users (moving back from digital platforms and reconnecting with producers through personal interaction), and blended practices (integrating digital platforms into everyday routines alongside more conventional food consumption practices). Our findings provide some evidence of consumers reinterpreting their relationship with local food as food consumption practices evolve and shift between traditional and digital platforms.

Figure & References are available from the author.

Exploring environmentally sustainable food purchases after shifts in retail pricing strategy

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Abstract

In recent years, pricing strategies have become an increasingly central focus in the retail sector, both as a means of driving sales and as a potential lever for promoting sustainable consumption. The existing literature has examined a wide variety of pricing approaches—including high-low (Hi-Lo), everyday low pricing (EDLP), promotional discounts, and hybrid strategies—demonstrating their effectiveness in shaping consumer behavior across diverse contexts. A growing body of research has also focused specifically on how price reductions can encourage the purchase of sustainable or organic food products, often finding that price interventions outperform educational or informational strategies in terms of immediacy and cost-effectiveness. However, these studies have largely been conducted in controlled settings, with interventions narrowly focused on specific product categories or isolated sustainability-related items.

What remains underexplored is how large-scale, non-targeted price reductions—such as a general lowering of prices across all grocery products in a retail chain—impact the sales performance of specific product lines, particularly those with strong sustainability positioning, such as private-label organic and biological goods. Existing studies tend to assume a direct link between discounted products and their sales performance, leaving a significant gap in understanding the indirect effects that broader pricing strategies may generate across an entire assortment. This is particularly relevant in real-world retail environments, where consumer choices are shaped by multiple interacting factors, including price perception, brand positioning, and category substitution.

Moreover, few studies have applied rigorous causal inference methods, such as difference-in-differences (DiD), in naturalistic retail contexts to assess how general pricing strategies affect sales performance at the product-line level. While DiD designs offer a valuable framework for evaluating causal effects in quasi-experimental settings, their application to pricing interventions in complex, real-life market environments remains limited—especially when it comes to isolating the effects of broad pricing changes on a subset of sustainable products.

This study addresses the gap in literature by analyzing the effects of a general price reduction policy implemented by a major grocery retailer (GDO), focusing on its impact on consumer purchasing behavior for private-label organic products. Using a real-world case and a difference-in-differences approach, the research aims to provide new insights into the indirect effects of systemic pricing changes, enhancing understanding of how pricing strategies can support sustainable consumption.

In particular, the strategy that the retailer applied has as objective to enhance overall price competitiveness by simultaneously lowering base and promotional prices, while reducing the average promotional intensity (i.e., the depth of discounts). This shift aimed to deliver greater value perception across all grocery categories, not through aggressive promotional campaigns, but through a recalibrated and more sustainable approach to everyday pricing. The strategy's implementation varied by store format, reflecting the retailer's differentiated approach across hypermarkets, superstores, supermarkets, and convenience stores.

Hypermarkets expanded their grocery assortment and improved availability on both shelves and promotional platforms, while slightly reducing promotional intensity in favor of more targeted and effective flyer campaigns. Superstores maintained a stable assortment and preserved the balance between shelf and promotional presence, optimizing flyer campaigns for consistency rather than

volume. Supermarkets took a different approach by streamlining their assortments—emphasizing fresh and local products—and significantly scaling back flyer promotions in favor of a service-focused and quality-driven offering. Meanwhile, smaller convenience stores adapted to local demand through smaller package sizes and removed flyer-based promotions altogether, relying instead on simplified assortment and everyday low pricing to meet customer expectations in compact retail environments.

Against this backdrop, the current study evaluates the effectiveness of the pricing intervention with a specific focus on a private-label line of eco-friendly, organic grocery products. These items are produced using certified organic farming methods that exclude genetically modified organisms, synthetic pesticides, and fertilizers, while promoting crop rotation and biodiversity. The product line also includes a sub-range of organic, plant-based foods designed to meet the dietary needs of vegetarians and vegans. All products within this assortment are certified by regulatory bodies authorized by the Italian Ministry of Agriculture, ensuring high standards in sustainability, environmental impact, and health-conscious consumption.

To assess the effect of the pricing changes on this specific sustainable product line, the study employs a Difference-in-Differences (DiD) approach. This econometric method allows for the estimation of causal effects by comparing changes in outcomes over time between a treatment group—Region 1, where the intervention was first introduced—and a control group—Region 0, where the strategy was implemented only after a seven-month lag. The analysis focuses on changes in both sales value and sales volume, disaggregated into shelf and promotional sales, while controlling for heterogeneity across store formats, product categories, and customer demographics. Through this framework, the research aims to provide robust evidence on the extent to which systemic pricing changes influence consumer behavior toward sustainable products in a real-world, retail setting.

In particular, the policy that the retailer applied, was first introduced in August 2023 in one region and then extended nationwide. The strategy's formal announcement in September 2023 marks the start of the treatment period analyzed. By comparing sales between a pre-treatment period (1 September 2022 to 19 March 2023) and the treatment period (1 September 2023 to 19 March 2024), the study isolates the effects of the intervention, controlling for external factors such as macroeconomic trends and market dynamics. The observation window excludes the months after March 2024, when the strategy began in the control region, preserving the integrity of the comparison.

The empirical analysis focuses on a subset of 135 eco-friendly private-label products selected based on the completeness of their sales records across both pre- and post-intervention periods, and across both the treated and control regions. Products with incomplete data were excluded to ensure consistency in comparisons and to maintain the internal validity of the analysis. The final sample includes products distributed across three different store departments and organized into 26 distinct product categories, allowing for a granular understanding of consumer responses across a diverse set of grocery goods.

Sales data were collected at the weekly level, covering the period from the week starting September 5th, 2023 to the week of March 11th, 2024, which defines the treatment period. For comparison, an equivalent pre-treatment period was defined using the corresponding weeks in the previous year, from September 2022 to March 2023. This symmetric structure enables a robust Difference-in-Differences analysis by aligning seasonal patterns and other time-related factors.

In total, the dataset comprises 30,240 observations, with 540 weekly entries generated by tracking the 135 products across the two regions (treated and control) and by segmenting sales between loyalty cardholders and non-cardholders. The inclusion of a binary variable identifying loyalty card users allows the model to control for heterogeneous consumer responses, which may reflect differences in shopping behavior, price sensitivity, or brand loyalty.

The dependent variables considered are both sales value and sales volume, enabling the evaluation of the strategy's effectiveness in both monetary and physical terms. Moreover, sales data are disaggregated into shelf (non-promotional) and promotional transactions, which provides additional

insight into how the revised pricing strategy, including reduced promotional intensity, influenced consumer purchasing behavior.

The dataset integrates information from multiple sources. Sales and product-level data were extracted from the retailer's internal databases, including detailed records of weekly sales transactions, product categorization, and store formats. Additional data were obtained from the retailer's promotional planning systems, including the weekly presence of products in promotional flyers and coupon distribution. To control for broader regional economic conditions, monthly Consumer Price Index (CPI) data for food and non-alcoholic beverages were drawn from the Italian national statistics institute (ISTAT), disaggregated at the regional level.

This rich and structured dataset lays the foundation for a rigorous econometric evaluation of the intervention's impact. In the following section, the specification of the econometric model used to estimate causal effects will be detailed, with a focus on how the Difference-in-Differences approach is implemented in this context, including controls for product fixed effects, time trends, and interactions with store and customer characteristics.

As stated, the primary objective of this study is to evaluate the causal impact of the retailer's revised pricing strategy on the sales performance of its eco-friendly private-label product line. Given the observational nature of the data and the non-randomized rollout of the intervention, a Difference-in-Differences (DiD) econometric approach has been selected as the most appropriate methodological framework. The DiD design enables estimation of the treatment effect by comparing the evolution of outcomes—namely, sales value and sales volume—in the treated region before and after the intervention, relative to a control region that did not receive the treatment within the same timeframe.

The core assumption underpinning the DiD approach is that, in the absence of the intervention, the sales trends in the treated and control groups would have followed parallel trajectories. Therefore, any systematic divergence in these trends post-intervention can be interpreted as the causal effect of the treatment, assuming no contemporaneous shocks uniquely affecting one region. This method offers a robust way to control for unobserved heterogeneity and time-varying confounders, such as regional economic fluctuations, seasonal effects, or broad market dynamics unrelated to the pricing policy.

To implement the DiD model, a rich set of variables were considered. These include:

Dummy variables identifying the treatment and control regions;

A time dummy capturing the post-intervention period;

A fidelity card ownership dummy to account for heterogeneity in consumer responsiveness (initially included in pooled analysis, and later explored in subgroup estimations);

An interaction term between the treatment and post-period dummies ($\text{Treatment} \times \text{Post}$), which captures the differential impact of the intervention on the treated group;

Time-fixed effects at the week and year levels to control for seasonality and macro trends;

Product-specific characteristics such as department, category, subcategory, and marketing segment;

Product positioning across different marketing areas (e.g., fresh, grocery, non-food);

Store-type distribution variables reflecting the number of outlets per format (hypermarkets, superstores, supermarkets, convenience stores, and wellness stores) stocking each reference;

Separate dependent variables for both shelf and promotional sales in terms of value and volume, allowing for detailed decomposition of the pricing strategy's effects.

The key coefficient of interest is that on the $\text{Treatment} \times \text{Post}$ interaction term. A statistically significant estimate would suggest that the new pricing strategy had a measurable and distinct impact on the sales of the eco-friendly product line in the treated region relative to the control.

To further strengthen the model, additional variables are introduced to account for weekly promotional communication efforts. These include data on flyer visibility at the product level, collected weekly, and the presence of discount coupons during specific promotional cycles. These

coupons—offering either €10 off a €30 purchase or €5 off a €15 purchase—were distributed periodically during the study period and varied by target group (fidelity card holders vs. all customers). Their presence is expected to introduce short-term boosts in sales, potentially confounding the treatment effect, and thus must be explicitly controlled for.

Regarding socio-economic controls, regional-level indicators such as unemployment rates or per capita GDP were considered. However, due to the limited temporal granularity of these indicators (available only quarterly) and the relatively short time frame of the analysis (seven months), they were excluded from the final model specification to avoid unnecessary noise.

Finally, to ensure the validity of inference, robust standard errors clustered at the product-region level will be used to account for potential heteroscedasticity and serial correlation in the panel data structure.

This analytical framework is expected to provide a credible estimate of the effect of the retailer's new pricing policy on the demand for sustainable products, disentangling the contribution of price adjustments, promotional intensity, and consumer segmentation. In the next section, the precise econometric specification of the DiD model will be presented, along with estimation strategy and robustness checks.

Building on the outlined methodological framework, the empirical strategy was further enriched by conducting disaggregated analyses at the category level and by customer segment—namely, fidelity card holders (members) and non-members. These additional layers of analysis were designed to explore potential heterogeneous effects of the pricing intervention across different product categories and consumer profiles, offering a more nuanced understanding of the policy's effectiveness.

The analysis at the category level, covering 26 distinct product categories across three marketing departments, allows the identification of whether specific types of products within the eco-friendly private-label line responded differently to the change in pricing strategy. This is particularly relevant given the variation in customer sensitivity to price and promotion intensity across food categories, especially those considered premium or niche, such as organic or plant-based items. Likewise, analyzing sales separately for members and non-members provides insights into the differential behavior of loyal customers, who may be more responsive to long-term pricing strategies and less influenced by short-term promotions.

Despite the comprehensiveness of the intervention and the analytical depth of the approach, preliminary results do not provide evidence of a positive impact of the new pricing strategy on the sales of the eco-friendly product line. Both in terms of sales value and volume, the Difference-in-Differences estimates suggest that, after accounting for promotional communication, coupon activity, and store format heterogeneity, the effect of the pricing intervention appears to be statistically insignificant or even slightly negative in some specifications. This finding is consistent across multiple robustness checks and remains stable when disaggregating the data by category or customer type.

Several potential explanations for these results can be considered. First, the overall price reduction, although strategically designed to increase convenience, may not have been sufficient to trigger significant changes in consumer behavior, especially in a segment like organic and sustainable products, where purchase decisions are often driven by values, habits, and perceived quality rather than price alone. Second, the concurrent reduction in promotional intensity may have offset the positive effects of shelf price reductions, particularly for consumers accustomed to strong promotional incentives. Third, the communication of the new strategy may not have been effective enough to reshape consumer perceptions of price competitiveness, especially given the limited visibility of flyer promotions in smaller formats and supermarkets.

Moreover, external factors such as general inflationary trends, changes in consumer purchasing power, and shifting post-pandemic consumption patterns may have played a role in dampening the responsiveness to the intervention. These dynamics highlight the complexity of driving sales growth in sustainability-oriented product lines through pricing alone, especially in a competitive and saturated grocery retail environment.

In light of these initial findings, the study underscores the importance of complementing pricing strategies with broader levers—such as in-store communication, shopper education, and tailored promotional mechanics—to effectively boost demand for sustainable products. The analysis sheds light also on fixed effects at the product-region level, interaction terms with flyer presence and coupon exposure, and dynamic DiD models to assess lagged treatment effects over time.

These results contribute to the broader literature on sustainable consumption and retail pricing by providing empirical evidence from a real-world intervention in a major Italian grocery chain, and by emphasizing the need for multidimensional strategies to influence consumer behavior in the eco-friendly product segment.

It is a matter of fairness: How partitioned pricing strategies can shift preferences for reusable food packaging

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Abstract

Packaging reuse is a promising strategy to reduce waste and promote sustainable consumption practices. However, in the retail sector, shifting consumer choices towards reusable packaging alternatives can be challenging, particularly when single-use packaging options remain available at a lower cost. In this paper, we propose that separating the total price into distinct costs for packaging and the product—a price framing strategy known as Partitioned Pricing (PP)—can help retailers and producers increase consumers' intention to choose reusable food packaging. Through three online survey experiments (N = 1,101), involving different packaging materials, product categories, and deposit costs, we find that PP enhances intended choice of reusable packaging by improving perceptions of price fairness. Our findings are grounded in Attribution Theory, which posits that itemising price components heightens the salience of the surcharge, allowing consumers to attribute the higher cost to environmental benefits. These insights provide valuable implications for retailers, producers, and policymakers aiming to promote the adoption of reusable packaging schemes.

Taste and text: What online reviews reveal about customer satisfaction in Indian restaurants

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Abstract

Introduction

The global food service market have a significant expansion, with projections indicating an increase from \$2,646.99 billion in 2023 to \$5,423.59 billion by the year 2030, thereby reflecting an annual growth rate of 10.79%, as cited in Fortune Business Insights (2023). This upward trend is evident within the Indian food service sector, which is anticipated to experience a growth rate of 9-10% during the period from 2018 to 2023 (NRAI, 2019). The Indian food market is predicted to increase at an 11.19% compound annual growth rate from 2022 to 2028, increasing its value from \$41.1 billion to \$79.65 billion (Press Trust of India, 2022). The Indian food market is growing faster than the world average due to rising disposable incomes, urbanization, and a growing consumer base, setting it apart from the more developed markets of other countries (Brar et al., 2014). Online reviews serve as an electronic version of word-of-mouth (e-WOM) facilitated by Web 2.0 technologies that have emerged over the past two decades (Gan et al., 2017). Also, there was a significant shift in the service industry brought about by the internet, which revolutionized the restaurant business by enable ordering on fingertips instead of dining. WOM was initially impacted by this shift, and later e-WOM became popular. Online reviews have become key sources for hospitality, tourism, and business research since they provide insights into customers' spontaneous and insightful feedback (Guo et al., 2017), reflecting either happiness or dissatisfaction with their experiences (Banerjee and Chua, 2016). Yelp, TripAdvisor, Google Maps, and Dianping all offer free online reviews (Mathayomchan & Taecharungroj, 2020), these platforms allow users to engage and publish reviews, which help reviewers express their emotions, provide information, describe experiences, and make recommendations (Racherla et al., 2013; Ye et al., 2014).

Customer experience influences a wide range of cognitive and behavioral reactions (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016). The Expectancy-Disconfirmation theory, introduced by Lewin (1938), is the most recognized theory for explaining customer satisfaction. It states that customers evaluate their satisfaction levels by comparing actual experiences or performance to their expectations. This customer satisfaction technique depends on the cognitive process of expectation confirmation (Oliver, 1980; Oliver, 1989). The theory recommends three scenarios for customer evaluations: (1) confirmation, which occurs when actual performance matches expectations; (2) positive disconfirmation, which occurs when actual performance exceeds expectations, resulting in satisfaction; and (3) negative disconfirmation, which occurs when actual performance is worse than expected, resulting in dissatisfaction (Ha and Jang, 2010). Positive experiences, for example, can result in satisfaction and loyalty (Hyun, 2010; Ryu and Han, 2011), a better attitude and brand preference (Hwang and Ok, 2013), intention to purchase (Ashton et al., 2010), and intention to return (Gupta et al., 2007). Alternatively, an inadequate encounter will result in customer dissatisfaction and negative emotional, cognitive, and behavioral responses (Abdelhamied, 2011). However, improving the restaurant experience is a challenging task because it is complicated and multidimensional, incorporating elements other than food (Ponnam and Balaji, 2014; Walter et al., 2010). Despite the complex nature of restaurant features, researchers have broadly defined four major restaurant attributes: cuisine, service, atmosphere, and value (Yrjölä et al., 2019).

The studies mentioned above investigated multiple factors that influence customer experience by conducting mixed method research and traditional techniques, but as per our knowledge none of the

study has explored the sentiments associated with all aspects in the restaurant context. This study will focus on online reviews of restaurants to better understand the underlying patterns. Further, these themes will be used to determine the most important factors that emphasize a positive or negative element of the business. These key factors will be used by restaurant managers to investigate the crucial reasons behind the surge or drop in customer traffic and to develop strategies based on consumer input.

Objectives

While extensive research exists on customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry, a notable gap exists in understanding the nuanced factors that influence customer perception and satisfaction across different dining establishments. Existing literature primarily focuses on general aspects of service quality, food quality, and ambiance (Yrjölä et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2012; Andaleeb & Conway, 2006; Ryu & Jang, 2008; Andersson & Mossberg, 2004; Heung and Gu, 2012; Harrington et al., 2012), but lacks in-depth analysis of specific factors that contribute to customer satisfaction. Previous studies have examined the relationship between customer ratings and overall satisfaction (Lee et al., 2015; Schlosser, 2005; Wang et al., 2018; Adomavicius et al., 2013; Ma et al., 2013; Hu and Li, 2011; Moe and Trusov, 2011), but there is limited research on the content analysis of online review provided by customers. Understanding the qualitative aspects of customer reviews is crucial for gaining deeper insights into their preferences and perceptions.

Given the insights gained from the literature review and the identified gap in existing literature, we formulate two primary research objectives:

1. Identifying key factors influencing customer satisfaction at Indian restaurants.
2. Determining restaurant-related parameters impacting customer satisfaction during food delivery services provided by these restaurants.

Methodology

In order to understand the overall sentiment expressed in reviews, we can use or apply sentiment analysis techniques. These techniques can categorize each review as positive, negative, or neutral. To go beyond basic sentiment and dive into the emotional nuances, we can use sentiment dictionaries specifically designed to identify emotions like joy, love, trust, anger, sadness, and surprise (Li et al., 2022). Additionally, exploring machine learning approaches for sentiment analysis can offer even deeper insights and potentially improve the accuracy of our analysis. Topic modelling is a machine learning technique that has gained significant attention in recent years for its ability to automatically uncover latent structures within large text datasets (Park et al., 2018). It involves the use of algorithms like Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to identify key themes or topics present in a corpus of text. These topics are extracted based on the occurrence of relevant keywords, enabling the recognition of knowledge structures and patterns within research articles (Lee et al., 2022).

In this study we will be collecting online reviews of the restaurants in India from different locations in the country (include all five zones) which includes metros as well as other Tier-I and Tier-II cities. The online food delivery aggregator platforms ensure a diverse range of reviews covering various restaurants and cuisines across the country. We have used python for scrapping the reviews in JSON format and then pre-processing will happen for applying text analytics.

Proposed Results

With the help of sentiment analysis, we can gain valuable insights into the restaurant industry in India. This process involves identifying key parameters that significantly influence overall customer evaluations based on the sentiment expressed in their reviews (Khan et al., 2022). By focusing on aspects that consistently generate positive sentiment, we can gain a deeper understanding of customer preferences and satisfaction levels. This analysis can further reveal areas for improvement and inform targeted recommendations for restaurants seeking to enhance their customer experience. Ultimately, these findings can be compiled into a comprehensive report that details the key parameters impacting sentiment in restaurant reviews, providing valuable insights for businesses in the Indian market.

Practical Implications

This study will focus on online reviews of restaurants to better understand the underlying patterns. Further, these themes will be used to determine the most important factors that emphasize a positive or negative element of the business. These key factors will be used by restaurant managers to investigate the crucial reasons behind the surge or drop in customer traffic and to develop strategies based on consumer input. If we see the other side from customer point of view, it will be very helpful to take purchase decision for having dinner from particular restaurant or not. This study will be providing the key areas which are lacking in terms of service or other aspects mentioned by customer, which acts as feedback mechanism.

Keywords: Online reviews, User-Generated-Content (UGC), Customer Satisfaction, Sentiment Analysis, Text analytics

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The influence of pre-attitudinal beliefs, knowledge, food neophobia, and cultural integration on the purchase and continued consumption of novel food alternatives

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Abstract

As global food systems face increasing sustainability challenges, novel food alternatives (NFAs), such as plant-based meat, cultured meat, and insect-based foods, are gaining attention as potential solutions. However, consumer adoption remains limited due to psychological, cultural, and informational barriers. This study examines how health consciousness, environmental concern, knowledge, food neophobia, and cultural integration influence both the initial purchase and the continued consumption of NFAs.

Beyond the decision to try NFAs, habit formation and sustained consumption play a critical role in their market success. While health consciousness and environmental concern can motivate initial trials, their long-term influence on repeated consumption remains unclear. Knowledge (both objective and subjective) is expected to facilitate informed decision-making, increasing consumer confidence and habitual consumption over time. In contrast, food neophobia may act as a persistent psychological barrier, preventing the transition from trial to regular consumption. Additionally, cultural background and exposure to diverse diets may influence how easily NFAs become part of daily eating habits.

This study employs a survey-based quantitative approach, collecting data from a diverse consumer sample to analyse the key determinants of both adoption and sustained consumption. Findings will contribute to consumer behaviour theory by offering insights into how psychological and informational factors shape not only initial purchase behaviour but also long-term dietary integration.

Furthermore, this research provides practical implications for policymakers and industry stakeholders, offering strategies to encourage long-term consumer engagement with NFAs. By understanding the factors that drive habitual consumption, this study aims to support the development of marketing and policy initiatives that promote sustainable dietary transitions. This research adheres to ethical standards, ensuring informed consent, anonymity, and data protection.

Keywords

Novel Food Alternatives, Health Consciousness, Environmental Concern, Food Neophobia, Knowledge, Consumption Habits, Consumer Behaviour

Utilizing choice architecture and the COM-B model to shape sustainable consumption choices: A study on alternative food proteins

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Abstract

Introduction

With projections estimating a global population of 9–10 billion by 2050 (United Nations, 2019) and mounting pressures from conventional meat production (Godfray et al., 2018), the transition toward alternative protein (AP) sources emerges as a critical pathway to establish more sustainable and healthful food systems. Behavioral shifts such as the replacement of red meat consumption with AP products have the potential to benefit health, environmental, and socioeconomic dimensions of European populations (Assunção et al., 2024). Such evidence supports the development of policies that encourage a shift from conventional to alternative diets. The need for such policies is underlined by the fact that, at the EU level, most policies directly influencing food environments are rated as weak when it comes to addressing diet-induced health problems, leaving plenty of room for improvement (Djojoseparto et al., 2022). The current paper outlines a survey exploring the impact of Choice Architecture-related interventions (i.e. choice editing and choice expansion), incorporating the COM-B framework as its conceptual basis and implemented within a Living Labs approach to data collection, on shifting consumer preferences towards APs. The Living Labs approach bridges the gap between pure lab conditions and real-life implementation, as it involves the cooperation of researchers, consumers, and food sector stakeholders.

Literature Review

Food Policy Interventions and Choice Architecture

A range of policy interventions affecting sustainable food choices emerge from the literature, with various reviews identifying types from more carefully crafted ones - with a focus on individual motivation and deliberate decision making - to more subtle ones - involving tools targeting automatic decision-making processes, such as label and information campaigns and changes in the choice architecture (Abrahamse, 2020; Ran et al., 2024). The role of policy interventions in making diets healthier and more sustainable appears pivotal, yet their scope and effectiveness vary. Interventions involving multiple components of the food system, community-based engagement, and both children and adults consistently appear highly effective in improving healthy eating (Hyseni et al., 2017; Lofton et al., 2023).

Nudging strategies and choice architecture interventions have shown promise in encouraging more sustainable food choices in general (Abrahamse, 2020; Siegrist et al., 2024) and the adoption of alternative proteins more specifically (Lopes, 2022). These interventions can take various forms, including choice editing, which involves both reducing meat options and increasing the availability of alternatives (Abrahamse, 2020), and choice expansion, which has proven effective in school food environments (Durão et al., 2024).

Public canteens, schools, nurseries, and universities present valuable settings for implementing these changes, as they can reach many people and act as role models by aligning offerings and pricing with environmental and planetary health goals (Schleicher & Töller, 2024). It is important to consider that the effectiveness of these strategies can differ based on socioeconomic status, with in-store and online

nudging potentially being more relevant to higher socioeconomic status consumers who shop online more frequently (Vos et al., 2022; Burgaz et al., 2023). Menu repositioning, such as presenting lower carbon-impact options first on food-delivery apps, has also significantly reduced the carbon footprint of meal choices (Lohmann et al., 2024).

While the evidence base for these interventions is growing, further research is needed to understand the role of various mediators and moderators, such as past behavior, cultural values, and prior beliefs, that influence their success (Abrahamse, 2020). Consumer acceptance of alternative proteins is also a key factor, influenced by motives, familiarity, neophobia, disgust, and cultural norms, with inconsistencies in these drivers indicating a need for more research (Siddiqui et al., 2022). Notably, nudging interventions targeting ‘system 1’ thinking (automatic and non-conscious), like the one exhibited in real-life decision-making contexts that a Living Lab approach tries to incorporate, have shown more statistically significant outcomes in promoting sustainable food choices (Blackford, 2021). To further facilitate sustainable consumption, clearer product-based indicators and stronger governmental regulation of unsustainable products may be necessary (Gunn & Mont, 2014; Yamoah et al., 2022).

The COM-B Framework

The COM-B model, developed by Michie et al. (2011), is a framework that explains behavior through three interacting components: *Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation*. Capability is an individual's psychological and physical capacity, such as knowledge and skills. Opportunity includes external factors like the environment that make behavior possible, and Motivation involves brain processes that drive and direct behavior, including both conscious decisions and automatic responses.

Behavior-change frameworks, including the COM-B model, serve as foundational tools for understanding the factors that drive behavior and for designing effective interventions aimed at modifying those behaviors, particularly in the realm of dietary choices. The COM-B model is increasingly being used to design interventions for health behaviors like dietary practices (McEvoy et al., 2018) and to understand the multifaceted drivers of food choices, including the rising interest in AP consumption (Kuosmanen et al., 2023). The framework is particularly relevant to the current study of choice architecture interventions, as the latter target key components of the COM-B framework (Michie et al., 2014; Zaleskiewicz et al., 2024). By utilizing this model, research can systematically investigate the mechanisms through which food environment modifications can lead to changes in dietary behavior, contributing to a more theoretically grounded understanding of how to encourage the adoption of AP food choices.

Methodology and results

The current paper outlines the implementation of two Choice Architecture interventions, i.e. choice editing and choice expansion, incorporated into a Living Lab run in a tangible food environment (i.e. a university canteen and the surrounding premises) in Athens, Greece, in two consecutive studies (iterations), the 1st in the period March-April 2024 (choice editing) and the 2nd in the period October-November 2024 (choice expansion). The Living Lab in Athens is one of 11 Labs that run simultaneously in those time intervals in another 10 EU countries, whereas the here-described work-in-progress will be completed with the implementation of two more studies that involve additional types of choice architecture interventions, such as choice environment.

Study 1: Choice Editing

Meat-based dishes in the university canteen were gradually reduced over five working days, from reducing one dish from the usual three offered daily on the first day (Monday), to eliminating meat completely by the fifth day (Friday). One conventional exchange was implemented first, consisting of 2 focus groups of 10 participants each who were invited to dine at the canteen, order from the edited menu with the reduced meat options, and then participated to a semi-structured focus group

discussion; followed by one interaction at the point of consumption (university canteen), consisting of a survey run for all 5 consecutive days of the intervention with a total number of N=365 students and faculty ordering or consuming food in the canteen. The purpose of both the focus groups and the survey was to assess the perception of the participants about the choice editing intervention and related COM-B elements pertinent to their choices. Consumer perceptions on the choice editing intervention were also assessed.

Findings

The COM-B data triangulation and analysis conducted on Living Labs' study 1 revealed balanced perspectives regarding consumer readiness for alternative proteins (APs), with both significant barriers and benefits/enablers identified across all three behavioral dimensions - capability, motivation, opportunity.

Capability barriers predominantly centered around limited knowledge and awareness regarding APs, including concerns about safety, health implications, palatability, and ingredient sources. Participants demonstrated skepticism and misinformation triggered by lack of accreditation/certification, safety and nutritional concerns, and doubts about biological suitability, contributing to food neophobia. Emotional barriers and sustainability concerns were also identified. Conversely, capability benefits included openness to new protein sources despite initial reluctance, with nutritional value, taste, and dietary diversification as key drivers. Participants acknowledged potential normalization, historical context of AP consumption, environmental considerations favoring gradual adoption, and the role of education in generational perspectives.

Cost emerged as a primary motivation barrier, with comparison to meat prices, and parallels with organic products. Disgust and aversion toward certain AP sources (insects, krill, fungi) were prominent, alongside health and safety doubts regarding long-term effects and production methods. Social change difficulties were noted despite sustainability acknowledgments. Motivation benefits included health and nutritional benefits as strong motives, cost-effectiveness, taste and palatability considerations, environmental and ethical factors, and rational acceptance offering tangible consumer value.

Opportunity barriers predominantly involved cultural and social norms leading to resistance and low acceptance of APs compared to traditional proteins. The Greek and Mediterranean food cultures' perceived connection to meat presented challenges, requiring gradual social transformation. Social influence, peer pressure, and limited accessibility for economically disadvantaged populations constituted additional barriers. Opportunity enablers included social influence through peer recommendations, streamlined availability across retail and foodservice channels, and media influence through popular shows, advertising, and influencer endorsements.

Study 2: choice expansion

One conventional exchange consisting of 2 focus groups with 16 participants each was conducted. A set 3-course meal made from plant-based protein sources (edamame, pea sprouts, soy milk, and chia seeds) was served, followed by a buffet of packaged insect-based food products. Tasting was optional for the latter. Feedback on products' packaging was offered for the insect products and tasting feedback for all food products consumed. Consumer perceptions on the choice expansion intervention type were also assessed.

Findings

As in study 1, the findings in study 2 revealed distinct patterns of acceptance and resistance that can be systematically categorized according to the COM-B framework.

Capability: Participants demonstrated high sensory capability for plant-based alternatives, particularly appreciating the taste similarity to conventional meat of the starter (mini burger with gyro from pea sprouts). The main dish (edamame with chili) received positive evaluations for taste, texture, and visual appeal, while the desert (chocolate mousse with soy milk and chia seeds) elicited mixed responses regarding texture and sweetness levels. As far as the sensory perceptions of insect-based

products are concerned, significant capability barriers were evident, manifested into lower ratings across sensory dimensions (smell, appearance, texture, mouthfeel, taste) compared to plant-based alternatives. Visible insect parts presented strong psychological barriers to consumption triggering neophobia.

Motivation: High willingness to purchase and recommend (84.4% for edamame, 93.8% recommendation rate for mini burgers) demonstrated strong motivational factors. The perceived similarity to conventional proteins, especially for savory options, enhanced motivational readiness for adoption. As far as the sensory perceptions of insect-based products are concerned, motivational barriers were substantial, with only one in four participants expressing willingness to buy insect-based snacks. Many participants indicated they would only consider these options under extreme circumstances, such as food scarcity or drastic price differentials, highlighting significant motivational resistance.

Opportunity: Participants identified several pathways for enhancing AP adoption opportunities, such as consumer education, market-based strategies including product adaptation to local diets, celebrity endorsements, increased availability, and competitive pricing; as well as environmental and nutritional messaging as key motivating factors. Overall, post-workshop assessment revealed predominantly positive perception shifts toward alternative proteins, particularly plant-based options, though insect-based products continued to face skepticism despite priming. These findings suggest that while choice expansion interventions can effectively introduce consumers to alternative proteins, differential approaches may be required based on the specific alternative protein source being promoted.

Discussion

The findings from the 2 Living Lab studies provide valuable insights into the complex dynamics of AP adoption within the specific cultural context. When examined through the lens of existing literature on dietary behavior change, several important patterns and implications emerge.

The COM-B analysis reveals that dietary behavior is influenced by a constellation of interrelated factors, confirming Schleicher and Töller's (2024) assertion that nutrition choices are strongly socially and culturally shaped, with established habits proving resistant to change. This is particularly evident in the capability and opportunity barriers identified in both iterations, where Greek and Mediterranean food cultures' perceived connection to meat presented significant cultural resistance. As the findings demonstrate, participants explicitly noted that "*our societies are meat-centered and this needs to change*"; yet they simultaneously expressed attachment to their cultural culinary heritage.

The polarized reactions to the choice editing intervention further substantiate the literature's recognition that dietary behavior is influenced by a diverse array of factors including values, environmental awareness, or awareness of the consequences of one's own behavior (Schleicher & Töller, 2024). Participant responses highlight how these factors become activated in specific decision-making contexts, with some embracing restrictions as opportunities for "*healthier eating and sustainability reflection*", while others perceived the same intervention as an infringement on personal freedom.

The stark contrast in acceptance between plant-based and insect-based options across both interventions aligns with Siegrist et al. (2024) observation of an overall consumer resistance to significant dietary changes resulting in a likely slow transition. The capability findings from study 2 particularly demonstrate how sensory capabilities vary dramatically between protein alternatives. This differential response pattern supports Lopes' (2022) finding that certain alternative proteins generate higher interest and face fewer adoption barriers than others. However, the study extends this understanding by highlighting the importance of specific sensory attributes and cultural compatibility in determining acceptance levels. The mini burger with gyro from pea sprouts exemplifies this principle, receiving exceptional ratings largely due to its integration with familiar culinary expectations.

Furthermore, our findings provide empirical support for Schleicher and Töller's (2024) assertion that a variety of measures are needed to reduce meat consumption. Participants in both studies identified multiple pathways for enhancing adoption, including consumer education and market-based strategies.

Importantly, the research challenges Yamoah et al. (2022) suggestion for mandatory government intervention in sustainable consumption. Instead, the findings strongly emphasize that most participants endorsed gradual implementation coupled with educational initiatives, transparency, and preservation of limited choice. This aligns with Schleicher and Töller's (2024) observation that citizen participation in developing nutritional policy instruments is essential for acceptance, as demonstrated by the Living Labs methodology itself.

The workshop environment in study 2 created a unique context that facilitated social learning and direct experiential engagement with novel protein sources. This finding substantiates literature's emphasis on contextual conditions as critical determinants of sustainable food choices. As Schleicher and Töller (2024) note, environments in supermarkets, public canteens, or restaurants, can be designed in a way which makes sustainable nutritional choices the easier ones. The positive shifts in perception following the choice expansion intervention demonstrate how carefully designed contexts can activate latent environmental awareness and values.

A limitation acknowledged in literature and relevant to this study is what Abrahamse (2020) identifies as limited knowledge about the long-term effects of interventions. While the Living Labs approach provides valuable insights into initial consumer responses, the durability of the observed behavioral changes remains uncertain. This highlights the need for longitudinal research examining how the identified capability, opportunity, and motivation factors evolve over time. The findings also substantiate Siegrist et al. (2024) assertion that improving the taste and texture of meat substitutes alongside their nutritional value is important for broader consumer acceptance. Participants consistently emphasized sensory attributes alongside health benefits as critical adoption factors, suggesting that technological advancements in AP development should prioritize these dimensions simultaneously.

Conclusion

The findings of this survey-in-progress so far demonstrate that effective dietary transitions toward alternative proteins require nuanced, multi-component interventions that address all dimensions of the COM-B framework while respecting cultural contexts and preserving consumer autonomy. The distinct patterns of acceptance between plant-based and insect-based alternatives further indicate that intervention strategies should be tailored to specific protein sources rather than applied universally across the alternative protein spectrum.

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Like a PRO

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Social CRM and brand equity: The new springboard for loyalty in the FMCG food sector

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Abstract

In today's digital era, Social Customer Relationship Management (SCRM) has become a key driver for building strong brand-consumer relationships, especially within the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) food sector. This research explores how SCRM, by combining behavioral data with real-time social interactions, contributes to enhancing brand equity and strengthening attitudinal loyalty. Drawing from both qualitative and quantitative insights in the Moroccan context, the study highlights how personalized, responsive exchanges, emotionally engaging content, and alignment with consumer trends all serve to deepen brand attachment. Special attention is given to the emotional resonance of nostalgic content, the value of originality, and the consumer's desire for authenticity and trust. Dimensions such as e-WOM, entertainment, and personalization emerge as strategic levers within the Social CRM framework. The findings show that consumers respond positively to humanized digital experiences, and that emotional engagement—when grounded in consistent brand values—can foster long-term loyalty. This study offers strategic guidance for brands seeking to differentiate themselves and maintain relevance in a saturated, fast-changing digital landscape.

Keywords: Social CRM, SMME, Brand Equity, Attitudinal Loyalty, Food Marketing, Consumer Engagement

The value of hygiene and desirable features in semi-fermented fish products: An analysis of consumer awareness and willingness to pay (WTP)

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Abstract

Food safety shapes consumer perceptions of purchasing fish and fishery products. In Bangladesh, a range of semi-fermented fish is available. However, this study only focused on a popular product locally known as Chepa or Shidal, hereafter referred to as SFB. The evaluation of consumer awareness and willingness to pay (WTP) for SFB is essential to understand their perception of processed fishery products. This study investigated the factors influencing consumers' WTP for hygienic and safe SFB. Additionally, the choice of the retail market has been examined to assess future potential. A total of 229 SFB consumers were surveyed from the northeastern part of Bangladesh. The study employed various methods (factorial analysis, log-linear regression, and multinomial logit model) to unveil the factors affecting consumers' WTP and their decisions when shopping SFB. Results indicated that consumers prioritise the production method as the most influential factor when choosing safe SFB and are willing to pay a premium for it. Demographic factors, including age, occupation, marital status, family size, and monthly income, collectively significantly affected the quality parameters of SFB. However, factors such as gender, religion, and place of residence, although important, did not appear to influence the WTP of SFB significantly. From the perspective of age, knowledge, and attitudes, specific sub-variables within each category, namely "higher education", "higher level of knowledge, and "positive attitude", were found to have a significant impact on consumers' preference for SFB as an alternative to fresh fish and their WTP. Consumers with lower income and limited education but processing more product knowledge tended to opt for SFB due to its ease of cooking. Moreover, quality and taste were identified as the primary factors influencing the purchase of SFB, as consumers were WTP more.

The affective-motivational pathway to food waste reduction: An integrated cognitive-emotional model

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Abstract

This study presents the Affective-Motivational Pathway Model for Food Waste Reduction (AMP-FWR), a novel framework grounded in Affective-Reflective Theory and Approach-Avoidance Motivation Theory. The model integrates cognitive appraisals, affective evaluations, discrete emotional responses, behavioral intentions, and self-reported food waste behavior. It distinguishes between three types of general awareness—environmental, economic, and moral—as reflective antecedents of food waste attitudes, which in turn elicit both positive (e.g., pride, satisfaction) and negative (e.g., guilt, regret) emotions. These affective responses differentially contribute to the formation of behavioral intentions and influence actual food waste behaviors in terms of both frequency and amount. Based on a representative UK sample of 627 respondents and tested using structural equation modeling demonstrated good fit and strong explanatory power for food waste intentions. Notably, positive action-related emotions emerged as a stronger and more consistent predictor of food waste reduction behavior than negative action-related emotions. Additionally, direct paths from emotional responses to behavior—bypassing intentions—were identified, highlighting motivational mechanisms beyond the intention–behavior link. These findings provide a more comprehensive and psychologically grounded understanding of food waste behavior. They support the need for interventions that not only inform but also emotionally engage individuals in a constructive, empowering way. The modular nature of the AMP-FWR model also allows for future adaptation to other sustainability domains by integrating context-relevant cognitive and motivational variables.